

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D5.2. Report on biodiversity of soil micro- and macro-organisms in the different case studies in terms of cropping system, management practices and pedoclimatic region

Universidade de Vigo

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Table of contents

INTRODUCTION	6
1 PROKARYOTIC DIVERSITY	7
1.1 Introduction.....	7
1.2 Material and Methods.....	8
1.2.1 DNA extraction and purification for 16S rRNA gene sequencing	8
1.2.2 16s ribosomal RNA (rRNA) amplicon sequencing.....	8
1.2.3 Data processing and analysis.....	8
1.2.4 DNA extraction and purification for qPCR.....	9
1.2.5 qPCR determination of functional gene abundance	9
1.2.6 Statistical analysis.....	12
1.3 Results and discussion	12
1.3.1 Sequencing quality and taxonomic characterization	12
1.3.2 Alpha-diversity.....	17
1.3.3 Beta-diversity	23
1.3.4 Differential abundant bacterial taxa	31
1.3.5 Functional gene abundance	31
1.4 References.....	43
2 FUNGAL DIVERSITY	47
2.1 Introduction.....	47
2.2 Material and Methods.....	47
2.2.1 DNA extractions and sequencing	47
2.2.2 Bioinformatics	47
2.2.3 Community and statistical analyses	48
2.3 Results and discussion	49
2.3.1 Taxonomic profiles	49
2.3.2 Alpha-diversity.....	65
2.3.3 Beta-diversity	68
2.3.4 Fungal associated to agricultural practices	74
2.3.5 Functional fungal guilds.....	81
2.3.6 Conclusions	87
2.4 References	89
3 MICROBIAL BIOMASS CHARACTERIZATION	94
3.1 Introduction.....	94
3.2 Material and Methods.....	94
3.3 Results and discussion	95
3.3.1 Total microbial abundance.....	106

3.3.2	Total bacterial abundance.....	106
3.3.3	Total fungi abundance.....	108
3.3.4	Unespecif microbial.....	109
3.4	References.....	110
4	NEMATODE DIVERSITY.....	111
4.1	Introduction.....	111
4.2	Material and Methods.....	112
4.2.1	Introduction.....	112
4.2.2	Nematode extraction.....	113
4.2.3	Morphological analysis.....	113
4.2.4	Nematode community sequencing.....	113
4.2.5	Nematode community sequence analysis.....	114
4.2.6	Nematode functional diversity analysis.....	114
4.3	Results and discussion.....	115
4.3.1	Absolute number of nematodes.....	115
4.3.2	Taxonomic profiles.....	124
4.3.3	Alpha-diversity.....	141
4.3.4	Beta-diversity.....	150
4.3.5	Indicator nematode taxa per case-study.....	156
4.3.6	Nematode functional biodiversity.....	168
4.4	References.....	184
5	EARTHWORM DIVERSITY.....	187
5.1	Introduction.....	187
5.2	Material and Methods.....	188
5.3	Results and discussion.....	189
5.3.1	Total earthworm abundance.....	189
5.3.2	Total earthworm biomass.....	196
5.3.3	Earthworm species richness ecological.....	201
5.3.4	Abundance of ecological groups.....	204
5.3.5	<i>Abundance of age classes</i>	217
5.3.6	<i>Conclusions</i>	232
5.4	References.....	232
	ANNEXES-TABLES.....	235

Introduction

In Work Package 5 (WP5), a total of 15 case studies comprising 17 distinct field sites across six European pedoclimatic regions were established to investigate the impact of various agricultural practices on soil biological diversity. The study focused on key soil biota groups, namely prokaryotes (archaea and bacteria), fungi, nematodes, and earthworms. Sampling and methodology across all WP5 case studies followed a standardised protocol, as outlined in the WP5 Handbook (Soto Gómez et al., 2020).

Two case studies (CS1 and CS2) were implemented in the Mediterranean South region of southern Spain to assess the effects of different chemical and organic fertilisation strategies, both with and without the addition of bacterial and/or fungal inoculants.

Three case studies (CS3, CS4, and CS5) were carried out in the Lusitanian region of north-western Spain (Galicia), focusing on the impacts of crop diversification and trap crops, the incorporation of mycorrhizae, and the use of a pest alert system.

Four case studies (CS6, CS7, CS8, and CS9), located in the Atlantic Central region of Belgium, examined the application of organic fertilisers, the cultivation of complex cover crop mixtures to enhance cropping system diversity, and the comparison of different agricultural systems (intensive vs extensive; conventional vs organic).

Case studies CS10a, CS10b, and CS11, situated in the Continental region of Germany, aimed to identify management practices that foster fungivorous soil fauna communities, which may act as antagonists to fungal plant pathogens.

Case study CS12, conducted in the Nemoral region of Estonia, investigated the effects of pest alert systems, suitable crop diversification strategies, and varying tillage systems.

Finally, case studies undertaken in the Boreal region of Finland explored: (a) the application of two types of recycled organic soil amendments derived from paper mill by-products in early potato fields (CS13); (b) the introduction of two different cover crops in early potato cultivation (CS15); and (c) the timing of tillage, specifically spring tillage in spring wheat fields (CS14a) and autumn tillage in winter wheat fields (CS14b).

The case study sites were monitored over three consecutive years. Samples for the identification of soil organisms, as well as for soil chemical and physical analyses, were collected annually—either at the flag leaf stage (for prokaryotes, fungi, and nematodes) or in autumn prior to harvest (for earthworms). Detailed sampling procedures and methodologies are provided in the SoildiverAgro Handbook (Soto Gómez et al., 2020).

biological diversity in each case study site are presented in the report. In many instances, the findings are based solely on data collected during the final year of monitoring.

References

Soto Gómez, D., Fernández Calviño, D., Koefoed Brandt, K., Waeyenberge, L., Zornoza, R., Martínez, S. 2020. Handbook on case studies set up, protocols for sampling, sample procedure and analysis. 214 pages. https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/wp5-handbook-09_05_2022.pdf

Prokaryotic diversity

1.1 Introduction

The soil microbiome is crucial for the functioning of terrestrial ecosystems, contributing to soil structure formation, nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and pollutant biodegradation (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2020; Nazir et al., 2010; Nielsen et al., 2011; Van Der Heijden et al., 2008). Among soil microorganisms, prokaryotes are the most abundant and diverse, providing key ecosystem services linked to soil fertility, pest control, climate regulation, regulation of environmental quality and biodiversity (Barrios, 2007; Bender et al., 2016; Regan et al., 2014; Treseder et al., 2012). Maintaining high prokaryotic diversity in agricultural soils is thought to be critical for sustainable crop production, reducing disease impact, and ensuring soil multifunctionality (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2016; Mendes et al., 2011).

Agricultural practices can have profound impacts on the soil microbiome, especially those involving ecological disturbance. Intensive agriculture, characterized by practices like deep tillage, pesticide use, and high fertilization rates, may lead to a decline in soil microbial diversity, which can adversely affect soil health and productivity (Kennedy and Smith, 1995; Levine et al., 2011; Tilman et al., 2002). Conversely, organic farming, which limits the use of synthetic inputs, is generally associated with positive effects on soil biodiversity and health (Gomiero et al., 2011). Conservation agriculture practices, such as diversified crop rotations, reduced tillage, and the use of cover crops, are increasingly adopted by both conventional and organic farms as they may aid in enhancing soil biodiversity, reducing degradation, and improving carbon sequestration (Neupane et al., 2021; Shahbaz et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2019). These practices align well with the EU's Farm to Fork strategy, which aims to create a sustainable food system with a positive environmental impact, contributing to climate change mitigation and biodiversity preservation ("Farm to Fork Strategy, European Commission," 2023). However, comprehensive studies integrating the effects of agricultural practices on the soil prokaryotic microbiome with effects on other soil biomes (e.g. fungi, nematodes, earthworms) and other soil quality parameters (e.g. nutrients, pesticide residues, soil physicochemical parameters) remain limited.

Here, we present initial results from WP5 of the SoilDiverAgro project, investigating the effects of different agricultural practices on prokaryotic diversity, community composition and functionality, in field studies across various pedoclimatic regions of Europe.

1.2 Material and Methods

1.2.1 DNA extraction and purification for 16S rRNA gene sequencing

DNA extraction was performed in accordance with the SoilDiverAgro handbook on soil biodiversity analysis (Lassen and Brandt, 2020). In brief, DNA was extracted from 0.25 g of soil using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen) according to the instruction manual, except for the bead-beating step, which was conducted using the environmental sample setting on an MP Fastprep-24 instrument (MP-bio). Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen) and NanoDrop ND1000 (ThermoFisher Scientific) were employed for subsequent DNA quantification and purity assessment. Extracted DNA was stored at -20°C before 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing.

1.2.2 16s ribosomal RNA (rRNA) amplicon sequencing

PCR was used to amplify the V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene from both bacteria and archaea using the modified forward primer 515F (GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA) and the modified reverse primer 806R (GGACTACNVGGGTWTCTAAT) (Walters et al., 2016). A small-fragment library was constructed, followed by paired-end sequencing using a 300nt MiSeq sequencer at StarSEQ® GmbH (Germany).

1.2.3 Data processing and analysis

The paired-end reads obtained from amplicon sequencing were processed using the DADA2 package in R, following the DADA2 pipeline tutorial (v. 1.16). In summary, the reads were filtered, trimmed, dereplicated, and processed using DADA2's core sample inference algorithm and trained error models. High-quality paired-end reads were then merged, and chimeras were removed, resulting in a table of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) and their corresponding abundance in each sample. Taxonomic classification of ASVs was performed using the SILVA database (v.138.1) (Quast et al., 2013). ASVs identified as mitochondrial or chloroplast DNA were excluded from downstream analyses.

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.0.3 (R Core Team, 2018) and RStudio version 1.3.1093. Figures were generated using the R packages "microeco" (Liu et al., 2021), 'phyloseq' (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013), "vegan," and 'ggplot2' (Wickham, 2016). Significant differences in mean alpha diversity (Shannon indices and observed ASVs) between treatments in each case study were assessed using Duncan's multiple range test (Duncan, 1955). Beta diversity was analyzed using nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) combined with permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) on Bray-Curtis distance matrices, implemented through the adonis2 function in the vegan package (Anderson, 2001).

1.2.4 DNA extraction and purification for qPCR

Soil DNA was extracted from 0.25 g of soil using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). All procedures were done following the instruction manual, except for the bead-beating step, which was conducted using the environmental sample setting on an MP Fastprep-24 instrument (MP-bio, Solon, OH, USA). DNA for qPCRs was then purified using NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select (Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany). Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Life Technologies, Carlsbad, California, US) and NanoDrop ND1000 (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, US) were employed for subsequent DNA quantification and purity assessment. Extracted DNA was stored at -20°C until further analysis.

1.2.5 qPCR determination of functional gene abundance

For the construction of qPCR standards, DNA extracted from soil samples as described above served as the template of PCR reactions. PCRs were conducted using the primer pairs listed in Table 1.1.

The expected size of the PCR products was verified by electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel in TAE buffer stained with ethidium bromide. Amplicons were purified and quantified as described in step 2.1. The purified PCR product was ligated into the pGEM®-T Easy Vector Systems kit (Promega), and the resulting ligation products were used to transform into *Escherichia coli* JM109 competent cells (Promega) following the instructions of the manufacturer. Cloning screening was performed with reamplification using the vector-specific primers pUC/M13. DNA extraction of the identified positive clones was performed using the QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit (Qiagen) and quantified with Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen). The copy numbers of each of the genes of interest were calculated from the known concentration of the extracted DNA plasmid. Ten-fold serial dilutions of plasmids were run in each qPCR assay in triplicate to generate a standard curve. The abundance of the five different genes was determined by qPCR using the Rotor-Gene Q (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) using the same primers as for cloning. Each reaction was performed in a 20 µl volume containing 10 µl of PowerUp SYBR Green Master Mix (Applied Biosystems), 0.56 µl of bovine serum albumin (Invitrogen), 400 nM of each primer, 5 µl of DNA template, and nuclease-free water. Amplification conditions are described in Table 1.2.

A final dissociation stage (melt curve analysis) was performed to detect nonspecific amplification. qPCRs products were also checked on an 2% agarose gel electrophoresis to check the specificity of the amplification.

TABLE 1.1

TARGET GENES						
Code	<i>amoA</i>	<i>nirK</i>	<i>nifH</i>	<i>ureC</i>	<i>cbbL</i>	GH7
Gene definition	ammonia monooxygenase	nitrite reductase	nitrogenase reductase	urease	cbbL red-like gene	cellulose degradation
Primer names	amoA1F amoA1R	nirK876F nirK1040R	PolF PolR	ureC-F ureC-R	cbbL-RedF cbbL-RedR	GH7-F GH7-R
Primer sequence (5'-3')(*)	GGGGTTT CTACTGG TGGT CCCCTCK GSAAAGC CTTCTTC	ATYGGCG GVCA YGG CGA GCCTCGA TCAGRTT RTGGTT	TGC GAY CCS AAR GCB GAC TC ATSGCCA TCATYTC RCCGGA	TGGGC CTTAA AATHC AYGAR GAYT GGG GGTG GTGGC ACACC ATNAN CATRTC	AAGGAYGACGA GAACATC TCGGTCGGSGT GTAGTTGAA	GAGATCAAG CGCYTCTAYG TBCA GTCRAGCCA SAGCATGTT GG
Ta (°C)	57	58	55	50/55	57	56
Amplicon size (bp)	491	165	362	340	-	242
Reference	Rotthauwe et al., 1997.	Henry et al., 2004.	Poly et al. (2001)	Reed (2001)	Selesi et al., 2005.	Tian et al., 2017.

Table 1.1. Primer pairs for each gene of interest. (*) Sequence of forward and reverse primer.

TABLE 1.2

STEP	# OF CYCLES	TEMPERATURE	TIME
<i>amoA</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	15 sec
Annealing		58°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	45 sec
<i>nirK</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	25 sec
Annealing		60°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec
<i>nifH</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	5 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	30 sec
Annealing		56°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec
<i>ureC</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	30 sec
Annealing		56°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec
<i>cbbL</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	1 min
Annealing		57°C	2 min
Extension		72°C	2 min
GH7			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	30 sec
Annealing		56°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec

Table 1.2. PCR cycling conditions for the different target genes.

1.2.6 Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.0.2 (R Core Team 2020) and R studio version 1.3.1073. All figures were made using 'ggplot2' (Wickham, 2016) R package. Significant differences in mean functional genes abundances between treatments in case studies with two treatments (CS14a and CS14b), were tested using a Mann-Whitney U test (Mann & Whitney, 1947; Wilcoxon, 1945). Differences in mean functional genes abundances between treatments in case studies with three or more treatments (CS1 to CS13 and CS15), were assessed with Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952). When significant values were obtained, a further analysis with a Dunn's test (Dunn, 1964) comparison procedure was performed as a post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) to control for multiple testing.

1.3 Results and discussion

1.3.1 Sequencing quality and taxonomic characterization

After quality filtering, a total of 6,296,484 reads were obtained for Case Study 1, with read counts per sample ranging from 25,968 to 54,072. For Case Study 2, 426,059 reads were obtained, with counts ranging from 28,434 to 40,207 per sample. In Case Study 1, the reads were classified into 3,932 ASVs across 885 genera and 43 phyla. In Case Study 2, the reads were classified into 3,731 ASVs across 669 genera and 39 phyla. Case Study 1 was predominantly composed of Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, and Actinobacteriota, while Case Study 2 was dominated by Actinobacteriota, Proteobacteria, and Acidobacteriota (Figure 1.1). No clear differences were observed between treatment groups.

Figure 1.1: Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla in Case Studies 1 and 2 (CS1 and CS2) from the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations for CS1 are: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50%; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50% plus “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant. Abbreviations for CS2 are: Ctrl, control with standard organic fertilization; org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial inoculant; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial and fungal inoculants.

For Case Studies 3, 4, and 5, a total of 348,711, 841,380, and 482,996 reads were obtained after quality filtering, respectively. In Case Study 3, the read counts ranged from 26,344 to 48,942 per sample, classified into 2,938 ASVs across 792 genera and 39 phyla. Case Study 4 had read counts ranging from 24,534 to 58,488 per sample, classified into 5,599 ASVs across 978 genera and 48 phyla. For Case Study 5, read counts ranged from 38,708 to 92,945 per sample, classified into 3,144 ASVs across 649 genera and 35 phyla. The Lusitanian case studies were primarily dominated by Actinobacteria, Proteobacteria, and Firmicutes (Figure 1.2). In Case Study 3, there was a slight increase in Proteobacteria when alternative crop rotation 2 (Alt2Pot) was used, with a corresponding reduction in Acidobacteria compared to the control and Alt1Pot treatment. In Case Study 5, a clear reduction in Proteobacteria and Acidobacteria was observed when no fungicide was applied (PotNoFA), while Firmicutes and Chloroflexi among others were enriched compared to the control treatment (pest alert system control in potato).

Figure 1.2: Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla in Case Studies 3, 4, and 5 (CS3, CS4, and CS5) from the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS3 are: Ctrl, control with

conventional potato treatment; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field. Abbreviations for CS4 are: Ctrl, control with conventional P fertilization in potato; MycNoP, mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization in potato; MycPotHP, mycorrhizal inoculant plus half the P fertilization in potato; PotHP, half the P fertilization in potato; PotNoP, potato field with no P fertilization. Abbreviations for CS5 are: Ctrl, pest alert system control in potato; ConvPotFA, conventional fungicide application in potato; PotNoFA, potato without fungicide application.

For the case studies in the Atlantic Central region, the number of reads after quality filtering were 775,161, 543,672, 461,539, and 464,529 for Case Studies 6, 7, 8, and 9, respectively. In Case Study 6, the read counts ranged from 32,453 to 67,792 per sample, classified into 4,084 ASVs across 784 genera and 41 phyla. For Case Study 7, reads ranged from 30,610 to 44,364 per sample, classified into 5,160 ASVs across 971 genera and 44 phyla. In Case Study 8, read counts ranged from 22,905 to 36,836 per sample, classified into 5,664 ASVs across 1,059 genera and 51 phyla. For Case Study 9, read counts ranged from 32,399 to 34,123 per sample, classified into 4,084 ASVs across 784 genera and 41 phyla. Case Studies 6 and 9 were predominantly composed of Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Acidobacteria, while Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, and Actinobacteriota were the dominant phyla in Case Studies 7 and 8 (Figure 1.3). No apparent major impact of the tested treatments was observed across the case studies.

Figure 1.3: Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla in Case Studies 6, 7, 8, and 9 (CS6, CS7, CS8, and CS9) from the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS6: Ctrl = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, FYM = with farm yard manure; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed; AFVFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material; brFYM = farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves). Abbreviations for CS7 are: Ctrl, standard conditions for potato as control; PhaEgClov, Phacelia and Egyptian

clover as cover crops for potato; Mix5, mixture of 5 cover crop species for potato; Mix12, mixture of 12 cover crop species for potato. Abbreviations for CS8 are: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables. Abbreviations for CS9 are: Ctrl, control wheat field without manure; Comp, composted green manure for wheat; FYM, farmyard manure for wheat; Ferm, fermented green manure for wheat.

After quality filtering, the number of reads in the Continental region case studies were 416,868, 338,562, and 589,949 for Case Studies 10a, 10b, and 11, respectively. In Case Study 10a, read counts ranged from 30,704 to 52,897 per sample, classified into 5,100 ASVs across 1,066 genera and 49 phyla. For Case Study 10b, read counts ranged from 30,817 to 41,681 per sample, classified into 4,148 ASVs across 1,066 genera and 49 phyla. In Case Study 11, read counts ranged from 29,758 to 71,955 per sample, classified into 5,828 ASVs across 811 genera and 41 phyla. The case studies involving wheat as the crop species (Case Studies 10a and 11) were predominantly composed of Proteobacteria, Actinobacteriota, and Acidobacteriota, while Case Study 10b, with potato as the crop species, was dominated by Proteobacteria, Actinobacteriota, Firmicutes, and Acidobacteriota (Figure 1.4). No major differences between treatments were observed across the case studies.

Figure 1.4: Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla in Case Studies 10a, 10b, and 11 (CS10a, CS10b, and CS11) from the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS10a are: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation with reduced fungicides as control; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), and reduced fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G), and reduced fungicides. Abbreviations for CS10b are: Ctrl, standard crop management for potato as control; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing. Abbreviations for CS11 are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides.

For Case Study 12 in the Nemoral region, 266,929 reads were obtained after quality filtering. The read counts ranged from 26,922 to 48,963 per sample, classified into 3,910 ASVs across 853 genera and 44 phyla. The most abundant phyla were Proteobacteria, Actinobacteriota, and Acidobacteriota, with no apparent differences observed between field treatments (Figure 1.5).

Figure 1.5: Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla in Case Study 12 (CS12) from the Nemoral pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage; ConVNoTill, conventional farming without tillage; FieldEdge, conditions at the edge of the field.

For the case studies in the Boreal region, the number of reads after quality filtering were 367,680, 222,044, 250,663, and 272,612 for Case Studies 13, 14a, 14b, and 15, respectively. In Case Study 13, read counts ranged from 24,950 to 62,133 per sample, classified into 4,540 ASVs across 962 genera and 48 phyla. For Case Study 14a, reads ranged from 32,460 to 33,896 per sample, classified into 3,442 ASVs across 953 genera and 48 phyla. In Case Study 14b, read counts ranged from 27,012 to 37,195 per sample, classified into 3,362 ASVs across 953 genera and 48 phyla. For Case Study 15, read counts ranged from 22,512 to 30,774 per sample, classified into 4,164 ASVs across 905 genera and 49 phyla. The most abundant phyla across all case studies were Proteobacteria, Acidobacteriota, and Actinobacteriota (Figure 1.6). No apparent impact of treatments was observed across the case studies.

Figure 1.6: Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla in Case Studies 13, 14a, 14b, and 15 (CS13, CS14a, CS14b, and CS15) from the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS13 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment. Abbreviations for CS15 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after early potato harvest; rye, mixture of rye grass as cover crop after early potato harvest. Abbreviations for CS14a are: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring. Abbreviations for CS14b are: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn.

1.3.2 Alpha-diversity

In Case Studies 1 and 2, alpha diversity was not significantly affected by the fertilization treatments compared to the control treatments with standard conventional and organic fertilization, respectively. However, in case study 1, a slight increasing trend was observed for samples treated with the reduced fertilization treatments relative to the control (Figure 1.7).

Figure 1.7. Shannon indices (Shannon) and Observed number of Amplicon Sequence Variants (Observed) for samples of case studies 1 and 2 (CS1 and CS2, respectively) located at the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS1 are: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50%; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50% plus “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant. Abbreviations for CS2 are: Ctrl, control with standard organic fertilization; org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial inoculant; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial and fungal inoculants. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using Dunn's test following a Kruskal-Wallis analysis and is indicated by letters a-c).

In the Lusitanian region, only Case Study 3 was significantly impacted by the tested crop rotation treatments (Figure 1.8). Specifically, the alternative crop rotation 2 (Alt2Pot) resulted in a significantly increased number of observed ASVs compared to the alternative crop rotation 1 treatment. However, the increased number of observed ASVs in the Alt2Pot treatment did not significantly differ from the conventional control treatment.

Figure 1.8. Shannon indices (Shannon) and Observed number of Amplicon Sequence Variants (Observed) for samples of the case study 3, 4 and 5 (CS3, CS4 and CS5, respectively) located at the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS3 are: Ctrl, control with conventional potato treatment; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field. Abbreviations for CS4 are: Ctrl, control with conventional P fertilization in potato; MycPotHP, mycorrhizal inoculant plus half the P fertilization in potato; MycNoP, mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization in potato; PotHP, half the P fertilization in potato; PotNoP, potato field with no P fertilization. Abbreviations for CS5 are: Ctrl, pest alert system control in potato; ConvPotFA, conventional fungicide application in potato; PotNoFA, potato without fungicide application. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using Dunn's test following a Kruskal-Wallis analysis and is indicated by letters a-c. Figure x. Average number of observed OTUs between agricultural management systems in the case studies implemented from each pedoclimatic region: CS1-2 (Mediterranean South), CS3-5 (Lusitanian), CS6-9 (Atlantic Central), CS10-11 (Continental), CS12 (Nemoral), CS13-15 (Boreal). Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue. Significant differences in values were obtained with t-test (p -values: **** < 0.0001 , *** < 0.001 , ** < 0.01 , * < 0.05).

Alpha diversity was not impacted by the treatments in case studies 6-9 of the Atlantic central region.

Figure

1.9. Shannon indices (Shannon) and Observed number of Amplicon Sequence Variants (Observed) for samples of the case study 6, 7, 8 and 9 (CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9, respectively) located at the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS6: Ctrl = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, FYM = with farm yard manure; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed; AFVbrFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material; brFYM = farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves). Abbreviations for CS7: Ctrl, standard conditions fro potato as control; PhaEgClov, Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crop for potato; Mix5, mixture of 5 cover crop species fro potato; Mix12, mixture of 12 cover crop species fro potato. Abbreviations for CS8: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables. Abbreviations for CS9: Ctrl, control wheat field without manure; Comp, composted green manure for wheat; FYM, farmyard manure for wheat; Ferm, fermented green manure for wheat. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using Dunn's test following a Kruskal-Wallis analysis and is indicated by letters a-c.

No significant differences between treatments were observed for the case studies of the continental region (Figure 1.10).

Figure

1.10. Shannon indices (Shannon) and Observed number of Amplicon Sequence Variants (Observed) for samples of the case study 10a, 10b and 11 (CS10a, CS10b, and CS11, respectively) located at the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS10a are: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation with reduced fungicides as control; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), and reduced fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G), and reduced fungicides. Abbreviations for CS10b are: Ctrl, standard crop management for potato as control; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing. Abbreviations for CS11 are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using Dunn's test following a Kruskal-Wallis analysis and is indicated by letters a-c.

No differences in alpha diversity metrics were observed for case study 12 of the nemoral region (Figure 1.11).

Figure 1.11. Shannon indices (Shannon) and Observed number of Amplicon Sequence Variants (Observed) for samples of the case study 12(CS12, respectively) located at the Nemoral pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage; ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage. FieldEdge, conditions in the edge of the field. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using Dunn's test following a Kruskal-Wallis analysis and is indicated by letters a-c.

None of the case studies in the Boreal region showed significant differences in alpha diversity across treatments (Figure 1.12), indicating a limited impact of the tested agricultural practices on prokaryotic alpha diversity.

Figure 1.12. Shannon indices (Shannon) and Observed number of Amplicon Sequence Variants (Observed) for samples of the case study 13, 14a, 14b and 15 (CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15 respectively) located at the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS13: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment. Abbreviations for CS15: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after the early potato harvest; rye, mixture of and rye grass as cover crop after the early potato harvest. Abbreviations for CS14a: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring. Abbreviations for CS14b: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using Dunn's test following a Kruskal-Wallis analysis and is indicated by letters a-c.

1.3.3 Beta-diversity

Beta diversity was significantly affected ($p < 0.05$) by the reduced chemical fertilization regimes in Case Study 1 of the Mediterranean South region, with a slight separation observed between the Control treatment with conventional chemical fertilization and the other treatments with reduced chemical fertilization (Figure 1.13 and Table 1.3). In contrast, Case Study 2 showed no significant differences between the treatments and the control.

Figure

1.13. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 1 and 2 (CS1 and CS2, respectively) implemented in the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS1 are: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50%; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50% plus “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant. Abbreviations for CS2 are: Ctrl, control with standard organic fertilization; org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial inoculant; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial and fungal inoculants. The number in the top-right corner of each plot indicate the stress level of the NMDS ordination

In the Lusitanian region, both Case Study 4 and Case Study 5 were significantly impacted by the implemented treatments (Figure 1.14 and Table 1.3). Particularly in Case Study 5, a clear separation was observed for the treatment with no fungicide application (PotNoFA) compared to the control and conventional fungicide treatment (ConvPotFA). No significant effects were noted in Case Study 3.

Figure 1.14. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 3, 4 and 5 (CS3, CS4 and CS5, respectively) implemented in the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS3 are: Ctrl, control with conventional potato treatment; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field. Abbreviations for CS4 are: Ctrl, control with conventional P fertilization in potato; MycPotHP, mycorrhizal inoculant plus half the P fertilization in potato; MycNoP, mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization in potato; PotHP, half the P fertilization in potato; PotNoP, potato field with no P fertilization. Abbreviations for CS5 are: Ctrl, pest alert system control in potato; ConvPotFA, conventional fungicide application in potato; PotNoFA, potato without fungicide application. The number in the top-right corner of each plot indicate the stress level of the NMDS ordination.

In the Atlantic Central region, Case Studies 8 and 9 were significantly impacted by the treatments (Figure 1.15 and Table 1.3). In Case Study 8, a clear separation was observed between conventionally (ConvExt and ConvInt) and organically (OrgExt and OrgInt) farmed samples. In Case Study 9, the impact of the treatments was less distinct. No significant effects were observed in Case Studies 6 and 7.

Figure

1.15. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 6, 7, 8 and 9 (CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9, respectively) implemented in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS6: Ctrl = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, FYM = with farm yard manure; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed; AFVbrFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material; brFYM = farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves). Abbreviations for CS7 are: Ctrl, standard conditions for potato as control; PhaEgClov, Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crops for potato; Mix5, mixture of 5 cover crop species for potato; Mix12, mixture of 12 cover crop species for potato. Abbreviations for CS8 are: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables. Abbreviations for CS9 are: Ctrl, control wheat field without manure; Comp, composted green manure for wheat; FYM, farmyard manure for wheat; Ferm, fermented green manure for wheat. The number in the top-right corner of each plot indicate the stress level of the NMDS ordination.

No significant impact on beta diversity was observed in the case studies of the Continental pedoclimatic region (Figure 1.16 and Table 1.3).

Figure 1.16. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 10a, 10b, and 11 (CS10a, CS10b and CS11, respectively) implemented in the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS10a are: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation with reduced fungicides as control; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), and reduced fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G), and reduced fungicides. Abbreviations for CS10b are: Ctrl, standard crop management for potato as control; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing. Abbreviations for CS11 are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; ExtWhw, extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides. The number in the top-right corner of each plot indicate the stress level of the NMDS ordination.

The sample size of the case study 12 of the Nemoral region were too small to conduct any statistical analysis, however, based on the NMDS plot, no apparent impact of the treatments were observed (Figure 1.17).

Figure 1.17. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case study 12 (CS12) implemented in the Nemoral pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage; ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage. FieldEdge, conditions in the edge of the field. The number in the top-right corner of each plot indicate the stress level of the NMDS ordination.

No statistically significant impact on beta diversity was detected in the Boreal case studies (Figure 1.18 and Table 1.3).

Figure 1.18. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15 (CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15, respectively) implemented in the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS13 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment. Abbreviations for CS15 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after early potato harvest; rye, mixture of rye grass as cover crop after early potato harvest. Abbreviations for CS14a are: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring. Abbreviations for CS14b are: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn. The number in the top-right corner of each plot indicate the stress level of the NMDS ordination.

Table 1.3. Results of PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of treatment (agricultural practice) conducted in different case studies on prokaryotic community composition for the last monitoring year. Differences are considered significant if $P \leq 0.05$.

REGION	CASE STUDY	SOURCE	R2	F	P
Mediterranean South	CS1	Treatment	0.26209	1.4207	0.004
		Residuals	0.73790		
	CS2	Treatment	0.21535	1.0977	0.122
		Residuals	0.78465		
Lusitanian	CS3	Treatment	0.21581	1.2383	0.086
		Residuals	0.78419		
	CS4	Treatment	0.29912	1.6005	0.001
		Residuals	0.70087		
	CS5	Treatment	0.41943	2.1674	0.006
		Residuals	0.58056		
Atlantic Central	CS6	Treatment	0.21731	0.9995	0.464
		Residuals	0.78268		
	CS7	Treatment	0.18817	0.9272	0.88
		Residuals	0.81182		
	CS8	Treatment	0.34151	2.0745	0.001
		Residuals	0.65848		
	CS9	Treatment	0.21999	1.1282	0.024
		Residuals	0.78000		
Continental	CS10a	Treatment	0.20070	1.12996	0.265
		Residuals	0.79929		
	CS10b	Treatment	0.19300	1.07622	0.154
		Residuals	0.80699		
CS11	Treatment	0.18953	1.05231	0.295	
	Residuals	0.81047			
Boreal	CS13	Treatment	0.16364	0.08804	0.779
		Residuals	0.83636		
	CS14a	Treatment	0.13146	0.90820	0.707
		Residuals	0.86853		
	CS14b	Treatment	0.13162	0.90945	0.771
		Residuals	0.86837		
	CS15	Treatment	0.17577	0.95965	0.713
		Residuals	0.82423		

1.3.4 Differential abundant bacterial taxa

In the previous report (D3.3) from WP3, we used the differential abundance analysis ANCOMBC (Lin and Peddada, 2020) to investigate significant associations between specific prokaryotic taxa and agricultural management practices (Organic vs. Conventional) across the pedoclimatic regions. However, the case studies of WP5 do not meet the minimum sample size requirement (>5) for this analysis, and it could therefore not be conducted for these samples.

1.3.5 Functional gene abundance

The abundance of six genes involved in the carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles were quantified using quantitative PCR (qPCR). These genes, encode for enzymes involved in processes such as nitrification (*amoA*), denitrification (*nirK*), N fixation (*nifH*), ammonification (*ureC*), carbon fixation (*cbbL*), or carbon degradation (GH7). Here, we show the results obtained from the last monitoring year.

In the Mediterranean South region (CS1 and CS2 sites), the abundance of the six targeted functional genes was statistically significant only in case study 1 fields and for the *nirK* and the *cbbL* genes (Figs 1.19a-f and Figs 1.20a-f).

In case study 1, fields with a reduced chemical fertilization by 50% (fert50) and inoculated with plant growth-promoting bacteria (red50Bacto) presented a lower abundance of the gene *nirK* relative to the control treatments (Fig 1.19b). This pattern was also observed for the *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7 genes (Figs 1.19c-f). The *cbbL* gene abundance, however, was higher in the treatments undergoing a reduced chemical fertilization together with the addition of both bacterial and fungal inoculants (red50Nuve) compared to fields with just reduced chemical fertilization (fert50) (Fig 1.19e).

In case study 2, a reduced abundance for the *amoA* gene was found in the treatment where a reduced organic fertilization plus bacterial inoculant was applied (org70BioBa) (Fig 1.20a), whereas the rest of the genes presented a rather even abundance between treatments and controls (Figs 1.20b-f).

Figure 1.19. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and *GH7*) for samples of case study 1 (CS1) located at the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS1 are: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50%; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50% plus “Nuve” inoculant (fungi + bacteria); red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” inoculant (plant growth-promoting bacteria). Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test followed by a Dunn’s test.

Figure 1.20. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and *GH7*) for samples of case study 2 (CCS2) located at the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS2 are: Ctrl, control with standard organic fertilization; org70,

by 70% plus bacterial inoculant; org70BioBaFun, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial and fungal inoculants. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

No statistical differences were detected between control and treatments in the Lusitanian case studies (CS3, CS4 and CS5) (Figs 1.21a-f, 1.22a-f and 1.23a-f) for any of the six quantified genes.

In case study 3, nevertheless, samples from the alternative crop rotation 1 system (Alt1Pot), presented an increased trend for all the genes except for the *amoA* gene, while the opposite trend was observed for samples from the alternative crop rotation 2 system (Alt2Pot) (Figs 1.21a-f).

In case study 4 fields, also a trend was observed where, in all the genes with the exception of *nifH*, increased abundances were found in the control and mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization (MycNoP) while the opposite was observed in samples where a mycorrhizal inoculant plus half P fertilization was added (MycPotHP), as well as in samples with no P fertilization (PotNoP) (Figs 1.22a-f).

In case study 5, generally, increased abundances were found in fields where conventional fungicide was applied (ConvPotFA) or not applied in relation to the control (Fig 1.23a-f).

Figure 1.21. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 3 (CS3) located at the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS3 are: Ctrl, control with conventional potato treatment; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 1.22. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case studies 4 (CS4) located at the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS4 are: Ctrl, control with conventional P fertilization in potato; MycPotHP, mycorrhizal inoculant plus half the P fertilization in potato; MycNoP, mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization in potato; PotHP, half the P fertilization in potato; PotNoP, potato field with no P fertilization. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 1.23. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 5 (CS5) located at the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS5 are: Ctrl, pest alert system control in potato; ConvPotFA, conventional fungicide application in potato; PotNoFA, potato without fungicide application. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

In the Atlantic Central region, no statistical differences were detected in any of the six functional genes studied in CS6 (Figs 1.24a-f). However, a trend was observed depicting greater abundances in both AFVfYm (cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure) and farm yard manure (FYM) and lower in AFVbrFYm (cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure and “brown” co-composted straw), and farm yard manure composted with ‘brown’ material (brFYm) (Figs 1.24a-f).

In CS7, significant differences were found for the content of the *nirK* and *ureC* genes (Figs 1.25 b and d) with an increased abundance found for the *nirK* gene in the mixture of 5 cover crop species (Mix5) relative to the mixture of 12 cover crop species (Mix12). Regarding the content of the *ureC* gene, a decreased abundance was found in the mixture of 12 cover crop species (Mix12) compared to the control. Also, a trend where Control and Mix5 were characterized with the highest abundance was observed across all genes except for *amoA* and *nifH* (Figs 1.25 b, d e and f).

CS8 presented significant differences in the abundance of genes *amoA*, *nirK*, and GH7 (Figs 1.26 a,b and f). The *amoA* and *nirK* content was higher in conventional extensive farming (ConvExt) compared to organic intensive farming (OrgInt), while GH7 exhibited a decreased amount in conventional intensive farming (ConvInt) relative to organic extensive farming (OrgExt). A pattern of reduced functional gene abundance was observed in organic intensive farming (OrgInt) across all genes except for GH7 (Figs 1.26 a-e).

No differences were detected between control and treatments in CS9 although as a general pattern, increased abundances were found in all the treatments relative to the control (Figs 1.27 a-f).

Figure 1.24. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbtL* and GH7) for samples of case study 6 (CS6) located at the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS6: Ctrl = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, FYM = with farm yard manure; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed; AFVfYm = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYm = cover crop mowed and removed with

farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material; brFYM = farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves). Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 1.25. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 7 (CS7) located at the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS7: Ctrl, standard conditions from potato as control; PhaEgClov, Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crop for potato; Mix5, mixture of 5 cover crop species from potato; Mix12, mixture of 12 cover crop species from potato. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test followed by a Dunn's test.

Figure 1.26. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 8 (CS8) located at the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS8: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test followed by a Dunn's test.

Figure 1.27. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) for samples of case study 9 (CS9) located at the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS9: Ctrl, control wheat field without manure; Comp, composted green manure for wheat; FYM, farmyard manure for wheat; Ferm, fermented green manure for wheat. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Continental case studies (CS10a, CS10b and CS11) did not present statistical differences between treatments (Figs 1.28a-f, 1.29a-f and 1.30a-f).

In case study 10a, worth mentioning is a clear tendency of conventional samples in which an additive, plant biostimulant, plant adjuvant, and reduced fungicides (BiostimAdj) were applied to be characterized by higher values in all the genes (Figs 1.28a-f).

In CS11, diversified extensive farming with wide seed rows, clover undersowing, and not pesticides (DivExtWhe) presented higher abundances in all genes except for *nifH*.

Figure 1.28. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) for samples of case study 10a (CS10a) located at the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS10a are: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation with reduced fungicides as control; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), and reduced fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G), and reduced fungicides. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 1.29. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 10b (CS10b) located at the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS10b are: Ctrl, standard crop management for potato as control; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 1.30. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 11 (CS11) located at the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS11 are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat

farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Statistics for CS12 in the Nemoral region could not be conducted, since there were only two replicate plots in this field site (Figs 1.31a-f).

Figure 1.31. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 12 (CS12, respectively) located at the Nemoral pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage; ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage. FieldEdge, conditions in the edge of the field. Statistics could not be conducted since there were only two replicate plots from the CS12 field site.

No statistical differences were detected in boreal case studies CS13 and CS14a (Figs 1.32a-f and 1.33a-f).

In case study 14a (CS14b), however, a slight reduced abundance in wheat farming with ploughing tillage (plough) was found in all genes except for *amoA* (1.33a-f).

In CS14b, a significant lower abundance of *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL*, and GH7 genes were found in organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn (plough) with the same trend observed for the remaining genes (*amoA* and *nirK*) (Figs 1.34c-f).

In case study 15 (CS15), a decreased amount for the *ureC* gene was obtained after the use of *Phacelia* as a cover crop (*pha*) relative to the fields where a mixture of and rye grass was employed as a cover crop (rye) (Fig 1.35d).

Figure 1.32. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and *GH7*) for samples of case study 13 (CS13) located at the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS13: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 1.33. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and *GH7*) for samples of case study 14a (CS14a) located at the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS14a: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in

spring. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 1.34. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 14b (CS14b) located at the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations for CS14b: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test followed by a Dunn's test.

Figure 1.35. Boxplot showing the abundance (gene copy number per gram of soil) of the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) for samples of case study 15 (CS15) located at the Boreal pedoclimatic

cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after the early potato harvest; rye, as cover crop after the early potato harvest. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatment groups were investigated using a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test followed by a Dunn's test.

1.4 References

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2 Fungal diversity

2.1 Introduction

Fungi play important part in agroecosystems, since they are involved in principal ecosystem services of soil, e.g., the decomposition of variety of organic compounds, maintenance of the physical soil structure and the water balance, producing of plant-growth promoting substances and acting as biological controllers of plant diseases (Frąc et al., 2018). Not all fungi are harmless, and climate warming are suggested to increase the abundance of soil-borne potential fungal plant pathogens (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2020). On the other hand, symbiotic soil fungi are suggested to enhance ecosystem resilience to climate change (Martínez-García et al. 2017). Disturbances or unbalances in fungal community may have detrimental effects on carbon and nutrient cycles or soil structure reflecting on soil and plant health and eventually on crop yields causing economic losses.

Agricultural practices modify soil chemical and physical conditions and thus also impact fungal community. It has been discussed that agricultural management strategies that aim at restoring fungal biodiversity could effectively diminish chemical, biological and ecological degradation of arable soils and mitigate nutrient and C loss, soil erosion, acidification, pollution and desertification (Hannula and Morriën 2022). Here we report about the first results about the investigations of WP5, where the effects of variety of agricultural practices on diversity and community composition of fungi conducted in separate field case studies reaching six different European regions. Report includes the fungal results mostly only from the last monitoring year.

2.2 Material and Methods

2.2.1 DNA extractions and sequencing

DNA extraction and sequencing of fungal ITS region was conducted similar to previous report D3.2 according to protocol described in the D3.1 Handbook (Lloret et al., 2020). For practical reasons, sequencing was conducted in several batches. Average size of sample libraries (raw reads) for each case study in different monitoring years are represented in Table A1 in Annex).

2.2.2 Bioinformatics

Raw fungal ITS sequence data was processed with Pipegraph version 2.0 following the OTU pipeline workflow with same parameters used in the previous report D3.2. Data sets for each case study from different years were separated for the clustering of OTUs and taxonomic annotation steps. Average size of sample libraries after filtering steps in different monitoring years are represented in Table A1 in Annex. However, due to the large differences in sequencing depths between the first and the following two monitoring years, case studies data sets for each year were investigated separately.

2.2.3 Community and statistical analyses

For all fungal analyses we used RStudio version 2023.9.0.463 (Posit team 2023) and R version 4.4.0 (R Core Team 2024). The composition of fungal taxa in each case study was investigated with phyloseq by using functions `prune_taxa` and `aggregate_rare` at Family level with detection threshold 0.02 and with prevalence as two from total amount samples. Figures were created with `ggplot2` (Wickham 2016) and `phyloseq` (McMurdie & Holmes 2013) packages. Alpha diversity metrics (OTU numbers, Shannon index) were obtained from the `phyloseq` objects with `microbiome` package (Lahti et al. 2017). Fungal guilds were obtained from taxonomically parsed fungal OTUs data using FUNGuild which a Python-based tool (Nguyen et al. 2016). The community composition was investigated with non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) or principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) in `vegan` package (Oksanen et al. 2024). The effects on practices on community composition with `permanova` using functions `adonis2` with 999 permutations and `pairwise.adonis` in `vegan`. Microbiome multivariable association with linear models (MaAsLin) method was applied to reveal significant associations between fungal OTUs and agricultural practices (Treatments) conducted in each case study by using `MaAsLin2` package (Mallick et al. 2021).

Alpha-diversity and fungal guild was analyzed using generalized linear mixed models (GLMM). Treatments were compared to the control treatment within experiments and years, and therefore the fixed effects of the models consisted of experiment, treatment, year, and all of their interactions. Random effects were block within experiment, experiment and year and experiment and treatment. The assumptions of gamma (with log link) and Gaussian (with identity link) distributions were applied to all six dependent variables. All models were fitted by using the residual pseudo likelihood (for gamma) or restricted maximum likelihood (for Gaussian) estimation method, respectively. The former was chosen due to the skewed distribution of the dependent variables and to minimize variation between experiments. Diagnostic plots were used to confirm the normality of residuals. Dunnett's method was employed for pairwise comparisons of treatments against the control treatment. A significance level of $\alpha=0.05$ was used for all analyses. Degrees of freedom were calculated using the Kenward-Roger method. The analyses were performed using the GLIMMIX procedure in SAS Enterprise Guide 8.3 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA).

2.3 Results and discussion

2.3.1 Taxonomic profiles

In CS1, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 1,548 OTUs across 249 families and 546 genera. There was a decreasing trend in the abundance of Basidiomycota in CS1 and family Wallemiaceae in red50Bacto treatment and a decreasing trend in the abundance of Psathyrellaceae in all treatments compared to control in the last monitoring year (Figure 2.1). *Wallemicia* contains representatives can tolerate higher concentrations of sugars and salts and thus are adapted to low water availability (Zalar et al. 2005, Kralj et al. 2010). Psathyrellaceae contain for example dung saprotrophs.

Figure 2.1. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS1 from the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization treatment; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50 %; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50 % + “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant.

In CS2, the reads were classified into 1,324 OTUs across 224 families and 452 genera. There was not any clear detectable decreasing or increasing trends in the abundances of the families between treatments (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS2 from the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 with 100% fertilization treatment; Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization treatment; org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% + bacterial inoculant; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% + bacterial and fungal inoculants; Is, Incertae_sedis.

In CS3, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,213 OTUs across 329 families and 702 genera. There was an increasing trend in the abundance of Nectriaceae and a decreasing trend in the abundance of Plectosphaerellaceae in Alt1Pot treatment of CS3. (Figure 2.3). The most abundant genera of these families, *Gibberella* and *Gibellulopsis* contain common plant pathogens and might have different response to Alt1Pot treatment. On the other hand, some strains of *Gibellulopsis* are reported to induce resistance against some potato pathogens (Hao et al. 2022). There was also an increasing trend in the abundance of Hydnodontaceae in Alt2Pot treatment of CS3. The most abundant genus of Hydnodontaceae, *Trechispora*, contains wood saprotrophs that might have benefited Alt2Pot treatment.

Figure 2.3. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS3 from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl, control with conventional potato farming; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in potato; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation2 in potato.

In CS4, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,932 OTUs across 375 families and 822 genera. There was an increasing trend in the abundance of Stephanosporaceae in PotNoP treatment (Figure 2.4). The most abundant genus of this family, *Lindtneria*, is a wood saprotroph and might have benefited from PotNoP treatment without P fertilization.

Figure 2.4. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS4 from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl, control with conventional potato farming; MycPotHP, potato plots with mycorrhizal inoculant + half less P fertilization; MycNoP, potato plots with mycorrhizal inoculant without P fertilization; PotHP, potato plots with half less P fertilization; PotNoP, potato plots without P fertilization.

In CS5, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2312 OTUs across 327 families and 698 genera. There was a decreasing trend in the abundance of Hydnodontaceae and its wood saprotrophs containing genus *Trechispora*, in ConvPotFA treatment (Figure 2.5). Thus, fungicide application might be potential harmful for these fungi.

Figure 2.5. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS5 from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl, potato plots with pest alert system; ConvPotFA, potato plots with conventional fungicide application; PotNoFA, potato plots without fungicide application; Is, Incertae_sedis.

In CS6, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 3,176 OTUs across 373 families and 808 genera. The relative abundance of Pyrenomataceae showed a slight increasing trend in FYM and AFVYM treatments (Figure 2.6). Pyrenomataceae including for instance dung saprotrophs.

Figure

2.6. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS6 from the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl: conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated without fertilizers; FYM, conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated with farm yard manure; AFV, cover crop mowed and removed without fertilizers; AFVYM, cover crop mowed and removed plus fertilizer with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYM, cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure and “brown” co-composted straw; brFYM, conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated with farm yard manure and “brown” co-composted straw. Is, Incertae_sedis.

In CS7, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,144 OTUs across 307 families and 645 genera. There was an increasing trend in the abundances of Helotiaceae in Mix5 treatment and abundances of Sordariales Incertae sedis (uncertain placement in order) and Pseudeurotiaceae Mix12 treatment (Figure 2.7). The most abundant genus of the Helotiaceae was *Tetracladium*, which is a plant saprotroph. The most abundant genus of Sordariales was *Papulospora* which contain fungi with variety of ecological roles from endophytes to mycoparasites and saprotrophs.

Figure

2.7. Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant families in CS7 from the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl: conventional potato farming; PhaEgClov, potato plot with Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crop; Mix5, potato plot with mixture of 5 cover crop species; Mix12, potato plots with mixture of 12 cover crop species.

In CS8, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,946 OTUs across 349 families and 759 genera. There was a decreasing trend in the abundance of Mortierellaceae and increasing trends in the abundances of Pyronemataceae and Hydnaceae in organic extensive farming compared to organic intensive farming treatment (Figure 2.8). Species of Pyronemataceae occur in all types of soil, and can use many substrates, e.g., from dung, decaying leaves and wood (Hansen et al. 2013). There was also a decreasing trend in Mortierellaceae and increasing trends in Pleosporales Incertae sedis and Bionectriaceae in conventional extensive farming compared to conventional intensive farming treatment. The most abundant genus of Bionectriaceae in ConvExt was *Geosmithia* which include for example bark beetle symbionts (Kolařík et al. 2023).

Figure 2.8. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS8 from the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables.

In CS9, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,246 OTUs across 300 families and 665 genera. There was an increasing trend in the abundance of Chaetomiaceae in Comp and abundances of Plectosphaerellaceae in FYM and Ferm treatments of CS9 (Figure 2.9). The most abundant of genera of Plectosphaerellaceae were *Gibelluslopsis* and *Plectosphaerella* which include common plant pathogens and saprotrops (Gao et al. 2016).

Figure 2.9. Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS9 from the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl: plot without manure; Comp, plot with composted green manure; FYM, plot with farmyard manure; Ferm, plot with fermented green manure. Is, Incertae_sedis.

In CS10a, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 1,981 OTUs across 313 families and 627 genera. There was a decreasing trend in the abundances of families Plectosphaerellaceae, Chaetomiaceae and Nectriaceae in Biostim treatment of CS10a (Figure 2.10). The most abundant genera of these families, *Gibellulopsis*, *Plectosphaerella*, *Fusarium* and *Fusicolla*, include many common pathogenic species suggesting their potential decrease after Biostim treatment (Gao et al. 2016). However, some *Gibellulopsis* strains can also induce resistance against some potato pathogens (Hao et al. 2022). On the other hand, Biostim treatment showed also increasing trend in the abundances of Junewangiaceae, Lasiosphaeriaceae and Hoehnelomycetaceae. The most abundant genus of Lasiosphaeriaceae family, *Schizothecium*, contain dung saprotrophs suggesting their increase after Biostim. Association with Lasiosphaeriaceae and organic cereal farming have been reported (Peltoniemi et al 2021). There was an increasing trend in the abundance of Phaeosphaeriaceae in BiostimAdj treatment. The most abundant genus of this family was *Sclerostagonospora* which contain species of plant pathogens and plant saprotrophs. Thus, plant stimulants with additives with reduced fungicides might have potential to decrease soilborne fungal pathogens and on the other hand they may stimulate fungi that benefit from less intensive farming.

Figure 2.10 Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS10a from from the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl, conventional wheat plot with reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat plot with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) and reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat plot with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) and reduction of fungicides; Is, Incertae_sedis.

In CS10b, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,322 OTUs across 323 families and 714 genera. Abundances of Glomerellaceae and Pleosporaceae showed a decreasing trends trend in both treatments (Figure 2.11). The most abundant genus of Pleosporaceae, *Alternaria*, contain species that are common pathogens causing early blight to potato (Schmey et al. 2024). The most abundant genus of Glomerellaceae, was *Colletotrichum* which contain species from plant endophytes to pathogens and saprotroph. Thus, both strip and broad undersowing might have potential to reduce plant diseases. There was also an increasing trend in abundances of Hypocreales Incertae sedis and Herpotrichillaceae in BroadUndSow treatment in CS10b. The most abundant genus of Herpotrichillaceae was *Exophiala* which contain dark-septate endophytes that have potential to increasing the tolerance of their host plants to abiotic stresses (Khan et al., 2012; Li et al., 2011a; Li et al., 2011b).

Figure 2.11 Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant families in CS10b from from the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl, conventional farming; StripUndSow; plot with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, plot with broad undersowing; Is, Incertae_sedis.

In CS11, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,273 OTUs across 334 families and 684 genera. There was a decreasing trend in the abundance of Trimorphomycetaceae and an increasing trend Hypocreales Incertae sedis (uncertain placement in order) in both treatments of CS11 (Figure 2.12). *Saitozyma podzolica* was the most abundant representative of the Trimorphomycetaceae and it is known as plant growth promoting yeast with ability to solubilize phosphorus (Marques et al. 2021). Thus, unexpectedly extensive wheat cultivation with diversification and without pesticides may not be beneficial to this taxon.

Figure 2.12 Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant families in CS11 from from the Continental pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ini1, Initial control plot1 before treatment; Ini2, Initial control plot 2 before treatment; Ini3, Initial control plot3 before treatment; Ini4, Initial control plot 4 before treatment; Ctrl, conventional wheat farming; ExtWhe; extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides; Is, Incertae_sedis.

In CS12 from the Nemoral region, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 3,802 OTUs across 393 families and 875 genera. There was an increasing trend in Hypocreales Incertae sedis in no tillage plots (Figure 2.13). There was an increasing trend in the abundance of the family Didymellaceae in organic farming plot with conventional tillage treatment. There was also an increasing trend in the abundance of Mortierellaceae in conventional farming treatment with conventional tillage.

Figure 2.13 Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant fungal families in the last two monitoring years in CS12 from Nemoral pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations: Ctrl; conventional farming with conventional tillage (winter wheat in 2022, pea in 2023); OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage (winter wheat in 2022, grass in 2023); ConvNoTillPest, conventional without tillage and with pesticides (spring wheat); ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage (*Medicago sativa* as crop plant); FieldEdge, non-cultivated site with wild grasses.

In CS13 from the Boreal region, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,537 OTUs across 349 families and 742 genera. In CPMS treatment the abundance of Polyporales Incertae sedis (uncertain placement in order) showed an increasing trend (Figure 2.14). Many species of Polyporales are saprotrophic for wood and composted fiber sludge may have potential to attract them. Both amendments showed a decreasing trend in the abundances of Nectriaceae and Pleosporaceae. Nectriaceae includes numerous plant and animal pathogens, as well as saprotrophs for variety of substrates and ability to be used in biocontrol agents (Lombard et al. 2015). The most abundant genera *Gibberella* and *Fusarium*, include known pathogenic species. Pleosporaceae have also a wide range of lifestyles, and the most abundant genus *Alternaria* includes important plant pathogens of various crops (Ariyawansa et al. 2015, Elkhateeb et al. 2021). It has been shown that wood-based compost amendments caused suppressive effect against soil-born plant pathogens (Markakis et al. 2016). It was also reported that wood-derived organic amendments would favor saprotrophs over potential plant pathogenic fungi (Clocchiatti et al. 2021), and that amendments with forest litter decreased *Fusarium* infections of wheat (Ridout and Newcombe 2016). Thus, our findings also indicate that wood-based amendments have ability to decrease the competitiveness of pathogens. In addition, in the first monitoring year CPMS treatment plot had high relative of the abundance of Didymellaceae which includes important potato pathogenic genus *Boeremia* (syn. *Phoma*) (Bennett et al. 2016). Thus, result might indicate that it may take some time before amendments impact soil fungal community.

Figure 2.14 Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant fungal families in CS13 from the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations; Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control (CS13) Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment.

In CS14a and CS14b, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,655 and 2,187 OTUs across 368 and 324 families and 764 and 690 genera, respectively. Spring ploughing treatment in CS14a showed an increasing trend in the abundance of Bionectriaceae (Figure 2.15). Genus *Clonostachys* was its most abundant representative of this family, which includes potential biocontrollers of *Fusarium* induced blight disease in cereals (Khairullina et al. 2023). Autumn ploughing in CS14b did not show clear trend in any directions (Figure 2.16).

Figure 2.15 Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant fungal families in CS14a from the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations; Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring.

Figure 2.16 Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant fungal families in CS14b from the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations; Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn.

In CS15, the fungal ITS reads were classified into 2,477 OTUs across 351 families and 734 genera. Phylum Ascomycota was the most abundant phylum in CS15 (Figure 2.17). There was a decreasing trend in the abundance of Pleosporaceae in cover crop treatments with both phacelia and rye in CS15. Further investigations showed that the abundance of representative genus of the family, *Alternaria*, showed also decreasing trend in cover crop plots which most likely explains the result. Thus, the result indicate indirectly that cover crops may have ability to decrease the abundance of important soil-borne fungal pathogen *Alternaria* (Ariyawansa et al. 2015, Elkhateeb et al. 2021).

Figure 2.17 Mean relative abundances (%) of the most abundant fungal families in CS15 from the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Abbreviations; Ctrl, conventional early potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after the early potato harvest; rye, mixture of and rye grass as cover crop after the early potato harvest

2.3.2 Alpha-diversity

Alpha diversity did not differ between control and fertilization treatments in CS1 and CS2 fields in the last monitoring year (Figure 2.18).

Figure 2.18. Alpha diversity metrics, OTU number and Shannon diversity index from the last monitoring year in CS1 and CS2 fields in the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.1

There was a trend towards less fungal OTUs in alternative crop rotation 2 compared to conventional control treatment in the potato field of CS3 (Figure 2.19). No differences were detected between control and treatments in the potato fields of CS4, whereas OTU numbers were significantly lower in treatment without fungicides in the last monitoring year in CS5 potato field.

Figure 2.19. Alpha diversity metrics, OTU numbers and Shannon diversity index from the last monitoring year in CS3, CS4 and CS5 fields in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.2.

There were less fungal OTUs in treatment where cover crops were mowed and removed including farmyard manure and “brown” co-composted straw fertilization (AFVbrFYM) compared to conventional control plot with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated into the field in CS6 (Figure 2.20). Shannon diversity was lower with farmyard manure (FYM) compared to control in CS6. Decrease in overall fungal diversity due to goat manure was expected, since the fungal community may have changed into certain taxa that are detected with manure (Hartmann et al. 2015). No statistical differences were detected between control and treatments in three other case study fields (CS7-CS9) of the Atlantic North region.

Figure 2.20. Alpha diversity metrics, OTU number and Shannon diversity index from the last monitoring year in CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9 fields in the Atlantic North region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.3.

No statistical differences were detected between control and treatments in CS10a and CS11 fields in the Atlantic North region (Figure 2.21). However, both undersowing treatments had significantly bigger Shannon diversity, especially that of under the broad undersowing plots, compared to control.

Figure 2.21. Alpha diversity metrics, OTU number and Shannon diversity index from the last monitoring year in CS10a, CS10b and CS11 fields in the Continental region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.4.

There was an increasing trend in Shannon diversity in organic farming with conventional tillage compared to conventional farming with conventional tillage (control) and in 2022 in CS12 (Figure 2.22). However, the result remains unclear because of the poor statistical power due to the lack of proper amount or replicates.

Figure 2.22. Alpha diversity metrics, OTU number and Shannon diversity index from the last two monitoring years in CS12 field in the Nemoral region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.5.

There was a nearly significant increase in both OTU numbers and Shannon diversity in CPMS soil amendment plots in CS13 (Figure 2.23). However, no statistical differences were detected between control and treatments in any of the four case study fields conducted in early potato fields (CS13 and CS15) and in wheat fields (CS14a and CS14b) in the last monitoring year.

Figure 2.23. Alpha diversity metrics, OTU number and Shannon diversity index from the last monitoring year in CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15 fields in the Boreal region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.6.

2.3.3 Beta-diversity

Total fungal community composition did not differ between control and treatments in the CS1 and CS2 from the Mediterranean south region (Figure 2.24, Table 2.1).

Figure 2.24. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots from CS1 and CS2 showing the fungal community composition of the field sites in the last monitoring year. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Abbreviations in Figure 2.1.

Fungal community composition differed between control and alternative potato rotation 2 in CS3, and between control and all different fertilization treatments with or without inoculants in CS4 (Figure 2.25, Table 2.1). Fungal community composition did not differ between control and treatment plots in CS5 from the Lusitanian region although there was slightly separating trend between control and PotNoFA treatment.

Figure 2.25. Two-dimensional NMDS plots (CS3 and CS4) and PCoA plot (CS5) showing the fungal community composition of the field sites in the last monitoring year. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Abbreviations in Figure 2.2.

According to NMDS and permanova there were slight differences in fungal community composition between treatments in the CS6 (Figure 2.26, Table 2.1). Composition in treatments with AFVFYM and FYM were similar and showed slightly divergent composition from the control, although paired comparison could not reveal differences probably because of the large variation in data. Fungal community composition did not vary between control and treatments in CS7 and CS9. Whereas fungal communities differed between intensive and extensive organic farming and between all organic and conventional farming plots for vegetables in CS8.

Figure 2.26. Two-dimensional NMDS plots showing the fungal community composition of CS5–CS9 field sites in the last monitoring year. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Abbreviations in Figure 2.3.

According to PERMOVA there was a slightly significant difference in fungal community composition between control and treatment plots in CS10a, whereas paired composition could not verify difference probably because of the large variation in the data from the Biostim treatment (Figure 2.27, Table 2.1). According to PERMANOVA and paired comparison there was also a slight difference between controls and both strip and broad undersowing treatments in wheat field in CS10b. According to PERMANOVA community composition differed between control and treatment paired comparison could not reveal actual differences probably due to large variation between replicate samples in CS11. However, there was slightly separating trend between control and DivExtWhe treatment.

Figure 2.27. Two-dimensional PCoA plots (CS10a and CS10b) and NMDS plot (CS11) showing the fungal community composition of the field sites in the last monitoring year. Abbreviations in Figure 2.4.

NMDS showed a trend towards the difference in fungal community composition between control (conventional farming with conventional tillage) and other treatments in CS12, but due to lack of replicates PERMANOVA and statistical significance could not be verified (Figure 2.28).

Figure 2.28. Two-dimensional NMDS plots showing the fungal community composition of the CS12 field sites in the last two monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Abbreviations in Figure 2.5.

Fungal community composition did not differ significantly between control and any of the treatments in boreal case study fields (CS13-CS15) (Figure 2.29, Table 2.1). There was a large variation in replicate samples which might have hindered some slight changes.

Figure 2.29. Two-dimensional NMDS plots showing the fungal community composition of field sites (CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15) in the last monitoring year from the Boreal region. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by framing practices (Treatment). Abbreviations in Figure 2.6.

Table 2.1. Results of PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of treatment (agricultural practice) conducted in different case studies on fungal community composition for the last monitoring year. Differences are considered significant if $P \leq 0.05$.

REGION	CASE STUDY	SOURCE	R2	F	P
Mediterranean South	CS1	Treatment	0.20469	1.0295	0.364
		Residuals	0.79531		
	CS2	Treatment	0.21431	1.091	0.213
		Residuals	0.78569		
Lusitanian	CS3	Treatment	0.28478	1.7918	0.01
		Residuals	0.71522		
	CS4	Treatment	0.36552	2.1603	0.001
		Residuals	0.63448		
	CS5	Treatment	0.35759	1.6699	0.161
		Residuals	0.64241		
Atlantic Central	CS6	Treatment	0.27898	1.3929	0.012
		Residuals	0.72102		
	CS7	Treatment	0.17265	0.8347	0.728
		Residuals	0.82735		
	CS8	Treatment	0.43339	3.0595	0.001
		Residuals	0.56661		
	CS9	Treatment	0.22137	1.1372	0.25
		Residuals	0.77863		
Continental	CS10a	Treatment	0.25117	1.5094	0.049
		Residuals	0.74883		
	CS10b	Treatment	0.26283	1.6044	0.006
		Residuals	0.73717		
	CS11	Treatment	0.26013	1.5822	0.015
		Residuals	0.73987		
Boreal	CS13	Treatment	0.19436	1.0856	0.332
		Residuals	0.80564		
	CS14a	Treatment	0.17295	1.2547	0.174
		Residuals	0.82705		
	CS14b	Treatment	0.19417	1.4457	0.118
		Residuals	0.80583		
	CS15	Treatment	0.15191	0.8061	0.893
		Residuals	0.84809		

2.3.4 Fungi associated to agricultural practices

Significant associations between fungal OTUs and agricultural practices from the last monitoring year were not detected with MaAsLin2 analysis in half of the case studies: CS2, CS3, CS6, CS7, Cs10a, CS14a, CS14b and CS15. However, associations were detected in eight other case studies. Here we represent heatmaps and/or relative abundances illustrating the association between fungal representative(s) and treatments. The positive effect of the treatment compared to control or other reference groups in the heatmap is shown in red and respectively, negative effect is shown in blue.

In CS1, only one OTU representing genus *Geosmithia* showed positive association to red50Nuve treatment (Figure 2.30). Genus contains widely distributed fungal associates of phloem- and xylem-feeding beetles and they are usually isolated from broadleaved and conifer trees (e.g. Kolařík et al. 2017). However, *Geosmithia* has been documented from many other substrates including soil (Kolařík et al. 2004). Based on this result it remains unclear how reduced chemical fertilization together with fungi and bacteria containing inoculants could have attracted this genus.

Figure 2.30. Relative abundance and positive association between OTU representing genus *Geosmithia* and red50Nuve treatment in the field of CS1.

There were over 200 associations (mostly negative) between a variety of fungal OTU representatives and treatments in CS4 and fifty of the most significant ones are shown (Figure 2.31). All treatments showed negative associations to OTUs that represented for example saprotrophic *Cristinia*, *Exophiala* with various roles as animal pathogen, endophyte and saprotroph, plant and wood saprotroph *Gymnopilus* and pathogenic *Alternaria*. However, a few of them showed positive associations with treatments. For example, OTUs associated with mycorrhizal inoculant and half less of P fertilization included saprotrophs (*Ramophialophora*, *Panaeolina*), dung saprotroph (*Trichobolus*) and fungal genus with various roles as animal and plant pathogen, endophyte, fungal parasite and saprotroph for wood (*Acremonium*). Treatment without P fertilization associated with OTUs including genus *Aspergillus*. Interestingly, both *Acremonium* and *Aspergillus* contain potential phosphate-solubilizing fungi, and *Aspergillus* has also antifungal activity against the plant pathogenic fungi (Ichriani et al. 2018; de Oliveira Mendes et al. 2014, Qin et al. 2019). OTU associated with treatment without P fertilization and mycorrhizal inoculant included for example genus *Cistella* with various roles as endophyte, plant and saprotroph seem to benefit from and has been reported to correlate positively with P deficiency (Khalid et al. 2021). Yet, OTU associated with treatment with half less P fertilization included for example *Ganoderma*, which as a part of compost residues with reduced chemical fertilizers improved soil pH, soil organic matter, available P and K levels, as well as crop growth (Feng et al. 2023).

Top 50 features with significant associations ($-\log(\text{qval}) \cdot \text{sign}(\text{coeff})$)

Figure 2.31. Heatmap from fifty of the most significant positive and negative associations between fungal OTUs and four different treatments compared to control in the field of CS4.

There were thirteen associations between fungal OTU representatives and treatments in CS5 (Figure 2.32). Fungal OTUs that showed the strongest negative association to both treatments included taxa Lecanoromycetes and *Chaetosphaeria*, which include endophytes and plant and wood saprotrophs. Fungal OTU representing genus *Entoloma* including ectomycorrhizal, fungal parasites and undefined saprotrophs showed positive association to both conventional fungicide application and without fungicide application compared to control with pest alert system. Conventional fungicide application showed positive association with OTUs representing plant saprotrophic *Clathrosphaerina* and dung saprotroph *Triangularina*.

Figure 2.32. Heatmap from the significant positive and negative associations between fungal OTUs and two different treatments compared to control in the field of CS5.

There were over 300 associations with the variety of fungal OTU representatives and treatments in CS8 when comparisons were conducted against conventional intensive farming treatment (Figure 2.33). Fungal OTUs that showed positive associations to conventional extensive farming compared to conventional intensive farming included representative genera for example from variety of saprotrophs: plant and wood saprotroph *Ganoderma*, pollen saprotroph *Operculomyces*, dung saprotroph *Iodophanus* and plant saprotroph *Striatibotrys*. Yet, fungal OTUs that showed positive associations to organic intensive farming included representatives for example from potential endophyte and biocontrolling agent as well as pathogenic *Fusarium oxysporium*, plant pathogen *Lectera*, wood saprotroph *Phomatodes*, animal parasite and saprotroph *Phialemonium*, and saprotroph *Chordomyces*. Fungal OTUs that showed positive associations to organic extensive farming included representatives for example from dung saprotroph *Pseudeurotium*, dung and plant saprotrophs *Conocybe*, plant pathogen and pollen saprotroph *Betamyces*, saprotroph *Pseudopyrenochaeta* and pathotroph *Minimedusa*. Those OTUs that seem to be associated positively with organic farming system included for example taxa from Chaetomiaceae with many roles from animal pathogen to dung saprotroph and endophyte and plant and wood saprotroph, saprotrophic *Aaossphaeria*, saprotrophic Lasiosphaeriaceae and Dictyosporiaceae families. Those OTUs that had negative associations to organic system might represent taxa that are favoured by conventional farming system including for example genera of wood-saprotroph *Trechispora*, *Penicillium* with various ecological roles, and species of *Trichoderma pubescens*. *T. pubescens* can act against a serious potato disease *Rhizoctonia solani* (Behiry et al. 2023).

Top 50 features with significant associations ($-\log(qval) \cdot \text{sign}(\text{coeff})$)

Figure 2.33. Heatmap from fifty of the most significant positive and negative associations between fungal OTUs and other three treatments compared to conventional intensive farming in the field of CS8.

In CS9, most of the associations with OTUs and different manure treatments were positive (Figure 2.34). For example, OTUs associated with farmyard manure (FYM) included representatives of three different *Kernia* species that are dung saprotrophs. Fermented green manure (Ferm) associated with many genera with multiple ecological roles as pathogens, saprotrophs and symbiotrophs (*Penicillium*, *Microascus*, *Fusarium* and *Hymenoscyphus*). Composted green manure (Comp), also associated with genera including dung saprotrophs (*Triangularia*) as well as others with multiple roles (*Penicillium*, *Candida*, and *Mortierella*). Saprotrophic genera *Filobasidium* and *Dictyosporiaceae* showed negative association to all three manure treatments.

Significant associations ($-\log(qval) * \text{sign}(\text{coeff})$)

Figure 2.34. Heatmap of the most significant positive and negative associations between fungal OTUs and treatments in the field of CS9.

In CS10b, nineteen OTUs showed only positive associations to treatments in the potato field (Figure 2.35). Taxa that showed associations with both treatments included representatives for example from common saprotrophs and endophytes (*Mortierella*), wood saprotrophs (*Pseudorobillarda*), *Trichoderma atroviride* with many roles as pathogen, endophyte and wood saprotroph, and *Septoria petroselini* which causes Septoria blight, a common, important disease, of parsley worldwide (Amein 2023). *T. atroviride* is a promising biocontrolling agent to promote antagonism and induction of plant systemic disease resistance (Brunner et al. 2005). However, most of the associations were detected with broad undersowing treatment. Fungal OTUs that associated with broad undersowing included representatives for example from saprotrophs (*Trichocladium* and *Mrakia*), and the commonest species in agricultural soils and strong capacities for decomposition of xylan and cellulose (*Niesslia mucida*) (Domsch and Gams 1969) and *Schizothecium* containing dung saprotrophs, plant pathogen and saprotroph *Pseudopithomyces angolensis*, and family *Chaetomiaceae*, which include representatives from animal pathogens to dung and plant saprotrophs and endophytes. Fungal OTUs that showed association with strip undersowing treatment included for example representatives from wood saprotrophs (*Junewangia*) and *Sodiomyces alcalophilus* which was first isolated from pig manure compost and it has alkalophilic (optimal growth at pH 9.0-9.2) and cellulolytic properties (Okada et al. 1993, Giraldo & Grous 2019).

Significant associations ($-\log(qval) \cdot \text{sign}(\text{coeff})$)

Figure 2.35. Heatmap of the most significant positive and negative associations between fungal OTUs and two treatments compared to control in the field of CS10b.

In CS11, 29 OTUs showed positive associations to treatments in the wheat field (Figure 2.36). Both treatments showed positive associations with OTUs of taxa that can act as endophytes, plant pathogens or saprotrophs (*Plectosphaerella*) and as saprotrophs (*Kiflimonium*) (Gao et al. 2016). OTUs that showed positive associations with extensive farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides included representatives from family Nectriaceae, and from species of wood-saprotrophic genus *Valsonectria*, endophytic and plant saprotrophic *Pyrenochaetopsis* and *Clonostachys* with roles from fungal parasite to plant pathogen and plant saprotroph as well as act as potential biocontroller of *Fusarium* induced blight disease in cereals (Khairullina et al. 2023). Nectriaceae includes numerous important plant pathogens, as well as several species used as biodegraders and biocontrol agents (Lombard et al. 2015). Taxa which showed positive associations with diversified extensive farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides included for example OTUs of from the species of pathogenic genus *Fusarium*, and saprotrophic genus *Chordomyces*. On the other hand, *Fusarium oxysporium* can act as root-endophyte and used as biocontrol against some plant pathogens (de Lamo et al. 2020). Fungal OTUs that showed negative associations with both extensive and diversified extensive farming without pesticides included species of *Trichoderma*, Chaetomiaceae, *Coniochaeta*, *Mortierella* and Capnodiales. *Trichoderma* can act as biocontrollers of fungal and nematode pathogens and induce plant systemic disease resistance (Brunner et al. 2005 Yao et al. 2023). Four other taxa include fungi with multiple roles as animal and plant pathogen to dung and plant saprotrophs and endophytes. Fungal OTUs that showed negative associations with extensive farming included for example species of wood-saprotrophic genera *Fibulochlamys*, saprotrophic *Dichotomopilus*, *Extremopsis* and plant pathogen and wood-saprotroph *Ganoderma*. Fungal OTUs that showed negative associations with diversified extensive farming included for example species of saprotrophic *Gliomastix* and *Purpureocillium* including animal and fungal parasites and undefined saprotrophs.

Significant associations $(-\log(qval)*\text{sign}(coeff))$

Figure 2.36. Heatmap of the most significant positive and negative associations between fungal OTUs and two treatments in the field of CS11.

In boreal early potato field CS13, only one fungal OTU representing plant-benefiting species *Trichoderma virens* showed positive association to nutrient-poor zero fiber organic soil amendment (Figure 2.37). *T. virens* has been reported to increase plant biomass and lateral root growth in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and thus might benefit the growth of other crops as well (Contreras-Cornejo et al. 2009). Application of *T. virens* to the compost have resulted in higher xylanase and cellulase activities which lead to increased decomposition of cellulose and hemicelluloses (Amira et al. 2011).

Figure 2.37. Relative abundance and positive association between OTU representing *T. virens* and nutrient-rich fiber sludge organic soil amendment in the early potato field of CS13.

2.3.5 Functional fungal guilds

There was an increase in the relative abundance of the pathogens due to 50% reduced fertilization with and without fungal and bacterial inoculant “Nuve” and a strong increasing trend in the abundance of symbiotrophs due to 50% reduced fertilization with fungal and bacterial inoculant “Nuve” in CS1 and a decreasing trend in the relative abundance of the pathogens due to all treatments in CS2 (Figure 2.38).

Figure 2.38. Relative abundances of saprotrophic (Sap), pathotrophic (Pat) and symbiotrophic (Sym) fungal guilds from the last monitoring year in CS1 and CS2 fields in the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.1.

There was a decreasing trend in the relative abundance of the pathogens due to alternative crop rotation 2 in potato field in CS3 field (Figure 2.39). There was a slight increasing trend in the relative abundance of saprotrophs due to fertilization with half amount of P in potato and a decreasing trend in the relative abundance of symbiotrophs due to all treatments in CS4. There was an increasing trend in the relative abundance of saprotrophs due to conventional fungicide application and a decrease in the abundances of symbiotrophs in potato farming without fungicides in CS5.

Figure 2.39. Relative abundances of saprotrophic (Sap), pathotrophic (Pat) and symbiotrophic (Sym) fungal guilds from the last monitoring year in CS3, CS4 and CS5 fields in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.25.

There was an increasing trend in the relative abundance of saprotrophs due to all treatments and decreasing trend in the relative abundance of pathotrophs due to AFVFYM and FYM in CS6 field (Figure 2.40). There was a decreasing trend in the relative abundance of symbiotrophs in potato plots with different cover crops and especially with Phacelia and Egyptian clover in CS7. However, changes were not statistically significant. There was an increasing trend in pathotrophs in organic extensive farming plot compared to organic intensive farming, and in symbiotrophs in conventional intensive farming plot compared to conventional extensive farming plot in CS8. There was a decreasing trend in the relative abundances of all guilds in potato plots with farmyard manure and especially plot with fermented green manure in CS9.

Figure 2.40. Relative abundances of saprotrophic (Sap), pathotrophic (Pat) and symbiotrophic (Sym) fungal guilds from the last monitoring year in CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9 fields in the Atlantic North region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.3.

The relative abundance of pathotrophs was significantly lower in the winter barley plots with plant biostimulants compared to control plots in CS10a (Figure 2.41). There was an increasing trend in the relative abundance of symbiotrophs in the plots with plant biostimulants and adjuvants, but due to large variation in the data the difference is not significant. The relative abundance of saprotrophs was significantly higher in mustard plot with broad undersowing treatment compared to control plots in CS10b. There was not any trends or significant changes between control and wheat plots with extensive or diversified extensive farming with undersown clover in CS11.

Figure 2.41 Relative abundances of saprotrophic (Sap), pathotrophic (Pat) and symbiotrophic (Sym) fungal guilds from the last monitoring year in CS10a, CS10b and CS11 fields in the Continental region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.4.

There was an increasing trend in the relative abundance of saprotrophs both in organic farming with tillage and in conventional farming without tillage compared to conventional tillage as a control in the last monitoring year 2023 in the CS12 field (Figure 2.42). There was also an increasing trend in the relative abundances of pathotrophs in organic farming with conventional tillage and in contrast a decreasing trend in conventional farming without tillage compared conventional tilled control. There was also an increasing trend in the relative abundance of symbiotrophs in organic farming with tillage in two last monitoring years.

Figure 2.42. Relative abundances of saprotrophic (Sap), pathotrophic (Pat) and symbiotrophic (Sym) fungal guilds from the last two monitoring years in CS12 field in the Nemoral region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.5.

There was a significant increase due to organic-rich composted fiber sludge (CPMS) and an increasing trend in the relative abundance of saprotrophs due to nutrient-poor fiber sludge (FS) in CS13 (Figure 2.43). There was also a strong and nearly significant decreasing trend in the relative abundance of pathotrophs due to organic-rich composted fiber sludge (CPMS). There was also a decreasing trend in the relative abundance of saprotrophs, and an increasing trend in the abundances of pathotrophs and symbiotrophs due to spring ploughing tillage treatment in CS14a. There was also an increasing trend in the abundances of pathotrophs due to autumn ploughing tillage treatment in CS14b. However, any of these trends was not statistically significant. The relative abundance of symbiotrophs was significantly lower in early potato plot with Phacelia as a cover crop in CS15.

figure 2.43. Relative abundances of saprotrophic (Sap), pathotrophic (Pat) and symbiotrophic (Sym) fungal guilds from the last monitoring year in CS13 , CS14a, CS14b and CS15 fields in the Boreal region. Abbreviations in Figure 2.6.

2.3.6 Conclusions

After the three monitoring years, soil fungi in Lusitanian case studies CS1 conducted in potato field and CS2 in wheat field from the Southern Mediterranean region did seem rather resilient to different fertilization treatments with and without inoculants. However, decreased fertilization (50% of the conventional one) alone and with “Nuve” inoculant containing both fungi and bacteria may decrease the number of pathotrophs and latter induce an increase of symbiotrophs indicating benefits to soil and plant health.

Whereas changes were detected in fungal community due to different agricultural practices in case studies (CS3-CS5) from the Lusitanian region conducted in potato fields. Fungal richness or diversity did not differ between treatments in CS3 or CS4. Fungal community composition differed between control and reduced or without P fertilization with or without mycorrhizal inoculants in CS4. Since fungi are essentially important organisms in P metabolism and its transfer to plants, the shift in the fungal community was expected. There were several fungal representatives associated with CS4 treatments. Most of them showed negative associations indicating that many taxa may decrease if P fertilization is decreased or removed with or without mycorrhizal inoculants. Those taxa that had negative associations with all these treatments included fungi with various ecological roles from saprotrophs to animal and plant pathogens, and to endophytes and saprotroph of plants and wood. However, there were fungi that seemed to benefit from the treatments. For example, fungi that might benefit from less of P fertilization included potential phosphate-solubilizing fungi (*Acremonium* and *Aspergillus*), saprotrophs that have been reported to appear under P deficiency (*Cistella*) or potential soil health and plant-growth promoters (*Ganoderma*). In CS5, fungal richness (OTU numbers) was lowered without fungicide application, but fungal composition of potato field between control with pest alert system and conventional fungicide application or treatment without fungicide application in potato field, were minor. Results indicated that fungicide application might have increased some saprotrophic taxa. Surprisingly, the abundance of symbiotrophs in conventional potato farming without fungicides would decrease. On the other hand, the detected amount of symbiotrophic OTUs was minor in general compared to other guilds.

There were also changes in fungal community due to agricultural practices in the last monitoring year in all case studies (CS6-CS9) from the Atlantic Central region. Cover crop mowing and removing combined with goat manure and co-composted straw in CS6 seem to decrease fungal richness, and pure fertilization with goat manure may decrease diversity. Soil fungal communities from the treatments with goat manure showed the most diverging trend from the control plots. In addition, all treatments may increase saprotrophs and goat manure with or without cover crop mowing and removing may decrease pathotrophs. However, most likely due to large variation of the data these trends could not be verified statistically. In CS7 potato field fungal richness or diversity or overall soil fungal community composition did not change due to any diversification treatment in potato field. However, there was a decrease in symbiotrophs in crop rotation with Phacelia and Egyptian clover and with cover crop mixture 5. Based on the results from CS8 it is clear, whether organic or conventional farming is conducted intensively or extensively affects largely soil fungal community. In studied plots, the abundance of symbiotrophs in both organic extensive and intensive farming was

lower compared to conventional extensive farming. Extensive

farming irrespective of the farming system (organic or conventional) seemed to favor fungi capable of dung decomposition (*Iodophanus*, *Pseudeurotium*, *Conocybe*). In the last monitoring year in CS9 potato field, fungal richness or diversity or overall soil fungal community composition did not show significant changes due to different fertilization treatments with composted or fermented or untreated farmyard manure. There was a decreasing trend in the relative abundances of all guilds in potato plots with farmyard manure and especially with fermented green manure. Results indicated that different types of manures attract different fungi, but many of them were expectedly decomposers of dung such as *Kernia* and *Triangularia*.

A few significant changes were detected in soil fungal community due to agricultural practices in the last monitoring year in case studies (CS10a-CS11) from the Continental region. In the last monitoring year in CS10a field with winter barley as main crop, fungal richness or diversity did not change due to two different treatments containing different biostimulants. However, the abundance of pathogens was lowered due to biostimulants without adjuvants. Thus, biostimulants might have beneficial impact if they can promote plant health against soil-borne diseases. In the last monitoring year in CS10a field with mustard as a main crop, both undersowing treatments and especially broad undersowing, seem to have increased fungal diversity. Undersowing methods changed soil fungal community composition. Broad undersowing might have potential to increase the amount of saprotrophs and to promote fungi with broad saprotrophic abilities to decompose variety of substrates from dung to complex plant-derived compounds. In addition, many changes in soil fungal community composition due to extensive or diversified extensive farming were detected in CS11 field with winter wheat as a main crop in the last monitoring year. Fungal community differed between control and diversified extensive farming plots with wide seed rows and without pesticides. Both extensive and diversified extensive farming showed negative associations with *Trichoderma* indicating that it did not benefit from less intensive agricultural practices (removal of pesticides, clover as a cover crop). However, *Trichoderma* propagules have been reported to be higher in soils from conventional farms before (Liu et al. 2008). On the other hand, extensive farming may have benefited *Clonostachys* which is a potential biocontroller of *Fusarium*.

In CS12 field consisted of different agricultural practices and variable crop plants during the three monitoring years. In addition, most of the treatment plots lacked replicates. These facts make it difficult to make any conclusion about the real effects of ploughing tillage. However, there was an increasing trend in Shannon diversity in organic farming with conventional tillage in 2022 in CS12. In addition, the abundance of pathotrophs showed a decrease in conventional farming with no tillage and an increasing trend in organic farming with conventional tillage in the last monitoring year. There was also an increasing trend in the relative abundance of symbiotrophs in organic farming with tillage in two last monitoring years.

In boreal case studies conducted in early potato fields (CS13 and CS15) or in wheat fields (CS14a and CS14b) we detected only minor changes due to treatments. However, fungal richness and diversity have a strong increasing trend due to nutrient-rich composted fiber sludge bases soil amendment in early potato field of CS13 (Figure 2.23). In addition, another result indicated that some plant-benefiting fungi might benefit from nutrient-poor zero fiber sludge based organic soil amendment in early potato field of CS13. There was also an increasing trend in the amounts of saprotrophs and

symbiotrophs in the plots with both different organic soil amendments originating from the recycled by-product of the pulp industry, which further indicates the potential of amendments to enhance beneficial soil fungi. There was an increasing trend in both spring and autumn ploughing in the abundance of pathotrophs CS14a and CS14b. We suggest that soil fungi in CS14a and CS14b fields that have been under organic farming for a long-time are not particularly sensitive or can recover rapidly from the occasional physical ploughing. In CS15, *Phacelia* as a catch crop in the early potato field decreased the abundance of symbiotrophic fungi. However, abundances of symbiotrophs in CS15 field and in all studied field in general were quite small most likely because we investigated only bulk soil and not soil from the rhizosphere.

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3 Microbial biomass characterization

3.1 Introduction

Soil microbial abundance is a key indicator of soil health and, by extension, of the functioning of terrestrial ecosystems. Soil microorganisms play a vital role in essential soil functions and ecosystem services, including nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, biodiversity maintenance, contaminant biodegradation, and climate regulation. As such, maintaining and/or enhancing microbial abundance and diversity in agricultural soils is fundamental for achieving sustainable crop production (Morugán-Coronado et al., 2022; FAO et al., 2020; Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2016).

Conventional agricultural practices—characterised by monocultures, intensive mechanisation, and the excessive use of synthetic fertilisers and pesticides—frequently lead to reductions in soil microbial diversity and abundance. This decline can compromise soil health and, in turn, adversely affect crop productivity, thereby undermining the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems (Morugán-Coronado et al., 2022; Tilman et al., 2002).

Conversely, the adoption of environmentally friendly and conservation-oriented agricultural practices—such as diversified crop rotations, conservation tillage, organic fertilisation, and the use of cover crops—offers a sustainable and viable alternative. These practices have been shown to alleviate the pressures of intensive agriculture and enhance both the diversity and abundance of soil microbial communities. Moreover, they contribute to reducing soil degradation, improving soil fertility, increasing carbon sequestration, and ultimately enhancing crop yield and quality (Scotti et al., 2015; Kraut-Cohen et al., 2020; Doran, 2002).

Such improvements foster more stable, resilient, and environmentally sound agricultural systems, aligning with the objectives of the European Commission's "Farm to Fork" strategy. This strategy seeks to establish a sustainable food system with minimal environmental impact, contributing to climate change mitigation and biodiversity preservation (European Commission, 2023).

Nevertheless, field-based studies examining the influence of diverse soil management practices and cropping systems on microbial diversity and abundance remain scarce.

Soil microbial abundance is commonly assessed using the phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) technique, which involves the extraction of lipids from microbial cell membranes. These lipids serve as biomarkers, as they are present only in viable microorganisms. The total PLFA content provides an estimate of total microbial biomass, while specific PLFA markers enable the quantification of distinct microbial groups, such as bacteria and fungi (Morugán-Coronado et al., 2022).

This report presents the initial findings from Work Package 5 (WP5) of the SoildiverAgro project, which explores the impact of diverse agricultural management practices on soil microbial abundance and community composition. The study was conducted across six pedoclimatic regions in Europe.

3.2 Material and Methods

To estimate the abundance of different groups of microbes, the method described by Frostegård and Bååth (1996) was used. Briefly: lipids were extracted from soils using “Bligh and Dyer” solution, and then neutral lipids, glycolipids and phospholipids were separated using silica columns and solvents with different polarity: methanol for neutral lipids, acetone for glycolipids and chloroform for phospholipids. After separation, neutral lipids and phospholipids were subjected to mild alkaline methanolysis (transesterification) to break the lipids and obtain the fatty acids. After this step, the fatty acids were determined by gas chromatography. Different fatty acids are specific of different microbial groups, allowing to calculate the abundance of these groups by summing different fatty acids. Most of microbial groups were estimated using phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) while neutral lipid fatty acid (NLFA) 16:1 ω 5 was used to estimate the abundance of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Table 3.1).

The statistical significance of differences between case study, region and management practices were estimated using one-way ANOVA, and the statistical analysis were performed using IBM SPSS statistics 25.0.

TABLE 3.1	
Total abundance	All determined PLFAs
Bacteria	PLFAs: i15:0, a15:0, 15:0, i16:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7t, i17:0, a17:0, 17:0, cy17:0, 18:1 ω 7, cy19:0
Gram-positive Bacteria	PLFAs: br17:0, br18:0, i17:0, a17:0, i16:0, i16:1, 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, i15:0, a15:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7c, 18:1 ω 7 and 19:1
Gram-negative Bacteria	PLFAs: cy17:0, cy19:0, r-hydroxy fatty acids, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7, 16:1 ω 5, 18:1 ω 7 and 19:1
Actinobacteria	PLFAs: 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0 and 10Me18:0
Fungi	PLFA: 18:2 ω 6 (linoleic acid)
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	NLFAs: 16:1 ω 5

Table 3.1. Fatty acid biomarkers used to estimate the abundance of different microbial groups.

3.3 Results and discussion

Data on total microbial abundance (estimated as total PLFA), as well as the abundance of specific microbial groups—including total bacteria, Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria, Firmicutes, Actinobacteria, total fungi, arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, Zygomycota, Ascomycota, Basidiomycota, and nonspecific microbes—are presented for each case study and in relation to the different treatments or management practices in Tables 3.2 to 3.18.

TABLE 3.2

	CTRL	FERT50	RED50BACTO	RED50NUVE
Total PLFA	25.6 ± 4.1	17.9 ± 4.8	20.4 ± 6.2	21.7 ± 2.4
Total Bacteria	14.8 ± 2.9	10.5 ± 3.1	11.8 ± 3.4	12.8 ± 1.7
Gram+ bacteria	8.6 ± 1.6	6.0 ± 1.8	6.8 ± 1.9	7.5 ± 1.0
<i>Firmicutes</i>	5.1 ± 1.2	3.7 ± 1.0	4.1 ± 1.2	4.7 ± 0.5
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	3.5 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 0.8	2.6 ± 0.7	2.8 ± 0.5
Gram- bacteria	6.2 ± 1.4	4.5 ± 1.3	5.0 ± 1.6	5.2 ± 0.8
Total Fungi	4.3 ± 0.8	3.0 ± 0.7	3.7 ± 1.6	3.7 ± 0.4
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	0.9 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.2
Zygomycota	2.6 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 0.4	2.1 ± 0.7	2.3 ± 0.2
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.8 ± 0.4	0.5 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.8	0.6 ± 0.1
Unspecific microbial	6.6 ± 0.7	4.4 ± 0.9	4.9 ± 1.3	5.3 ± 0.4

Table 3.2. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS1 (Southern Mediterranean pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50%; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50% plus “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant.

TABLE 3.3

	CTRL	ORG70BIOBA	ORG70BIOBAFU	ORG70
Total PLFA	20.7 ± 3.6	29.9 ± 2.0	28.7 ± 4.4	25.2 ± 6.9
Total Bacteria	10.9 ± 2.0	16.6 ± 0.8	16.2 ± 2.6	13.8 ± 3.9
Gram+ bacteria	5.0 ± 1.1	7.6 ± 0.3	7.6 ± 1.3	6.6 ± 2.0
<i>Firmicutes</i>	2.8 ± 0.7	4.0 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.9	3.7 ± 1.1
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	2.2 ± 0.4	3.6 ± 0.2	3.5 ± 0.4	2.9 ± 0.9
Gram- bacteria	6.0 ± 0.9	9.0 ± 0.5	8.6 ± 1.4	7.2 ± 1.9
Total Fungi	5.4 ± 0.9	7.5 ± 0.9	6.9 ± 1.0	6.3 ± 1.6
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.1 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.3	1.4 ± 0.4
Zygomycota	3.2 ± 0.4	4.3 ± 0.4	3.9 ± 0.5	3.5 ± 0.8
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	1.1 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 0.3	1.4 ± 0.4
Unspecific microbial	4.4 ± 0.8	5.8 ± 0.4	5.6 ± 0.8	5.2 ± 1.4

Table 3.3. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS2 (Southern Mediterranean pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, control with standard organic fertilization; org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70%; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial inoculant; org70BioBaFu, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial and fungal inoculants.

TABLE 3.4

	CTRL	ALT1POT	ALT2POT
Total PLFA	56.9 ± 12.9	63.4 ± 5.4	48.3 ± 16.9
Total Bacteria	33.4 ± 7.9	36.7 ± 3.5	27.8 ± 10.2
Gram+ bacteria	21.6 ± 5.2	23.5 ± 2.7	17.6 ± 6.0
<i>Firmicutes</i>	14.9 ± 3.1	15.9 ± 1.8	12.2 ± 4.1
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	6.7 ± 2.1	7.7 ± 1.1	5.3 ± 1.9
Gram- bacteria	11.8 ± 2.9	13.1 ± 1.0	10.2 ± 4.2
Total Fungi	6.4 ± 1.5	7.9 ± 0.5	6.2 ± 3.0
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	0.9 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.3
Zygomycota	4.8 ± 1.2	6.0 ± 0.5	4.5 ± 2.2
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.7 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.6
Unspecific microbial	17.1 ± 3.6	18.8 ± 1.7	14.3 ± 3.7

Table 3.4. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments carried out in the case study CS3 (Lusitanian pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, control with conventional potato treatment; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field.

TABLE 3.5

	CTRL	MYCPOTH P	MYCNO P	POTHP	POTNOP
Total PLFA	39.7 ± 2.3	36.6 ± 5.6	41.9 ± 5.1	35.2 ± 3.4	30.6 ± 4.8
Total Bacteria	23.1 ± 1.6	21.0 ± 3.4	24.3 ± 3.1	19.9 ± 2.2	17.1 ± 2.9
Gram+ bacteria	15.0 ± 0.8	13.5 ± 2.0	15.8 ± 1.8	12.2 ± 1.6	10.3 ± 1.7
<i>Firmicutes</i>	10.5 ± 0.4	9.6 ± 1.7	11.0 ± 1.3	7.8 ± 1.1	6.7 ± 1.2
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	4.5 ± 0.7	3.9 ± 0.6	4.7 ± 0.5	4.4 ± 0.5	3.7 ± 0.5
Gram- bacteria	8.1 ± 0.9	7.4 ± 1.4	8.5 ± 1.4	7.7 ± 0.8	6.8 ± 1.3
Total Fungi	5.0 ± 0.5	4.3 ± 0.6	5.1 ± 0.9	4.7 ± 0.5	3.8 ± 0.6
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.0 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1
Zygomycota	3.3 ± 0.3	2.8 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.5	3.2 ± 0.3	2.6 ± 0.3
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.7 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.3	0.7 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1
Unspecific microbial	11.7 ± 0.3	11.3 ± 1.6	12.5 ± 1.1	10.7 ± 0.9	9.7 ± 1.3

Table 3.5. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as

well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS4 (Lusitanian pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, control with conventional P fertilization in potato; MycNoP, mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization in potato; MycPotHP, mycorrhizal inoculant plus half the P fertilization in potato; PotHP, half the P fertilization in potato; PotNoP, potato field with no P fertilization.

TABLE 3.6

	CTRL	CONVPOTFA	POTNOFA
Total PLFA	31.6 ± 4.2	33.5 ± 2.0	31.6 ± 4.5
Total Bacteria	18.5 ± 2.7	19.5 ± 1.1	18.2 ± 3.2
Gram+ bacteria	12.3 ± 1.9	12.5 ± 0.7	11.8 ± 1.6
<i>Firmicutes</i>	7.9 ± 1.4	8.3 ± 0.5	7.8 ± 0.9
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	4.3 ± 0.5	4.2 ± 0.3	3.9 ± 0.7
Gram- bacteria	6.2 ± 0.8	7.0 ± 0.3	6.4 ± 1.6
Total Fungi	3.7 ± 0.4	4.2 ± 0.3	3.6 ± 0.7
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	0.5 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.1
Zygomycota	2.7 ± 0.2	3.1 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.5
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.5 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1
Unspecific microbial	9.4 ± 1.1	9.9 ± 0.7	9.8 ± 0.6

Table 3.6. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS5 (Lusitanian pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, pest alert system control in potato; ConvPotFA, conventional fungicide application in potato; PotNoFA, potato without fungicide application.

TABLE 3.7

	CTRL	AFV	FYM	AFV FYM	BR FYM	AFV BR FYM
Total PLFA	23.9 ± 3.0	28.1 ± 4.2	28.1 ± 3.5	25.9 ± 2.9	24.9 ± 3.1	25.61 ± 2.1
Total Bacteria	15.0 ± 1.9	17.9 ± 3.0	18.2 ± 2.4	16.0 ± 1.8	15.8 ± 2.3	16.6 ± 1.6
Gram+ bacteria	8.6 ± 0.9	9.9 ± 1.4	9.9 ± 1.5	8.7 ± 0.9	8.7 ± 1.0	9.4 ± 0.8
<i>Firmicutes</i>	5.8 ± 0.9	6.6 ± 0.7	6.7 ± 1.0	5.9 ± 1.0	5.9 ± 0.8	6.3 ± 0.6
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	2.8 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.7	3.2 ± 0.5	2.9 ± 0.4	2.8 ± 0.3	3.1 ± 0.4
Gram- bacteria	6.4 ± 1.0	8.0 ± 1.7	8.3 ± 1.0	7.3 ± 1.1	7.1 ± 1.3	7.3 ± 0.8
Total Fungi	3.2 ± 0.5	3.8 ± 0.7	3.9 ± 0.5	3.8 ± 0.6	3.4 ± 0.5	3.4 ± 0.3
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	0.9 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.1
Zygomycota	2.0 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.3	2.2 ± 0.3	2.3 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.1
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0
Unspecific microbial	5.7 ± 0.7	6.4 ± 0.6	6.1 ± 0.8	6.1 ± 0.7	5.8 ± 0.4	5.6 ± 0.3

Table 3.7. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS6 (Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, FYM = with farm yard manure; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed; AFV FYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure; AFVbr FYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material; br FYM = farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves).

TABLE 3.8

	CTRL	MIX5	MIX12	PHAEGCLOV
Total PLFA	39.9 ± 5.2	34.1 ± 1.3	40.3 ± 5.1	36.7 ± 3.6
Total Bacteria	25.6 ± 3.6	21.9 ± 0.8	25.6 ± 3.3	23.6 ± 2.6
Gram+ bacteria	13.7 ± 1.9	12.9 ± 1.2	13.6 ± 1.4	13.2 ± 1.5
<i>Firmicutes</i>	9.0 ± 1.2	8.3 ± 0.4	8.9 ± 0.9	8.5 ± 0.7
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	4.7 ± 0.7	4.6 ± 0.8	4.7 ± 0.5	4.7 ± 0.9
Gram- bacteria	11.9 ± 1.8	9.0 ± 0.9	12.0 ± 1.9	10.4 ± 1.6
Total Fungi	5.6 ± 0.9	4.3 ± 0.2	5.5 ± 0.8	4.9 ± 0.7
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.5 ± 0.3	1.1 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.3	1.2 ± 0.3
Zygomycota	3.4 ± 0.5	2.9 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.4	3.1 ± 0.4
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.7 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.1
Unspecific microbial	8.8 ± 0.7	7.9 ± 0.4	9.1 ± 1.1	8.3 ± 0.5

Table 3.8. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS7 (Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, standard conditions for potato as control; PhaEgClov, Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crops for potato; Mix5, mixture of 5 cover crop species for potato; Mix12, mixture of 12 cover crop species for potato.

TABLE 3.9

	CONVIN T	CONVEX	ORGINT	ORGEXT
Total PLFA	37.9 ± 2.6	41.4 ± 1.3	35.4 ± 2.7	48.9 ± 5.2
Total Bacteria	22.3 ± 1.6	23.8 ± 2.1	20.4 ± 1.7	28.3 ± 2.2
Gram+ bacteria	12.6 ± 1.0	13.5 ± 1.4	11.6 ± 0.9	15.9 ± 1.2
<i>Firmicutes</i>	8.1 ± 0.7	9.1 ± 1.1	7.9 ± 0.7	11.0 ± 0.9
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	4.5 ± 0.4	4.5 ± 0.3	3.6 ± 0.2	5.0 ± 0.3
Gram- bacteria	9.7 ± 0.7	10.3 ± 0.8	8.8 ± 0.9	12.4 ± 1.0
Total Fungi	5.3 ± 0.5	6.3 ± 0.3	5.1 ± 0.5	7.7 ± 0.9
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.4 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	2.3 ± 0.2
Zygomycota	3.0 ± 0.3	3.2 ± 0.1	2.8 ± 0.2	4.0 ± 0.4

Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.9 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.2
Unspecific microbial	10.3 ± 0.5	11.3 ± 1.5	9.9 ± 0.6	13.0 ± 2.3

Table 3.9. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS8 (Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables.

TABLE 3.10

	CTRL	COMP	FYM	FERM
Total PLFA	42.5 ± 5.0	47.4 ± 4.8	46.9 ± 3.6	48.9 ± 8.3
Total Bacteria	26.5 ± 2.2	29.9 ± 2.7	29.8 ± 2.1	30.8 ± 5.8
Gram+ bacteria	14.1 ± 1.3	15.6 ± 1.8	15.2 ± 0.8	16.1 ± 2.7
<i>Firmicutes</i>	9.2 ± 0.9	10.2 ± 1.3	9.9 ± 0.6	10.6 ± 1.8
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	5.0 ± 0.4	5.4 ± 0.5	5.3 ± 0.3	5.5 ± 1.0
Gram- bacteria	12.4 ± 0.9	14.3 ± 1.0	14.6 ± 1.3	14.7 ± 3.1
Total Fungi	7.5 ± 1.4	8.3 ± 0.9	8.3 ± 0.6	8.6 ± 1.4
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	2.1 ± .02	2.5 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.4
Zygomycota	4.4 ± 0.8	4.7 ± 0.4	4.8 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.8
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	1.0 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.3
Unspecific microbial	8.5 ± 1.5	9.2 ± 1.2	8.9 ± 0.9	9.4 ± 1.1

Table 3.10. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS9 (Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, control wheat field without manure; Comp, composted green manure for wheat; FYM, farmyard manure for wheat; Ferm, fermented green manure for wheat.

TABLE 3.11

	CTRL	BIOSTIM	BIOSTIMADJ
Total PLFA	50.2 ± 8.2	45.3 ± 10.5	43.4 ± 4.8
Total Bacteria	32.4 ± 5.5	29.1 ± 6.9	27.7 ± 3.4
Gram+ bacteria	15.5 ± 2.0	14.2 ± 3.4	13.0 ± 1.7
<i>Firmicutes</i>	9.4 ± 1.2	8.6 ± 2.1	7.9 ± 1.1
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	6.1 ± 0.9	5.6 ± 1.3	5.0 ± 0.7
Gram- bacteria	16.9 ± 3.5	14.9 ± 3.5	14.7 ± 1.7
Total Fungi	9.2 ± 1.9	8.1 ± 2.2	7.9 ± 1.0
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	2.2 ± 0.6	1.9 ± 0.6	1.9 ± 0.2
Zygomycota	5.2 ± 1.0	4.7 ± 1.3	4.5 ± 0.6
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	1.7 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 0.5	1.4 ± 0.4

Unspecific microbial 8.6 ± 0.9 8.1 ± 1.4 7.9 ± 0.5

Table 3.11. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS10a (Continental pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation with reduced fungicides as control; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), and reduced fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G), and reduced fungicides.

TABLE 3.12

	CTRL	STRIPUNDSOW	BROADUNDSOW
Total PLFA	24.8 ± 11.3	31.8 ± 2.2	31.5 ± 0.8
Total Bacteria	12.8 ± 5.6	17.0 ± 0.9	16.7 ± 0.9
Gram+ bacteria	6.8 ± 3.2	9.5 ± 0.5	9.3 ± 0.6
<i>Firmicutes</i>	4.5 ± 2.1	6.3 ± 0.4	6.1 ± 0.4
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	2.3 ± 1.1	3.2 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.2
Gram- bacteria	6.0 ± 2.5	7.5 ± 0.5	7.5 ± 0.3
Total Fungi	4.6 ± 2.1	4.9 ± 0.6	5.0 ± 0.2
Arbsucular mycorrhizal fungi	0.9 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.0	1.1 ± 0.1
Zygomycota	1.9 ± 0.7	2.3 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.3
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	1.8 ± 1.1	1.5 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 0.2
Unspecific microbial	7.4 ± 3.6	9.9 ± 0.8	9.8 ± 0.5

Table 3.12. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS10b (Continental pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, standard crop management for potato as control; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing.

TABLE 3.13

	CTRL	EXTWHE	DIVEXTWHE
Total PLFA	49.8 ± 7.9	53.9 ± 4.1	49.5 ± 7.1
Total Bacteria	31.1 ± 5.7	33.8 ± 2.8	31.8 ± 4.7
Gram+ bacteria	15.8 ± 3.2	17.3 ± 1.5	16.2 ± 2.3
<i>Firmicutes</i>	9.9 ± 2.0	10.8 ± 1.0	10.1 ± 1.5
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	5.9 ± 1.2	6.4 ± 0.5	6.0 ± 0.8
Gram- bacteria	15.4 ± 2.5	16.6 ± 1.4	15.6 ± 2.5
Total Fungi	8.1 ± 1.1	8.8 ± 0.8	7.8 ± 1.3

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.9 ± 0.4	2.0 ± 0.3	1.9 ± 0.3
Zygomycota	4.8 ± 0.7	5.4 ± 0.4	4.8 ± 0.7
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	1.4 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2
Unspecific microbial	10.6 ± 1.2	11.2 ± 0.6	9.9 ± 1.1

Table 3.12. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS11 (Continental pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; ExtWhw, extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides.

TABLE 3.14

	ORGCONVTILL	CONVCONVTILL	CONVNOTILL	FIELDEDGE
Total PLFA	59.3 ± 4.3	69.0 ± 6.7	90.9 ± 10.7	70.7
Total Bacteria	38.6 ± 1.9	45.4 ± 6.0	59.7 ± 6.6	44.7
Gram+ bacteria	19.7 ± 1.6	21.7 ± 2.7	31.1 ± 3.2	23.9
<i>Firmicutes</i>	12.8 ± 1.1	13.9 ± 1.9	19.7 ± 1.4	15.7
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	6.9 ± 0.4	7.8 ± 0.8	11.4 ± 1.8	8.2
Gram- bacteria	18.9 ± 0.3	23.6 ± 3.3	28.6 ± 3.4	20.8
Total Fungi	9.1 ± 0.2	11.8 ± 0.8	15.1 ± 2.7	10.9
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	2.9 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.6	4.4 ± 1.3	2.5
Zygomycota	5.3 ± 0.1	7.1 ± 0.3	9.4 ± 1.5	7.2
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.8 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.0	1.2
Unspecific microbial	11.7 ± 2.2	11.9 ± 0.1	16.1 ± 1.4	15.1

Table 3.14. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS12 (Nemoral pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage; ConvConvTill: conventional farming with conventional tillage; ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage; FieldEdge, conditions at the edge of the field.

TABLE 3.15

	CTRL	FS	CPMS
Total PLFA	41.9 ± 14.9	46.2 ± 17.7	45.1 ± 18.8
Total Bacteria	23.8 ± 10.0	27.5 ± 11.6	26.4 ± 12.0
Gram+ bacteria	12.7 ± 5.5	14.7 ± 6.7	14.0 ± 6.7
<i>Firmicutes</i>	7.5 ± 3.2	8.7 ± 4.4	8.5 ± 4.1

<i>Actinobacteria</i>	5.3 ± 2.3	5.9 ± 2.3	5.5 ± 2.6
Gram- bacteria	11.1 ± 4.5	12.9 ± 4.9	12.4 ± 5.3
Total Fungi	6.6 ± 2.2	6.1 ± 2.2	6.1 ± 2.2
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.0 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.3	0.9 ± 0.3
Zygomycota	4.7 ± 2.0	4.1 ± 1.6	4.2 ± 1.7
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.9 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.2
Unspecific microbial	11.5 ± 3.5	12.5 ± 4.0	12.6 ± 4.6

Table 3.15. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS13 (Boreal pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment.

TABLE 3.16

	CTRL	PLOUGH
Total PLFA	38.4 ± 6.4	37.0 ± 3.6
Total Bacteria	23.1 ± 3.8	22.2 ± 2.1
Gram+ bacteria	11.1 ± 2.2	10.6 ± 1.2
<i>Firmicutes</i>	6.5 ± 1.4	6.1 ± 0.9
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	4.6 ± 0.9	4.4 ± 0.3
Gram- bacteria	12.1 ± 1.6	11.6 ± 0.9
Total Fungi	5.7 ± 0.8	5.4 ± 0.3
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.5 ± 0.3	1.4 ± 0.1
Zygomycota	3.6 ± 0.5	3.4 ± 0.1
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	0.6 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1
Unspecific microbial	9.6 ± 1.9	9.4 ± 1.3

Table 3.16. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS14a (Boreal pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring.

TABLE 3.17

	CTRL	PLOUGH
Total PLFA	72.6 ± 7.1	65.3 ± 8.7
Total Bacteria	46.3 ± 5.0	42.0 ± 6.0
Gram+ bacteria	23.2 ± 2.2	21.1 ± 2.7
<i>Firmicutes</i>	15.9 ± 1.4	14.5 ± 1.7

<i>Actinobacteria</i>	7.3 ± 0.8	6.6 ± 1.0
Gram- bacteria	23.1 ± 2.7	20.9 ± 3.3
Total Fungi	12.4 ± 1.2	10.8 ± 1.4
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	3.9 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.4
Zygomycota	6.7 ± 0.6	5.9 ± 0.7
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	1.8 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 0.3
Unspecific microbial	14.0 ± 1.1	12.6 ± 1.3

Table 3.17. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS14b (Boreal pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn.

TABLE 3.18

	CTRL	PHA	RYE
Total PLFA	42.4 ± 3.7	40.2 ± 7.8	39.7 ± 6.7
Total Bacteria	23.7 ± 2.4	21.9 ± 4.7	22.2 ± 4.5
Gram+ bacteria	11.8 ± 1.8	10.3 ± 2.8	10.7 ± 2.5
<i>Firmicutes</i>	7.3 ± 1.7	6.1 ± 1.9	6.4 ± 1.4
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	4.4 ± 0.3	4.2 ± 0.9	4.3 ± 1.0
Gram- bacteria	11.9 ± 0.7	11.7 ± 1.9	11.5 ± 2.1
Total Fungi	6.2 ± 0.3	6.3 ± 1.2	6.1 ± 0.7
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	1.3 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.3
Zygomycota	3.8 ± 0.1	3.9 ± 0.8	3.7 ± 0.4
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota	1.1 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.0
Unspecific microbial	12.6 ± 1.2	12.0 ± 2.0	11.4 ± 1.5

Table 3.18. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹), as well as abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹), found for the different treatments/management practices carried out in the case study CS15 (Boreal pedoclimatic region). Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after early potato harvest; rye, mixture of rye grass as cover crop after early potato harvest.

3.3.1 Total microbial abundance

The total microbial abundance data (estimated as total PLFAs) for the control treatment, taking into account all case studies, varied between 20.7 ± 3.6 nmol g⁻¹ for CS2 and 72.6 ± 7.1 nmol g⁻¹ for CS14b (Tables 3.2 to 3.18). Significant differences between the different case studies were found (F= 14.083, P<0.001), following the next sequence: CS2 < CS6 ≈ CS10b ≈ CS1 < CS5 < CS8 < CS14a ≈ CS4 ≈ CS7 <

CS13 ≈ CS15 ≈ CS9 < CS11 ≈ CS10a < CS3 < CS12 < CS14b. Grouping

the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F=6.954$, $P<0.001$), following the next sequence: Mediterranean South < Atlantic Central ≈ Continental ≈ Lusitanian < Boreal < Nemoral.

On the other hand, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were only found in case studies CS4 ($F=3.873$, $P<0.05$), following the sequence PotNoP < PotHP ≈ MycPotHP ≈ Ctrl < MycNoP, and CS8 ($F=13.033$, $P<0.001$), following the sequence ConvInt ≈ ConvExt ≈ OrgInt < OrgExt.

3.3.2 Total bacterial abundance

The values for bacterial abundance (expressed as bacterial PLFAs) for the control treatment considering all case studies ranged from 10.9 ± 2.0 nmol g^{-1} for CS2 to 46.3 ± 5.0 nmol g^{-1} for CS14b (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), showing significant differences between the different case studies ($F=15.861$, $P<0.001$), with the sequence: CS2 < CS10b < CS1 ≈ CS6 < CS5 < CS8 ≈ CS4 ≈ CS14a ≈ CS15 ≈ CS13 ≈ CS7 ≈ CS9 ≈ CS11 ≈ CS10 < CS3 < CS12 < CS14b. Taking into account the pedoclimatic regions, significant differences were also found ($F=6.498$, $P<0.001$), following the sequence: Mediterranean South < Atlantic Center ≈ Continental ≈ Lusitanian < Boreal < Nemoral, which is equal to that obtained for the

total microbial abundance. Finally, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were found in case studies CS2 ($F=4.082$, $P<0.05$), with the sequence Ctrl < org70 ≈ orgBioBaFu < org70BioBa, CS4 ($F=4.248$, $P<0.95$), with the sequence PotNoP < PotHP ≈ MycPotHP < Ctrl ≈ MycNoP, and CS8 ($F=12.148$, $P<0.001$), with the sequence OrgInt ≈ ConvInt ≈ ConvExt < OrgExt.

3.3.2.1 Gram-positive bacteria abundance

Bacterial Gram+ PLFAs data for the control treatment considering all case studies ranged from 5.0 ± 1.1 nmol g^{-1} for CS2 to 23.2 ± 2.2 nmol g^{-1} for CS14b (Tables 3.2 to 3.18). Significant differences between the different case studies have been found ($F=13.779$, $p<0.001$), following the sequence CS2 < CS10b < CS1 ≈ CS6 < CS14a ≈ CS15 ≈ CS5 ≈ CS8 ≈ CS13 ≈ CS7 ≈ CS9 < CS4 ≈ CS10 ≈ CS11 < CS3 ≈ CS12 ≈ CS14b, which is very similar to that obtained for the total microbial abundance and the total bacterial abundance. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F=6.482$, $P<0.001$), with the sequence Mediterranean South < Atlantic Center ≈ Continental < Boreal ≈ Lusitanian ≈ Nemoral.

On the other hand, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were found in case studies CS4 ($F=7.127$, $P<0.05$), following the sequence PotNoP < PotHP < MycPotHP ≈ Ctrl ≈ MycNoP, CS8 ($F=10.847$, $P<0.001$), following the sequence OrgInt ≈ ConvInt ≈ ConvExt < OrgExt, and CS12 ($F=11.024$, $P<0.05$), following the sequence OrgConvTill < ConvConvTill ≈ ConvNoTill.

3.3.2.1.1 Actinobacteria abundance

Actinobacterial abundance (expressed as sum of PLFA markers related with this group) for the control treatment considering all case studies ranged between 2.2 ± 0.4 nmol g^{-1} for CS2 and 11.4 ± 1.8 nmol g^{-1} for CS12 (Tables 3.2 to 3.18). Significant differences between the different case studies have been

found ($F = 8.737$, $P < 0.001$), obtaining the following sequence:

CS2 \approx CS10b < CS6 < CS1 < CS5 \approx CS15 \approx CS8 \approx CS4 < CS14a \approx CS7 \approx CS9 < CS13 \approx CS11 \approx CS10a \approx CS3 \approx CS14b \approx CS12. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F = 5.330$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Mediterranean South < Atlantic Central \approx Continental \approx Lusitanian < Boreal \approx Nemoral. Finally, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were only found in case study CS2 ($F = 5.618$, $P < 0.05$), with the sequence Ctrl < org70 \approx org70BioBaFu \approx org70BioBa.

3.3.2.1.2 Firmicutes abundance

Firmicutes PLFAs data for the control treatment taking into account all case studies ranged from 2.8 ± 0.7 nmol g⁻¹ for CS2 to 19.7 ± 1.4 nmol g⁻¹ for CS12 (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), showing significant differences between the different case studies ($F = 17.203$, $p < 0.001$), obtaining the next sequence: CS2 < CS10b < CS1 < CS6 < CS14a \approx CS15 \approx CS13 \approx CS5 \approx CS8 \approx CS7 \approx CS9 \approx CS10a \approx CS11 < CS4 < CS12 \approx CS3 \approx CS14b. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F = 6.974$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Mediterranean South < Continental \approx Atlantic Central < Boreal \approx Lusitanian \approx Nemoral.

On the other hand, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were found in case studies CS4 ($F = 9.248$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence PotNoP

< PotHP < MycPotHP \approx Ctrl \approx MycNoP, CS8 ($F = 10.487$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence OrgInt \approx ConvInt \approx ConvExt < OrgExt, and CS12 ($F = 11.826$, $P < 0.05$), with the sequence OrgConvTill < ConvConvTill \approx ConvNoTill.

3.3.2.2 Gram-negative bacteria abundance

Bacterial Gram- PLFAs data for the control treatment considering all case studies varied between 4.5 ± 1.3 nmol g⁻¹ for CS1 and 28.6 ± 3.4 nmol g⁻¹ for CS12 (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), with significant differences between the different case studies ($F = 20.962$, $p < 0.001$), following the sequence: CS2 < CS10b < CS1 \approx CS5 \approx CS6 < CS4 < CS8 < CS13 \approx CS3 \approx CS7 \approx CS15 \approx CS14a \approx CS9 \approx CS11 \approx CS10a < CS14b \approx CS12. Taking into account the pedoclimatic regions, significant differences were also found ($F = 8.980$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Mediterranean South < Lusitanian \approx Atlantic Center \approx Continental \approx Boreal < Nemoral.

On the other hand, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were only found in case studies CS2 ($F = 4.742$, $P < 0.05$), following the sequence Ctrl < org70 \approx org70BioBaFu \approx org70BioBa, and CS8 ($F = 12.688$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence OrgInt \approx ConvInt \approx ConvExt < OrgExt.

3.3.3 Total fungi abundance

The values for fungi abundance, expressed as fungi PLFAs, for the control treatment considering all case studies ranged from 3.0 ± 0.7 nmol g⁻¹ for CS1 to 15.1 ± 2.7 nmol g⁻¹ for CS12 (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), showing significant differences between the different case studies ($F = 15.574$, $P < 0.001$), following the next sequence: CS6 < CS5 \approx CS1 < CS10b < CS4 \approx CS8 \approx CS2 \approx CS7 \approx CS14a < CS15 \approx CS3 \approx CS13 \approx CS9 \approx CS11 < CS10a \approx CS12 \approx CS14b. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F = 6.066$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Mediterranean South \approx

which is very similar to that obtained for total bacterial abundance. Finally, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were only found in case study CS8 ($F = 15.005$, $P < 0.001$), obtaining the sequence OrgInt ≈ ConvInt ≈ ConvExt < OrgExt.

3.3.3.1 Arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi abundance

The values for arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi abundance (expressed as arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi PLFAs) for the control treatment considering all case studies varied between 0.5 ± 0.1 nmol g⁻¹ for CS5 and 4.4 ± 1.3 nmol g⁻¹ for CS12 (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), showing significant differences between the different case studies ($F = 33.486$, $P < 0.001$), following the next sequence: CS5 < CS10b ≈ CS1 ≈ CS3 ≈ CS6 ≈ CS13 ≈ CS4 < CS2 ≈ CS15 < CS8 < CS7 ≈ CS14a ≈ CS11 ≈ CS9 ≈ CS10a < CS12 ≈ CS14b. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F = 6.045$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Lusitanian ≈ Mediterranean South ≈ Atlantic Central ≈ Continental ≈ Boreal < Nemoral.

On the other hand, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were only found in case studies CS4 ($F = 5.282$, $P < 0.05$), obtaining the sequence PotNoP < PotHP ≈ MycPotHP ≈ Ctrl ≈ MycNoP, and CS8 ($F = 28.121$, $P < 0.001$), obtaining the sequence ConvInt ≈ OrgInt < ConvExt ≈ OrgExt.

3.3.3.2 Zygomycota fungi abundance

The values for zygomycota fungi abundance (expressed as zygomycota fungi PLFAs) for the control treatment considering all case studies ranged from 1.8 ± 0.4 nmol g⁻¹ for CS1 to 9.4 ± 1.5 nmol g⁻¹ for CS12 (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), obtaining significant differences between the different case studies ($F = 12.177$, $P < 0.001$), following the sequence: CS10b ≈ CS6 < CS1 < CS5 < CS8 < CS2 ≈ CS4 ≈ CS7 ≈ CS14a ≈ CS15 ≈ CS9 < CS13 ≈ CS3 ≈ CS11 < CS10a ≈ CS14b ≈ CS12. Taking into account the different pedoclimatic regions, significant differences were also found ($F = 5.537$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Mediterranean South ≈ Atlantic Central ≈ Lusitana ≈ Continental ≈ Boreal < Nemoral.

Finally, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were only found in case studies CS8 ($F = 13.775$, $P < 0.001$), following the sequence OrgInt ≈ ConvInt ≈ ConvExt < OrgExt, and CS12 ($F = 10.629$, $P < 0.05$), with the sequence OrgConvTill < ConvConvTill ≈ ConvNoTill.

3.3.3.3 Ascomycota and Basidiomycota abundance

The values for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi abundance for the control treatment taking into account all case studies varied between 0.3 ± 0.1 nmol g⁻¹ for CS6 and 1.8 ± 1.1 nmol g⁻¹ for CS10b (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), showing significant differences between the different case studies ($F = 6.724$, $P < 0.001$), obtaining the next sequence: CS6 < CS5 ≈ CS14a ≈ CS7 ≈ CS4 ≈ CS3 < CS1 < CS13 ≈ CS8 ≈ CS9 ≈ CS2 ≈ CS15 ≈ CS12 ≈ CS11 ≈ CS10a ≈ CS10b ≈ CS14b. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F = 8.709$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Lusitanian < Atlantic Central < Mediterranean South ≈ Boreal ≈ Nemoral ≈ Continental.

On the other hand, when management

practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were found in case studies CS2 ($F = 3.102$, $P < 0.05$), with the sequence Ctrl < org70 \approx org70BioBaFu \approx org70BioBa, CS7 ($F = 4.984$, $P < 0.05$), with the sequence Mix5 < PhaEgClov \approx Ctrl \approx Mix12, CS8 ($F = 5.721$, $P < 0.05$), with the sequence OrgInt \approx ConvInt < ConvExt \approx OrgExt, and CS12 ($F = 19.666$, $P < 0.05$), with the sequence OrgConvTill < ConvNoTill \approx ConvConvTill.

3.3.4 Unespecific microbial

Finally, the values for unespecific microbial abundance for the control treatment taking into account all case studies varied between 4.4 ± 0.8 nmol g⁻¹ for CS2 and 18.8 ± 1.7 nmol g⁻¹ for CS3 (Tables 3.2 to 3.18), showing significant differences between the different case studies ($F = 11.864$, $P < 0.001$), following the next sequence: CS2 < CS3 < CS1 < CS10b < CS9 \approx CS10a \approx CS7 < CS5 \approx CS14 \approx CS8 \approx CS11 \approx CS13 \approx CS4 \approx CS12 < CS15 \approx CS14b \approx CS3. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F = 11.996$, $P < 0.001$), with the sequence: Mediterranean South < Atlantic Central < Continental \approx Nemoral \approx Boreal \approx Lusitanian.

On the other hand, when management practices/treatments were compared for each case study, significant differences were found in case studies CS1 ($F = 4.406$, $P < 0.05$), following the sequence fert50 < red50Bacto \approx red50Nuve \approx Ctrl, CS4 ($F = 3.399$, $P < 0.05$), following the sequence PotNoP < Ctrl \approx MycPotHP \approx Ctrl \approx MycNoP, and CS8 ($F = 3.851$, $P < 0.05$), following the sequence OrgInt < ConvInt \approx ConvExt \approx OrgExt.

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4 Nematode diversity

4.1 Introduction

Nematodes are among the most abundant multicellular organisms on Earth, playing crucial roles in various ecosystems, including agricultural environments. These microscopic worms can be classified broadly into two categories: free-living nematodes, which contribute to soil health and nutrient cycling, and plant-parasitic nematodes (PPNs), which can cause significant damage to crops. As we focus in this report on the complete biodiversity, the data obtained concerning PPNS is reserved for Deliverable Report 5.3 in which there is a special attention to ecosystem services including crop yield and quality and disease suppressiveness.

Assessing the diversity and abundance of nematode communities can provide insights into the biological activity and overall health of the soil. High diversity in nematode communities often correlates with healthy, resilient soils that support robust plant growth. Conversely, low diversity or

dominance by specific groups, such as PPNs, can indicate soil

degradation or potential crop threats. Therefore, regular monitoring of nematode communities can serve as an early warning system for soil health, allowing farmers to implement corrective measures before significant crop damage occurs (Ferris et al., 2001; Neher, 2001).

Agricultural practices significantly influence nematode community structure and function. Practices such as tillage, crop rotation, pesticide use, and organic amendments can either support or disrupt the balance of nematode communities. Tillage is a common agricultural practice that involves the mechanical disturbance of soil to prepare seedbeds and control weeds. However, tillage can have detrimental effects on nematode communities. It often leads to a reduction in nematode diversity by disrupting soil structure, which is crucial for the habitats of many free-living nematodes (Berkelmans et al., 2003; Bongiorno et al., 2019). Additionally, tillage can negatively impact organic matter and reduce the populations of beneficial nematodes, thereby impairing nutrient cycling processes (Bongers & Ferris, 1999). Crop rotation, on the other hand, can promote nematode diversity by providing a variety of root systems that support different nematode communities. Diverse crops can reduce the build-up of PPNs specific to certain plants, thereby lowering the risk of nematode-induced crop damage. For example, rotating susceptible crops with non-host plants can disrupt the life cycle of PPNs, reducing their populations and mitigating their impact on crops (Halbrendt & LaMondia, 2003). The application of organic amendments, such as compost or green manure, can enhance soil health by increasing organic matter content and supporting a diverse community of beneficial nematodes. Organic amendments provide a food source for bacterivorous and fungivorous nematodes, which in turn stimulate microbial activity and improve nutrient availability for plants. This practice can lead to healthier soils with more balanced nematode communities and fewer PPNs (Bulluck et al., 2002). While pesticides are used to control PPNs, their non-target effects can also reduce populations of beneficial nematodes, thereby disrupting soil ecology (Eisenhauer, 2010). Over-reliance on chemical control methods can lead to the development of pesticide-resistant nematode

strains and a decrease in overall soil health. Integrated pest management (IPM) strategies, which combine biological, cultural, and chemical controls, are recommended to manage nematode populations sustainably (Norris et al., 2003).

Nematode community assessments are vital tools for sustainable agricultural management. By understanding the composition and dynamics of nematode communities, farmers can gain insights into soil health and make informed decisions about management practices. Sustainable practices that promote nematode diversity, such as reduced tillage and pesticide use, a more diversified crop rotation, use of alternative organic amendments, can lead to healthier soils and more resilient agricultural systems. Ultimately, integrating nematode assessments into routine soil health monitoring can contribute to more sustainable and productive agricultural practices.

In this chapter, effects of different agricultural practices on nematode diversity and community composition in field studies across various pedoclimatic regions of Europe is investigated.

4.2 Material and Methods

4.2.1 Introduction

Traditionally, nematode identification relies on microscopic examination, where morphological traits, such as body shape, size, and specialized structures, are used to distinguish between different taxa. While effective, this method is time-consuming and requires expert taxonomists, making it less suitable for large-scale ecological studies which aim to investigate nematode suspensions from different soil samples containing each easily a few thousands of individuals. Additionally, some nematode species exhibit cryptic morphology, meaning they are morphologically indistinguishable despite being genetically distinct, which further complicates identification.

Advancements in molecular techniques, particularly DNA metabarcoding, have revolutionized nematode community analysis. DNA metabarcoding allows for high-throughput identification of nematode species by targeting specific genetic markers, such as the 18S rRNA gene, and sequencing them en masse. This approach can detect a broader diversity of nematodes, including those that are rare, small, or morphologically cryptic. Moreover, DNA metabarcoding enables the simultaneous identification of multiple species from mixed samples, which enhances the accuracy and efficiency of ecological studies. While DNA metabarcoding is a powerful tool, it is not without limitations, such as PCR biases, incomplete reference databases, and the potential for overestimating diversity due to sequencing errors.

To address some of the aforementioned limitations, DNA-extraction of nematode communities and the processing of raw sequence data, with special attention to taxon assignment, were optimized. Additionally, a curated and extended nematode DNA reference database (V6-V8 variable regions of the 18S rRNA gene) was created. All these efforts were executed during work package 4 as part of the SoildiverAgro-project (see D4.2 'Report on improved nematode DNA-metabarcoding') and the results

were implemented into a protocol to analyse the nematode communities from soil samples taken from the case-studies organized under work package 5. Integrating microscopic and molecular methods provides a more comprehensive understanding of nematode communities, offering valuable insights into their ecological roles and the health of soil ecosystems.

4.2.2 Nematode extraction

Soil samples from a total of 17 case-studies organized in 9 different pedoclimatic regions were collected. More information about the case-studies, their set-up, management and location, can be found in Deliverable Report D5.4. From each sample, a sub-sample of 100cc was separated to collect the nematode communities from by automated zonal centrifugation (Hendrickx, 1995). As already explained in Deliverable Report D3.3, this technique uses a separation liquid (MgSO_4) with a certain

density to separate the nematodes (and some other organic particles

and organisms) from the mineral fraction of the soil during centrifugation. The result is a nematode suspension in 150ml of water with a residual amount of the separation liquid. The nematode suspension subsequently is reduced until approximately 40ml after a minimum of 4 hours during which the nematodes settle down to the bottom of the beaker. At this point, the beakers can be processed immediately or stored at 4°C during one week before further processing.

4.2.3 Morphological analysis

Similar to the nematode suspensions collected for work package 3, the total number of nematode individuals was determined using a binocular microscope (Leica M80, 40X) (see Deliverable Report D3.3). After counting, the nematode suspension was concentrated as explained in “Handbook - protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis” (Calviño et al., 2020; <http://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>) for molecular analysis.

The data of the morphological analysis was further processed in Microsoft 365 Excel-program and in the open-source programming language and software environment ‘R’ version 4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024) (see chapter 4.2.5 for more details). Due to the low number of repeats per treatment in each case-study, the assumption of normality and homogeneity of the data is unlikely. Therefore a non-parametric statistical model (Wilcoxon rank-sum test) was applied to determine which treatment did or did not significantly change the number of nematodes after application of a treatment. Although the number of nematodes give no information about the composition, a change already gives an indication of an effect of the treatment.

4.2.4 Nematode community sequencing

All nematode suspensions were also analysed molecularly by DNA-metabarcoding. Briefly, DNA was extracted using the DNeasy Powersoil Powerlyzer DNA-extraction Kit (Qiagen) with little modifications, the quality and concentration of the DNA was checked several times with a UV-spectrophotometer (Nanodrop ND-1000, ThermoFisher Scientific) or fluorometer (Quantus E6150,

Promega), a library was prepared from each nematode DNA extract by applying a 2-step amplification process. Amplicon libraries with sample-specific indices were pooled in equimolar amounts according to the instructions provided by the sequence service company (Admera Health Biopharma Services, South Plainfield, USA) and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq PE300 platform (2 x 300 bp). More specifically, from each nematode, the V6-V8 expansion region of the 18S rRNA gene was sequenced, analysed and quality checked. The retained sequences were characterized by comparing them with our in-house curated custom NCBI reference nematode sequence database complemented with own sequence data. A more detailed description of this procedure can be found in the Handbook of WP3 (‘Protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis’, (Calviño et al., 2020; <http://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>) and the Deliverable report D3.3.

4.2.5 Nematode community sequence analysis

All steps for the nematode sequence analysis was conducted in the open-source programming language and software environment 'R' version 4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024) using, especially, the DADA2 v. 1.32.0 (Callahan et al., 2016), the Phyloseq v. 1.48.0 (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013), the vegan v. 2.6-6.1 (Oksanen, 2023), the DESeq2 v. 1.44.0 (Love et al., 2014) and the ggplot2 v. 3.5.1 (Wickham, 2016) packages. The dada2 package infers exact amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) from high-throughput amplicon sequencing data, replacing the coarser and less accurate OTU clustering approach. The dada2 pipeline takes as input demultiplexed fastq files which we received from the sequence service company (Admera Health Biopharma Services, South Plainfield, USA), and outputs the sequence variants and their sample-wise abundances after removing substitution and chimera errors. Taxonomic classification is established applying the native implementation of the RDP naive Bayesian classifier, and species/genus-level assignment to our in house curated nematode sequence database by exact matching. Phyloseq was used to calculate (relative) abundances for each sequence variant per sample subsequently followed by removing unassigned sequences at order level (as blasting with the NCBI sequence databased indicated that these sequences do not belong to the phylum Nematoda) and sequences of which the abundance is <10. In conjunction with vegan, DESeq2 and ggplot2, alpha diversity indices (Shannon and InvSimpson) were calculated, and beta diversity analysis, including NMDS ordinations based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index and the statistical analysis PERMANOVA, performed. Additional statistical tests like Wilcoxon rank-sum test to infer statistical significance, were executed (p-values below 0.05 were considered statistically significant). The abundances of taxa were compared with DESeq2 to determine key drivers (i.e., taxonomic nematode groups) responsible for any observed differences.

4.2.6 Nematode functional diversity analysis

Nematode functional guilds and a nematode-specific ecological index (Structural index; Ferris & Bongers, 2009), can be determined by importing the obtained data-set after the nematode community sequence analysis (see previous chapter) into the online freely accessible program Nematode INDicator Joint Analysis (NINJA, <https://sieriebriennikov.shinyapps.io/ninja/>) (Sieriebriennikov et al., 2014; Ferris et al., 2001).

As was mentioned in the Deliverable report D3.3, the frequencies of sequence reads assigned to certain nematode taxa don't correlate with the absolute numbers of individuals of the concerned taxa present in a soil sample (Creer et al., 2010). Various reasons can be recited but this phenomenon cannot yet be solved. As a result, the number of individuals belonging to certain nematode genera are overrated, while others are underrated following DNA-metabarcoding (Bik et al., 2013). More or less similar to the data of work package 3, we compared subsets of data within one case-study with each other and report whether treatment X resulted into a better or worse (functional) biodiversity compared to treatment Y in stead of assessing biodiversity *per se* due to the incorrectness of relative proportions between certain nematode genera.

4.3 Results and discussion

4.3.1 Absolute number of nematodes

All Case-studies

Overall we see a lower number of nematode individuals in the Mediterranean south and Lusitanian region (Iberian Peninsula) at the start of the case-studies (Figure. 4.1). Not considering the outlier of 12264 individuals, the number range from 216 till 6764 (mean = 2003,69). The Atlantic Central and Nemoral region averagely shows higher numbers ranging, not considering the outliers, from 1454 till 9526 (mean = 6062,46) while in the remaining regions (Continental and Boreal) it differs between the case-studies. Based on these numbers we cannot conclude much, however, it is very important to see that the nematodes seem not always to be uniformly distributed over the entire experimental areas. For a number of case-studies the box plots show a relatively larger distribution of the datapoints representing absolute numbers of individuals per soil sample at the beginning of the experiments. So it important to keep in mind that it will be needed to compare the results of each treatment within each case-study separately for conclusive remarks. The statistical significance of the change in absolute number of nematodes between the start and the end of the treatment in the separate case-studies can be found in table 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes per case-study at the start of the experiment (code = abbreviation of the pedoclimatic zone combined with the case-study (CS) number). CS1-2: MS = Mediterranean South, CS3-5: LUS = Lusitanian, CS6-9: AC = Atlantic Central, CS10-11: CON = Continental, CS12: NEM = Nemoral, CS13-15: BOR = Boreal.

TABLE 4.1

Ctrl	a	b	c	d	e
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CS 1	0,03	0,06	0,11	0,11	-	-
CS 2	0,34	0,03	0,20	0,06	-	-
CS 3	0,89	0,03	0,20	-	-	-
CS 4	0,34	0,69	0,49	0,49	0,34	-
CS 5	0,10	0,10	0,10	-	-	-
CS 6	0,03	0,06	0,03	0,03	0,11	0,03
CS 7	0,03	0,34	0,89	1,00	-	-
CS 8	0,53	0,53	0,06	1,00	-	-
CS 9	0,40	0,80	0,40	0,40	-	-
CS 10a	1,00	0,89	0,69	-	-	-
CS 10b	0,49	1,00	0,34	-	-	-
CS 11	0,03	0,49	0,03	-	-	-
CS 12	-	-	-	-	-	-
CS 13	0,34	0,03	0,03	-	-	-
CS 14a	0,03	0,03	-	-	-	-
CS 14b	0,69	0,03	-	-	-	-
CS 15	0,34	0,34	0,20	-	-	-

Table 4.1 Results (p-values) of the Wilcoxon rank-sum test to infer statistical significance of the change in absolute number of nematodes between the start and end of the treatments applied in each case-study. P-values less than or equal to 0.05 (in red) are considered statically significant. CS = case-study. For treatments explanation (Ctrl, a till e): see figures 4.2 till 4.8.

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

Only in the control-treatment in case-study 1 and treatment 'a' in case-study 2 the absolute number of nematodes significantly changed during the experiment (see table 4.1). However, in case-study 1 we consistently notice an increase in nematode counts, in case-study 2 a decrease (Figure 4.2). Although both case-studies applied the same product, a biofertilizer, in case-study 1 the product was used to replace a chemical fertilizer, in case-study 2 an organic fertilizer. Whether the different types of fertilizer, chemical versus organic, caused the opposite trend in nematode number is unclear. More important is to realise that the year of sampling is different and most probably interfered with the results. Indeed both case-studies started during the same year (2021) but case-study 1 ended in 2023, while case-study 2 already was terminated in 2022. In figure 4.3 it can be noticed that in case-study 1 during the year 2022 (second year) the number of nematodes remained more or less the same or was also decreasing. Therefor caution is at place when analysing the results of case-studies with a different

last year of sampling together. In fact, similar to the decision made for molecular data (see chapter 4.2.6), it was decided to analyse the data per case-study separately.

Figure 4.2. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 1 and 2. Case-study 1: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer. Case-study 2: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.1).

Figure 4.3. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes of the first and second year for each treatment within case-study 1: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer. Black dots = outliers.

Figure 4.4. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 3, 4 and 5. Case-study 3: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation. Case-study 4: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization. Case-study 5: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.1).

In all case-studies from the Lusitanian region, no significant changes in absolute number of nematodes was recorded with exception of treatment 'a' in case-study 3 (see table 4.1 and figure 4.4). In this treatment the number of nematodes dropped drastically while in the other treatment and control numbers of nematodes were maintained or increased moderately. In case-study 5 we notice a clear drop of nematode numbers in all treatments. A factor overruling the effect of the treatments must have occurred.

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

Figure 4.5. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 6, 7, 8 and 9. Case-study 6: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 7: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 8: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system. Case-study 9: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.1).

Case-study 6 is the only case-study of this region in which in most treatments (not treatment 'a' and 'd') the absolute number of nematodes significantly changed (see table 4.1 and figure 4.5). However, all treatments show the same decreasing trend of number of nematodes indicating towards a common factor overruling the treatments. The same can be noticed in case-study 9 although in this case always an increase in number of nematodes is recorded (Figure 4.5). In the other case-studies the number of

nematodes increased or decreased but not statistically significant with the exception of the control-treatment in case-study 7 (Figure 4.5).

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

Figure 4.6. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 10a, 10b and 11. Case-study 10a: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides. Case-study 10b: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 11: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.1).

No significant changes in number of nematodes was noted in case-studies 10a and b (see table 4.1 and figure 4.6). In case-study 11, treatment 'b' (together with the control treatment) significantly changed the number of nematodes while this was not the case for treatment 'a' (see table 4.1 and figure 4.6).

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

Figure 4.7. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes of the first and last year for each treatment within case-study 12: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.1).

In case-study 12 different plots were sampled during the different years of sampling. Therefore the boxplots (Figure 4.7) cannot reveal anything between the first and last year of sampling. For this case-study each sample will be analysed separately.

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

All treatments in case-studies 13, 14a and 14b caused a significant change in nematode number while this was not the case for the controls (with exception of case-study 14a although when excluding the outlier then also in this case the control-treatment becomes not statistically significant) (see table 4.1 and figure 4.8). The treatments in these cases were based on organic amendments or tillage. Both are known to be capable of impacting nematode numbers although in literature this conclusion is not always consistent. It will be interesting to see whether the nematode composition is impacted as well. In case-study 15 the treatments were based on the application of catch crops. Statistical analysis did not reveal a significant impact on the number of nematodes (see table 4.1 and figure 4.8).

Figure 4.8. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15. Case-study 13: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest. Case-study 14a: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat. Case-study 14b: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat. Case-study 15: a = phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.1).

4.3.2 Taxonomic profiles

Table 4.2 contains the total number, mean and range of the reads per case-study retained after quality filtering and additional filtering. Additional filtering comprises deleting reads for which the taxonomic assignment stopped at Class or a higher level, or reads for which the taxonomic assignment at order/family/genus level was lower than 10. Blasting (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) the sequences for which the taxonomic assignment stopped at Class or a higher level turned out to be no nematode sequences.

One sample eventually did not pass the quality control and thus was omitted from further analysis: CS5-21(4).

TABLE 4.2

	Number	Mean	Maximum	Minimum
CS 1	3059397	63737,44	411589	2672
CS 2	810956	25342,38	87659	1956
CS 3	1574837	32809,10	101758	1781
CS 4	2402447	30030,59	203467	3558
CS 5	946858	52603,22	70070	5416
CS 6	4465606	47006,38	138812	1101
CS 7	3641047	53544,81	252056	5804
CS 8	2344846	39080,77	490905	6070
CS 9	1443304	78016,43	85171	5301
CS 10a	2253930	46956,88	297135	4517
CS 10b	1823615	37991,98	106242	3121
CS 11	2881625	60033,85	277838	585
CS 12	906285	27463,18	124431	5346
CS 13	1105063	59733,14	89944	1516
CS 14a	373986	15582,75	36881	1405
CS 14b	1611412	67142,17	233885	5534
CS 15	913052	49354,16	92367	6120

Table 4.2 Total number, mean, minimum and maximum number of reads per case-study retained after quality filtering.

Table 4.3 shows the number of ASVs (Amplicon Sequence Variants) per case-study derived from the reads retained after quality and additional filtering. Subsequent taxonomic profiling classified the ASVs into a number of families or genera. These numbers, which give an indication of the biodiversity richness in the total area of each case-study, was added into the same table (table 4.3). On the level of family, the number between the case-studies is pretty constant and their taxonomic profile indicates that many nematode families are present in agricultural fields spread over different pedoclimatic regions with their specific climate. As was noticed in the results of WP3, this indicates that the nematode taxonomic composition at family level is less influenced by the pedoclimatic region compared to some of the other organism groups investigated. On the level of the genera the variation in number and their characterization is increasing but still not dramatically. The presence of certain nematode species is much more dependent on the pedoclimatic conditions, however, for biodiversity studies it is sufficient to characterize nematodes on genus (family) level. This means that nematodes more than bacteria and fungi are useful to compare the biodiversity situation in different pedoclimatic regions, if that would be desired.

TABLE 4.3

Case-study	# ASVs	# families	# genera
CS 1	4174	49	115
CS 2	569	38	81
CS 3	1321	44	103
CS 4	1806	45	113
CS 5	1274	45	102
CS 6	1780	45	115
CS 7	7961	49	128
CS 8	1534	42	102
CS 9	1279	45	100
CS 10a	2524	50	105
CS 10b	1405	41	102
CS 11	1678	49	108
CS 12	1410	46	106
CS 13	923	35	81
CS 14a	567	42	86
CS 14b	2085	49	106
CS 15	1045	42	93

Table 4.3 Number of ASVs per case-study with linked number of families and genera obtained after taxonomic characterisation.

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

Figure

4.9: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 1 (CS1). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer.

At the start of case-study 1, the nematode community looks quite similar in both composition and abundancies. The community was predominantly composed of the genera *Acrebeloides*, *Pristionchus* and *Aphelenchoides* (Figure 4.9). At the end of the experiment, the community looks more complex and different per treatment. This indicated towards an effect of the treatments on the nematode diversity. The dominant genus remains *Acrobeloides* only.

The same is true for case-study 2. At the start of this case-study, the nematode community again looks quite similar in both composition and abundancies. However, at the end of case-study 2 the composition is still quite similar for all treatments but the diversity seems to be increased (higher number of genera) (Figure 4.10). At the start, the predominant genera were *Acrebeloides*, *Aphelenchoides*, *Geocenamus* and *Heterodera*. *Pristionchus* seems to be almost undetectable but becomes quite dominant at the end of the case-study. Interesting to say is that at the start of the experiment the genus *Heterodera*, containing economically important plant-parasitic nematode species, was clearly detected in all treatments areas, while at the end the detection remained only in

treatment “a” and the control, however with a distinct lower relative abundance. Possibly the crop, but maybe also the treatment caused this result.

Figure 4.10: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 2 (CS2). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer.

Case-studies 3, 4 & 5, Lusitanian region

All case-studies organized in the Lusitanian region seem to show at their start a slightly less homogeneous composition of the nematode communities compared to the Mediterranean South region (figures 4.11, 12 and 13). In case-study 3 (Figure 4.11), the predominant genera were Acrobeloides, Aphelenchoides, Cruznema and Aphelenchus. At the start, also Panagrolaimus is obviously present in treatments “a” and “Ctrl”. However, this genus is not highly represented in treatment “b”, nor in all treatments at the end of the case-study. On the other hand, at the start and the end of case-study 3, Pristionchus is predominantly present in treatment “b” while this is not the case in the other treatments. In case-study 4 (Figure 4.12), the predominant genera are similar to case-study 3: Acrobeloides, Aphelenchoides and Cruznema. At the start of case-study 4, Rhabditophanes and again Panagrolaimus are obviously present in all treatments but they are less detected at the end of the experiment. In case-study 5 (Figure 4.13), Acrobeloides, Aphelenchoides and Pristionchus are the predominantly genera present in the nematode communities. Also Paratylenchus is obviously present. Paratylenchus is a plant-parasitic nematode genus capable of causing yield loss in carrot,

cabbages, celeriac and maybe other crops because this genus is not very well studied yet (Ingham et al., 1996).

In case-study 3 (Figure 4.11) and 5 (Figure 4.13) there seem to be a more complex nematode diversity at the end of the experiments compared to the first year. This conclusion is less obvious for case-study 4 (Figure 4.12), however, there is a clear shift visible in the composition of the communities in all treatments.

Figure 4.11: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 3 (CS3). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation.

Figure 4.12: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 4 (CS4). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization.

Figure

4.13: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 5 (CS5). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system.

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

From the soil samples taken at the start of case-study 6 (2019), the number of sequences that could not be characterized till genus level is rather high (Figure 4.14). This is potentially due to the fact that these soil samples were stored a longer time compared to the soil samples taken for case-study 6 during the consecutive years and during all the years concerning the other case-studies (2020 till 2023). On the contrary to the other case-studies, case-study 6 was already set-up at the start of the SoildiverAgro project and soil samples were taken before the actual protocol for sampling and soil analysis was available. So it was decided to store the samples in a cooled chamber (4°C) until the protocol was discussed and finalised. Although it sounds very unlikely, possibly this longer storage period triggered an event resulting into a higher presence of inhibitors and/or other chemicals causing a negative effect on the amplification of the extracted DNA resulting in smaller fragments or causing the introduction of point mutations into the DNA resulting in an altered nematode sequence making it more difficult to analyse and finally characterize the ASV's (Amplicon Sequence Variants).

Figure 4.14: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 6 (CS6). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual.

The nematode community in case-study 6 at the start and at the end seem to be rather similar between the treatments, however, with a difference in composition between both periods (Figure 4.14). The predominant genus in case-study 6 was clearly *Acrobeloides*. Other predominantly present species were masked by the presence of many uncharacterized sequences (as explained before). However, at the end of case-study 6, also *Geocenamus* was present in relatively high numbers. This genus was also present at the start but less obviously. It is worth to mention that at the end of the case-study, the genera *Trichodorus* and *Tylenchorhynchus* possess a relatively bigger part of the nematode community. Both genera are ectoparasitic plant-feeders causing potentially damage to crops. The presence of these genera in higher numbers could also caused the previously mentioned higher number of uncharacterized sequences. During soil storage, the food for these nematode genera

becomes depleted while this is not the case for the nematodes with other food preferences (bacteria feeders, predators etc.). Their decay could cause their DNA to decay as well resulting in again smaller fragments more difficult to characterize. The sum of the relative amount of both genera together with the still unknown number of sequences at the end resembles more or less the relative amount of uncharacterized sequences at the start of the case-study.

Figure 4.15: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 7 (CS7). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual.

At the start of case-study 7, the predominant genera were Acrobeloides, Aphelenchoides, Geocenamus and Panagrolaimus (Figure 4.15). At the end, the same genera are still present but they are less or not (relatively) predominant anymore. Also at the start of case-study 7, the composition of the nematode communities is slightly more different between the treatments. This is less the case at the end of the experiment while additionally a more complex diversity can be noticed. So, at first glance it seems that all the treatments or an external factor caused an increase in diversity.

Figure 4.16: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 8 (CS8). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system.

In case-study 8 again another situation occurs. As well as at the start as at the end of this case-study, the nematode communities seem to be quite different between the treatments (Figure 4.16). A causing factor could be the field history and its experimental set-up. In this case-study, not particular treatments like in the other case-studies, but complete farming systems were compared (extensive versus intensive, organic versus conventional). Predominant genera in more or less extent depending on the treatment and sampling period, seem to be Acrobeloides, Clarkus and Pristionchus (Figure 4.16). Importantly, Pratylenchus also seems to be predominantly present in both periods in all treatments. Species belonging to the Pratylenchus genus are migratory endoparasitic causing crop yield reduction and damage to many arable crops including a range of vegetables.

In case-study 9, we notice different nematode communities at the start but a more homogeneous and diverse composition at the end of the experiment (Figure 4.17). It seems that a common factor caused the nematode communities to become more diverse. At the start, predominant genera were Acrobeloides, Aphelenchoides, Cruznema and Pristionchus. At the end, Acrobeloides remained a predominant genus but the others were replaced by Geocenamus, by a lesser extent Rhabditophanes

and *Pratylenchus*. It was already mentioned that species belonging to this genus are migratory endoparasitic causing economic loss to many crops.

Figure 4.17: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 9 (CS9). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer.

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

Figure

4.18: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 10a (CS10a). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides.

At the start of case-study 10a, the composition of the nematode communities seem to be quite similar between the treatments (Figure 4.18). This is less the case at the end of the experiment. While at the start the predominant genera were Acrobeloides and Geocenamus, at the end, Acrobeloides and Geocenamus still remain predominant but they tend to be accompanied by Pristionchus.

Concerning case-study 10b, the nematode community looks slightly different between the treatments in both sampling events (first and last year). There is a tendency to notice a more homogeneous composition between the treatments during the last year, but it is more difficult to see since the nematode communities are obviously more divers (Figure 4.19). The predominant genus was at the start of this case-study Acrobeloides. At the end, Acrobeloides is accompanied by Meloidogyne and Paratylenchus. Both are genera with potentially harmful species for the crop. Especially Meloidogyne is a big concern as it contain economically devastating plant-parasitic nematode species, of which a few even are recorded on the European quarantine list. It has to be remarked that Meloidogyne was

also detected at the start of the experiment, but its relative proportion in the community increased at the end of the experiment.

Figure 4.19: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 10b (CS10b). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual.

Similar to case-study 8, case-study 11 compared complete farming systems. In case-study 8 we noticed a more diverse nematode community as well as at the start as at the end of the experiment. In case-study 11 we notice a similar situation, however, there seems to be a more clear differentiation of the communities between the 2 sampling years (Figure 4.20).

At the start of case-study 11 the predominant genera were Acrobeloides, Geocenamus, Aphelenchoides and Paratylenchus. As mentioned before, the latter is a plant-parasitic nematode genus. At the end of this case-study, the annotation of predominant genera is more difficult. The nematode communities seem to be more balanced.

Figure 4.20: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 11 (CS11). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming.

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

In the nemoral case-study, different fields conducting different farming systems were sampled during the different years. So it is difficult to compare the results between the first and last year of sampling. Clearly we can notice that for each treatment and sampling event shown in figure 4.21, the nematode communities look very divers with 1 predominant genus in all cases: Acrobeloides. Other genera become more predominant depending on the year of sampling and the experiment conducted. For example in the year 2023, Paratylenchus is predominantly present in treatments “b” and “c”.

Figure 4.21: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 12 (CS12). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control.

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

In Case Study 13, the nematode communities look quite diverse and different between both sampling years and in a lesser extent between the treatments (Figure 4.22). At the start of case-study 13, the predominant genus was *Pristionchus*, less obviously also *Acrobeloides* and *Aphelenchoides*. At the end, *Acrobeloides* and *Aphelenchoides* remained predominant but not *Pristionchus*.

The nematode communities look at the start of case-study 14a in treatment “a” and the control quite similar concerning composition (Figure 4.23). This remained more or less during the last year of sampling, but the compositions seem to be changed slightly into more diverse communities. Predominant genera in all treatments and sampling events were *Acrobeloides* and *Aphelenchoides*.

Figure 4.22: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 13 (CS13). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest.

Figure 4.23: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 14a (CS14a). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat.

Figure 4.24: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode communities at the start and the end of case-study 14b (CS14b). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat.

Case-study 14b starts with a quite diverse nematode community on the entire experimental area with *Aphelenchoides* as the predominant genus accompanied with *Pristionchus* for treatment 'a'. At the end of the case-study, the nematode communities became even more diverse with no obvious predominant genus.

In case-study 15 we see a shift from already quite diverse nematode communities with similar compositions in all treatments during the first year, towards even more diverse nematode communities in the last year of the experiment. Soil samples from the first sampling event show clear predominant genera (*Acrobeloides* and *Pristionchus*). Predominant genera are less obviously detected during the last year of the case-study. However, it is important to mention that *Pratylenchus* became quite prominently present at the end of the experiment. Species belonging to the *Pratylenchus* genus are migratory endoparasitic causing crop yield reduction and damage to many different crops.

Figure 4.25: Mean relative abundance and composition on genus level of the nematode community at the start and the end of case-study 15 (CS15). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest.

4.3.3 Alpha-diversity

The statistical significance of the change in the alpha-diversity measured by the Shannon and inverse Simpson indexes of the nematode communities between the start and the end of the treatments in the separate case-studies can be found in table 4.4. The results are not always consistent when comparing both indexes. The explanation is that both biodiversity indexes measure biodiversity, but they focus on slightly different things. The Shannon index looks at how diverse and evenly distributed species are in an ecosystem, in this case from the nematode communities. The Simpson index emphasizes the dominance of certain species, looking at the chance that two randomly selected individuals belong to the same species. So, the Shannon index gives more weight to both variety and balance between species, emphasizing even distribution while the Simpson index is more sensitive to whether one or a few species dominate the community. Both are useful for different purposes, depending on whether the interest is in evenness (Shannon) or dominance (Simpson) in biodiversity.

A variation of results between the case-studies can be found. In certain case-studies no significant changes happened in both indexes for all treatments inclusive of the control (case-studies 5, 9, 13, 14a and 15). Aversively, in other case-studies for almost all treatments, both indexes significantly

changed (for example case-studies 1, 6, 7, 11 and 14b). In some case-studies only one or few treatments for one or both indexes shows significant changes (for example case-studies 2, 4 and 8). Finally, case-studies 10a and b shows a drastic difference in significant change of the nematode communities between both indexes. Detailed results can be found in figures 4.26 till 4.31. Also, the results of the alpha diversity are more discussed in chapter 4.3.6 to compare it with the results of the nematode functional biodiversity.

TABLE 4.4

	SHANNON						INVERSE SIMPSON					
	Ctrl	a	b	c	d	e	Ctrl	a	b	c	d	e
CS 1	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-	0,31	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-
CS 2	0,66	0,66	0,19	0,11	-	-	1,00	0,03	0,03	0,31	-	-
CS 3	0,03	0,06	0,03	-	-	-	0,19	0,88	0,03	-	-	-
CS 4	0,03	0,19	0,47	0,06	0,06	-	0,47	0,31	0,66	0,31	0,66	-
CS 5	0,08	0,15	0,08	-	-	-	0,66	0,15	0,08	-	-	-
CS 6	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,06	0,06	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,19
CS 7	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,06	-	-
CS 8	0,1	0,1	0,03	0,03	-	-	1	0,10	0,03	0,47	-	-
CS 9	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,29	-	-	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,29	-	-
CS 10a	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-	-	0,47	0,19	0,66	-	-	-
CS 10b	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-	-	0,11	1	0,03	-	-	-
CS 11	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-	-	0,03	0,03	0,19	-	-	-
CS 12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CS 13	0,47	0,19	0,31	-	-	-	0,66	0,31	0,31	-	-	-
CS 14a	0,31	0,66	-	-	-	-	0,31	0,66	-	-	-	-
CS 14b	0,03	0,03	-	-	-	-	0,03	0,03	-	-	-	-
CS 15	0,11	0,31	0,06	-	-	-	0,47	0,31	0,31	-	-	-

Table 4.4 Results (p-values) of the Wilcoxon rank-sum test to infer statistical significance of the change in the alpha-diversity (Shannon / Inverse Simpson) of the nematode communities between the start and end of the treatments applied in each case-study. P-values less than 0.05 (in red) are considered statically significant. CS = case-study. For treatments explanation (Ctrl, a till e): see figures 4.27 till 4.31.

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

Figure 4.26. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 1 and 2. Case-study 1: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer. Case-study 2: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

Case-studies 3, 4 & 5, Lusitanian region

Figure 4.27. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 3, 4 and 5. Case-study 3: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation. Case-study 4: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization. Case-study 5: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

Figure 4.28a. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 6 and 7. Case-study 6: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 7: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

Figure 4.28b. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 8 and 9. Case-study 8: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system. Case-study 9: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

Figure 4.29. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 10a, 10b and 11. Case-study 10a: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides. Case-study 10b: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 11: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

Figure 4.30. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-study 12: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

Figure 4.31a. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 13: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

Figure 4.31b. Boxplots of the alpha diversity calculations (left: Shannon, right: Inverse Simpson biodiversity index) based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 14a, 14b and 15. Case-study 14a: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat. Case-study 14b: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat. Case-study 15: a = phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.4).

4.3.4 Beta-diversity

In table 4.5 an overview of the permanova analysis per case-study is listed. The effect of the treatments for both sampling events together as well as the effect of the sampling event between the start and the end of each case-study and the combination (sampling event and treatment) is given. Results indicate that in almost each case-study the time of the sampling event overrules the treatment in affecting significantly the nematode diversity. With other words, temporal dynamics influence biodiversity in the case-studies. If we consider both factors treatment and year, then again we notice a significant impact on nematode composition. This indicates that the effect of treatment changes depending on the year, with other words the effectiveness of the treatment in enhancing or affecting biodiversity varies based on the specific year, perhaps due to environmental conditions, species responses, or other ecological factors.

TABLE 4.5

	TREATMENT			YEAR			TREATMENT*YEAR		
	R ² (%)	F	p	R ² (%)	F	p	R ² (%)	F	p
CS 1	6,00	0,626	0,973	25,76	10,40	0,001	40	2,293	0,001
CS 2	10,54	1,099	0,319	37,26	17,81	0,001	58,59	4,851	0,001
CS 3	11,66	1,386	0,113	19,80	5,432	0,001	40,63	2,464	0,001
CS 4	9,48	0,916	0,616	27,42	14,35	0,001	46,55	2,903	0,001
CS 5	11,29	0,891	0,586	32,66	7,274	0,001	53,44	2,525	0,001
CS 6	3,79	0,331	1	65,85	88,71	0,001	72,85	8,781	0,001
CS 7	8,48	0,865	0,546	49,23	29,09	0,001	65,21	6,425	0,001
CS 8	28,88	3,249	0,002	26,01	9,14	0,001	68,29	6,152	0,001
CS 9	13,64	0,842	0,599	55,52	22,46	0,001	79,88	6,808	0,001
CS 10a	7,40	0,839	0,669	18,24	4,909	0,001	31,57	1,661	0,008
CS 10b	8,06	0,920	0,455	44,51	17,65	0,001	60,96	5,621	0,001
CS 11	6,27	0,703	0,529	62,42	36,54	0,001	74,38	10,44	0,001
CS 12	42,66	1,637	0,002	19,24	3,573	0,001	42,66	1,637	0,001
CS 13	5,26	0,583	0,867	42,88	16,51	0,001	52,85	4,035	0,001
CS 14a	3,66	0,531	0,913	24,04	4,432	0,001	32,56	1,931	0,034
CS 14b	4,9	0,721	0,553	31,34	6,389	0,001	40,03	2,670	0,007
CS 15	4,04	0,442	0,99	43,44	16,90	0,001	51,42	3,810	0,001

Table 4.5 Results of PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of the treatment (agricultural practice) and the year of sampling (between the start and the end) in each case-study on nematode community composition. CS = case-study. Differences are considered significant if $p \leq 0.05$ (n red).

The results of the permanova analysis are more or less demonstrated in the NMDS plots (figures 4.32 till 37). Clearly, we can see that per case-study datapoints group much more obviously together depending on the year of sampling while this is not the case for grouping based on the treatments (overlapping groups). One notable exception is case-study 8. In this case-study the treatments have a significant impact while the impact of the time of sampling is less significant compared to the other case-studies. A possible reason can be that not a particular treatment but complete farming systems were compared. However, also case-study 11 was testing complete farming systems, while results show the same overall conclusion like most of the other case-studies.

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

Figure 4.32. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 1 and 2. Case-study 1: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer. Case-study 2: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. Significant differences caused by the treatments, sampling event or the combination were tested with Permanova (see table 4.5).

Case-studies 3, 4 & 5, Lusitanian region

Figure 4.33. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 3, 4 and 5. Case-study 3: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation. Case-study 4: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization. Case-study 5: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. Insufficient number of repeats in CS5 made it impossible to visualise the grouping with a certain confidence interval. Significant differences caused by the treatments, sampling event or the combination were tested with Permanova (see table 4.5).

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

Figure 4.34. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 6 till 9. Case-study 6: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 7: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 8: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system. Case-study 9: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. Insufficient number of repeats in CS9 made it impossible to draw the NMDS plot. Significant differences caused by the treatments, sampling event or the combination were tested with Permanova (see table 4.5).

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

Figure 4.35. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 10a, 10b and 11. Case-study 10a: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides. Case-study 10b: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 11: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. Significant differences caused by the treatments, sampling event or the combination were tested with Permanova (see table 4.5).

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

Figure 4.36. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-study 12: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. Significant differences caused by the treatments, sampling event or the combination were tested with Permanova (see table 4.5).

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

Figure 4.37b. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15. Case-study 13: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest. Case-study 14a: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat. Case-study 14b: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat. Case-study 15: a = phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. Significant differences caused by the treatments, sampling event or the combination were tested with Permanova (see table 4.5).

4.3.5 Indicator nematode taxa per case-study

Figures 4.38 till 4.54 shows the indicator nematode genera (families) per case-study. A positive Log2FoldChange indicates that the abundance of that taxon is statistically significantly higher at the end of the case-study compared to the start of the experiment (for all treatments together). A negative Log2FoldChange indicates a lower abundance.

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

Figure 4.38. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 1 (CS1) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.39. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 2 (CS2) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Case-studies 3, 4 & 5, Lusitanian region

Figure 4.40. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 3 (CS3) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.41. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 4 (CS4) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.42. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 5 (CS5) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

Figure 4.43. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 6 (CS6) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.44. Log₂FoldChange results for case-study 7 (CS7) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.45. Log₂FoldChange results for case-study 8 (CS8) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.46. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 9 (CS9) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

Figure 4.47. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 10a (CS10a) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.48. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 10b (CS10b) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.49. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 11 (CS11) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

Figure 4.50. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 12 (CS12) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

Figure 4.51. Log2FoldChange results for case-study 13 (CS13) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Figure 4.54. Log₂FoldChange results for case-study 15 (CS15) calculated by DeSeq2. Each dot is a single ASV representing a taxon showing a significant difference in abundance between the first and last year of the case-study ($p \leq 0.05$). Negative values indicate a significant negative evolution, positive values a positive evolution in the abundance of the mentioned nematode taxon. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

Since it is difficult to overview all results, table 4.6 gives a summary of the nematode indicator genera per case-study for which the log₂FoldChange is higher than 10 (green) or less than -10 (red). Some genera are case-study specific, for example *Achromadora* for case-study 9. Other genera are indicators for a few till a lot of case-studies. However, none of the genera are indicative for all case-studies, although few come close, for example *Acrobeloides*, *Aphelenchoides* and *Panagrolaimus*. Some case-studies show only few nematode indicator taxa (for example case-study 8), others have many (for example case-study 9).

TABLE 4.6

NEMATODE GENUS

CASE STUDY

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
										10A	10B	11	12	13	14A	14B	15
Achromadora									Green								
Acrobeles						Red						Green				Green	
Acrobeloides	Red		Yellow	Red	Red		Red	Green	Yellow	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow		Yellow
Acrostichus																	Red
Alaimus									Green				Green				
Anaplectus		Green							Green								
Anatonchus		Green							Green								Green
Aphelenchoides	Green	Yellow			Red	Red			Green	Green		Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow
Aphelenchus					Green							Green		Yellow		Green	
Aporcella		Red												Green			
Aquatides									Green								
Basiria													Red		Green		
Bastiania																Green	
Boleodorus									Green				Green		Red		Green
Bursaphelenchus						Red											
Clarkus		Green							Green								
Coslenchus							Green		Green	Green	Green	Red	Green		Green		Green
Cruznema			Red	Red													
Diphtherophora	Green						Green		Green						Green		Green
Diplogasteroides		Green															
Diploscapter							Green		Green								Green
Discopersicus						Green	Red		Green							Green	Green
Ditylenchus		Green	Green	Green	Green				Green		Green	Yellow				Green	
Ekta-phelenchoides							Green										
Filenchus									Green	Green				Green		Red	Green
Heterorhabditis																Green	
Hexameris							Green		Green	Green							
Howardula													Green	Green			
Mesodorylaimus									Green								Red
Mesorhabditis									Green								Green

4.3.6 Nematode functional biodiversity

The statistical significance of the change in the Structure Index inferred from the nematode communities at the start and the end of each treatment in the separate case-studies can be found in table 4.7. Likewise the results of the alpha diversity indices (table 4.4), a variation of results between the case-studies can be found. In certain case-studies no significant changes happened for all treatments inclusive of the control (case-studies 1, 5, 8, 9, 14a and 15). Aversively, in some case-studies, the index significantly changed for all applied treatments (case-studies 7, 10b and 11). In the remaining case-studies, only one or few treatments significantly changed (for example case-studies 2, 4 and 8). Possibly in these case-studies the treatment had an effect on functional biodiversity. However, it is clear that the Structure Index significantly changed in not always the same treatments in certain case-studies compared to the Shannon and Simpson biodiversity indices (chapter 4.3.3). This is expected as the nematode taxa were grouped into functional guilds before calculating the mentioned nematode-specific index. Changes in the diversity within one functional group has a reduced impact on the Structure Index resulting in a potential non-significant change, while this is not the case for the biological diversity for which all taxa are considered with equally importance. On the other hand, changes in the diversity related to different functional groups has a higher impact on the Structure Index resulting in a potential significant change.

TABLE 4.7

	Ctrl	a	b	c	d	e
CS 1	0,11	0,19	0,88	0,31	-	-
CS 2	0,31	1	0,03	0,31	-	-
CS 3	0,03	0,06	0,03	-	-	-
CS 4	0,06	0,31	0,06	0,66	0,03	-
CS 5	0,08	0,15	0,08	-	-	-
CS 6	0,31	0,05	0,06	0,03	0,03	0,03
CS 7	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-
CS 8	1	1	0,31	0,11	-	-
CS 9	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,29	-	-
CS 10a	0,11	0,03	0,19	-	-	-
CS 10b	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-	-
CS 11	0,03	0,03	0,03	-	-	-
CS 12	-	-	-	-	-	-
CS 13	0,03	0,66	0,88	-	-	-
CS 14a	0,66	1	-	-	-	-
CS 14b	0,03	0,19	-	-	-	-
CS 15	0,11	0,11	0,06	-	-	-

Table 4.7 Results (p-values) of the Wilcoxon rank-sum test to infer statistical significance of the change in the nematode-specific Structure Index (SI) between the start and end of the treatments applied in each case-study. P-values less than or equal to 0.05 (in red) are considered statically significant. CS = case-study. For treatments explanation (Ctrl, a till e): see figures 4.2 till 4.8.

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

Only in treatment 'b' of case-study 2, the Structure Index significantly changed during the experiment (see table 4.7).

In case-study 1 a consistent increase in nematode counts, in case-study 2 a decrease (Figure 4.2) was noted. This is not the case concerning the calculated values of the Structure Index (Figure 4.57). Some treatments show an increase, others a decrease within the same case-study, possibly linked to the treatment. The alpha-diversity also was consistently increasing concerning case-study 1 (Figure 4.26). For case-study 2, the biodiversity indices showed sometimes a decrease, sometimes an increase depending on the treatment (Figure 4.26). It is obvious that nematode counts alone give insufficient information about (functional) diversity and therefor results can be different. Also the functional diversity results can be different compared to the biological diversity for the reason already mentioned before.

Concerning the treatments: in both case-studies, a biofertilizer containing bacteria, whether or not with fungi, was applied. This can have an effect on the Structure Index as certain nematode taxa feed on bacteria and fungi causing an increased development of these nematode taxa shortly after the biofertilizer was applied, causing on its turn a decreased functional complexity of the nematode community (treatment "a" and "b") (Figure 4.55 and 4.56). Also the alpha diversity can be affected due to the same reason. However, we do not see similar results between both diversity methods (alpha diversity versus fuctional diversity), nor the same effect due to the application of the biofertilizer.

Figure 4.55: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 1 (CS1). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer.

Figure 4.56: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 2 (CS2). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer.

Figure 4.57. Boxplots of the Structure Index (SI) values of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 1 and 2. Case-study 1: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer. Case-study 2: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.7).

Case-studies 3, 4 & 5, Lusitanian region

In case-study 3 the control and “b” treatment show a significant increase concerning functional biodiversity (Table 4.7). However, also in treatment “a”, although not statistically significant, an increase in Structure Index can be noted (Figure 4.61). This is also the case for the biodiversity indices (Figure 4.27). Alternative crop rotations were investigated in this case-study and more complex crop rotations can induce a higher nematode community complexity. In this case (Figure 4.58), the alternative crop rotations did not trigger this effect more as the control also shows an increased Structure, Shannon and Inverse Simpson index.

Another evolution is true for case-study 4 (Figure 4.59). Only treatment “d” shows a significant change of the Structure Index (Table 4.7). However, this time we notice for all treatments a decrease of the Structure Index in stead of an increase (Figure 4.61). This is not in agreement with the Shannon index (Figure 4.27). The latter also showed an increase in biodiversity for all treatments. On the contrary, results seem to be in agreement with the Inverse Simpson index, except for treatment “d” (Figure 4.27). A clear explanation is at this point not possible.

All treatments in case-study 5 show an increase of the Structure Index (Figure 4.61) being it in all cases not statistically significant (Table 4.7). The same results were noted concerning the biodiversity indices (Figure 4.27). Seemingly, the pest alert system applied to reduce the use of a fungicide did not boost

the nematode biodiversity (Figure 4.60). An important note is that the no fungicide application (treatment “b”) showed the highest increase of the Structure Index and biodiversity indices. This points towards a positive trend concerning the biodiversity if no fungicide products are used or if it is possible to reduce the usage. Indeed, the pest alert system also shows a higher increase of the Structure Index compared to the conventional use of fungicides (treatment “a”).

The increased or decreased Structure Index in case-studies 3 till 5 (Figure 4.61) is in agreement with the remark that the taxonomic profile in case-study 3 (Figure 4.11) and 5 (Figure 4.13) seem to be more complex at the end of the experiments compared to the first year. This conclusion was less obvious for case-study 4 (Figure 4.12).

Figure 4.58: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 3 (CS3). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation.

Figure 4.59: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 4 (CS4). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization.

Figure 4.60: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 5 (CS5). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system.

Figure 4.61. Boxplots of the Structure Index (SI) values of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 3, 4 and 5. Case-study 3: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation. Case-study 4: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization. Case-study 5: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.7).

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

In case-study 6, the treatments do not have a clear effect on functional biodiversity because the control treatment shows the same trend. Remarkably, the Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices (Figure 4.28a) show a clear increase while the opposite is true for the Structure Index (Figure 4.66). The latter can be caused by a reduction of the relative proportion of carnivores and omnivores (Figure 4.62), which points to a reduced food web complexity. Another explanation could be the already mentioned high proportion of not annotated ASV's. This for sure has an impact on richness and thus biodiversity, but less on functional diversity due to the grouping of nematode taxa according to their feeding behaviour and life strategy (which is not possible for not annotated ASV's which consequently are ignored). For this case-study, we can conclude that the functional biodiversity is less biased.

The taxonomic profile of case-study 7 is notable more complex at the end of the experiment (Figure 4.15) for all treatments including the control. This is translated into significantly increased Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices (Figure 4.28a), as well as an increased Structure Index (Figure 4.66), also statistically significant (Table 4.7). So, it is confirmed that an external factor caused an increase in

diversity overruling the effect of the different treatments. The cover crop mixtures seemingly did not (yet) induce an increased biodiversity compared to the control as this is actually expected from an increased crop rotation complexity (Figure 4.63).

It has been mentioned that concerning case-study 8 (Figure 4.64), the nematode communities seem to be quite different between the treatments as well as at the start as at the end of the experiments (Figure 4.16), possibly due to the fact that complete farming systems with a different combination of treatments were compared. Nevertheless, all systems showed an increase in the biological indices (Figure 4.28b) being it statistically significant for treatment “b” for both indices and treatment “c” for the Shannon index alone (Table 4.4). Also the Structure Index shows an increase (Figure 4.66) but in each case not statistically significant (Table 4.7).

The results of case-study 9 (Figure 4.65) are similar to case-study 7. Increased Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices (Figure 4.28b), as well as an increased Structure Index (Figure 4.66) can be noticed. Possibly again an external factor caused an increase in diversity overruling the effect of the different treatments (different sources of organic fertilizer).

Figure 4.62: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 6 (CS6). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual.

Figure 4.63: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 7 (CS7). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual.

Figure 4.64: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 8 (CS8). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system.

Figure 4.65: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 9 (CS9). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer.

Figure 4.66. Boxplots of the Structure Index (SI) values of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 6, 7, 8 and 9. Case-study 6: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 7: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop

mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 8: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system. Case-study 9: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.7).

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

The functional diversity of the nematode communities in case-study 10a clearly increase at the end of the experiment (Figure 4.70). Treatment “a” even shows a statistically significant increase (Table 4.7), the increase is less clear for treatment “b”. Also the biological indices show the same trend (Figure 4.29). The Shannon index even results in a statistically significant increase for all treatments, while the increase concerning the Inverse Simpson index is not statistically significant. It was noticed before that an reduces application of fungicides, which is the case in all treatments of case-study 10a, can positively impact biodiversity (Figure 4.67).

In case-study 10b (Figure 4.68 and 4.70), a more or less similar result can be noted compared to case-study 10a. Almost all treatments show an increase in biodiversity for both methods (alpha diversity and functional diversity). The Structure Index as well as the Shannon index even shows statistically increased values (Table 4.4 and 4.7). It seems that undersowing was not the impacting factor as the control lacking this treatment resulted in the same trend.

Also case-study 11 (Figure 4.69 and 4.70) resulted into a more or less similar conclusion. The Structure Index as well as the Shannon index show statistically increased values (Table 4.4 and 4.7). Also the Inverse Simpson index increases but not always statistically significant (Table 4.4). Again the treatment is not the most important factor impacting biodiversity.

Figure 4.67: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 10a (CS10a). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides.

Figure 4.68: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 10b (CS10b). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual.

Figure 4.69: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 11 (CS11). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming.

Figure 4.70. Boxplots of the Structure Index (SI) values of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 10a, 10b and 11. Case-study 10a: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides. Case-study 10b: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 11: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.7).

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

As mentioned before, in case-study 12 (Figure 4.71) different plots were sampled during the different years of sampling. Therefore the boxplots (Figure 4.72) cannot reveal anything between the first and last year of sampling.

Figure 4.71: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 12 (CS12). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control.

Figure 4.72. Boxplots of the Structure Index (SI) values of the first and last year for each treatment within case-study 12: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.7).

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

The Shannon, Inverse Simpson (Figure 4.31a) indices and Structure Index (Figure 4.77) show a decreasing trend in all treatments for case-study 13. An external factor must have caused this.

In case-studies 14a and b (Figures 4.74 and 4.75), the Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices (Figure 4.31a) increase for both treatments. For case-study 14b this increase is even statistically significant

(Table 4.4). The Structure Index also increases in case-study 14b but not in case-study 14a in which it remains more or less unchanged (Figure 4.77). At this point it is difficult to explain this.

Case-study 15 overall shows an increase in Shannon, Inverse Simpson (Figure 4.31b) indices and Structure Index (Figure 4.77). The increase is less obvious in the control pointing towards the impression that the treatments had an effect on biodiversity (Figure 4.76).

Figure 4.73: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 13 (CS13). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest.

Figure 4.74: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 14a (CS14a). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat.

Figure 4.75: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 14b (CS14b). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the treatment: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat.

Figure 4.76: Mean relative abundance (%) and composition of the nematode functional guilds at the start and the end of case-study 15 (CS15). The figure in the code represents the year of sampling, the letter(s) the

treatment: a = phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest.

Figure 4.77. Boxplots of the Structure Index (SI) values of the first and last year for each treatment within case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15. Case-study 13: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest. Case-study 14a: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat. Case-study 14b: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat. Case-study 15: a = phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest. Black dots = outliers. Significant differences caused by the treatments were tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test (see table 4.7).

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5 Earthworm

5.1 Introduction

Earthworms play a key role in maintaining and improving soil ecosystem services, performing important functions, including: a) decomposition of plant residues; b) regulation of nutrient cycles; c) improvement of soil structure; and d) regulation and improvement of soil biota (Turbé et al., 2010; Blouin et al., 2013). Regarding agricultural soils, it is well known that earthworms contribute to improving soil fertility, thus causing positive effects on crop growth and yield (Scheu, 2003; van Groenigen et al., 2014).

Earthworm abundance varies widely across the different regions of the world, depending mainly on soil type and climatic factors (precipitation and temperature). For Europe, maximum abundances of 300 individuals m^{-2} have been observed in agricultural soils, while earthworm abundance in grasslands is higher, with more than 600 individuals m^{-2} (Edwards and Arancon, 2022). Regarding soil properties, soil texture is the main edaphic factor determining the abundance of earthworms, with medium and coarse textures being the most favorable for earthworms (Guild, 1948; Nieminen et al., 2011). Furthermore, it should be noted that, in contrast to natural systems, arable farming systems generally hinder the development of species-rich earthworm communities, mainly due to the succession of agricultural tasks such as seedbed preparation, sowing, harvesting and tillage, among others (Phillips et al., 2019).

Depending on their morphological characteristics and specific abilities, earthworms can be classified into three different ecological groups: a) epigeans, which are small in size and highly pigmented, and are usually found in leaf litter or near the soil surface; b) endogeans, which are medium in size and lightly pigmented, and have the ability to burrow in mineral soils; and c) anecicans, which are large in size and pigmented at the front end of their body, and have the ability to burrow vertically. Furthermore, in terms of their diet, epigean and anecic species are primary decomposers, feeding mainly on energy-rich organic material, such as plant remains, while endogean species are secondary decomposers, feeding on more humified organic material (Bouché, 1977; Bottinelli and Capowiez, 2021).

On the other hand, it should be noted that both the abundance and species richness of earthworms are sensitive to alterations in the physical and chemical soil environment and by the availability of food sources. Therefore, in agricultural soils, earthworms are affected by the type of tillage, by the types and qualities of fertilizers and pesticides used, and by the type of crop, as well as by other management techniques, such as the application of crop rotation or cover crops, among others (Briones y Schmidt, 2017; Curry, 2004; Melman et al., 2019). In this sense, it should be noted that a reduction in the intensity and depth of tillage, as well as a reduction in the use of inputs (fertilizers and pesticides), constitute agricultural practices that positively affect both the abundance and diversity of earthworms (Briones and Schmidt, 2017).

Regarding climatic conditions, previous studies indicate that high soil temperatures and droughts lead to lower earthworm diversity and abundance. In this sense, in Europe, earthworm abundance and diversity are high in Atlantic regions, characterized by high rainfall, while they are much lower in Mediterranean regions, which are warmer and drier (Phillips et al., 2019; Rutgers et al., 2016). In addition, taking into account the temperature increases, and severe droughts associated with climate change, which are increasingly affecting the northernmost areas of Europe, it is expected that earthworm communities will be negatively affected in these areas (Hiltbold et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2019).

On the other hand, it is well known that the use of the soil biological community is essential to carry out the implementation of organic or conservative agricultural practices, where plant nutrition is based on the efficient functioning of the soil decomposer network fed by organic fertilizers (Bertrand et al., 2015). In this sense, previous studies suggest that the abundance of earthworms could be greater in organic agriculture than in conventional agriculture (Bengtsson et al., 2005; Christel et al., 2021). Despite this, comprehensive studies with systematic approaches to investigate the effect of different agricultural systems on earthworm communities are very rare.

Considering the key role that earthworms play in soil ecosystem services, it is essential to study the variation of earthworm communities (both in terms of abundance and diversity) along a large climatic gradient to understand the possible consequences of climate change on these communities. This will also allow us to know whether different farming systems could alleviate these negative effects of climate change on earthworm communities. Therefore, in the present work we investigated the abundance and diversity of earthworms in the main pedoclimatic regions of Europe (Mediterranean South, Lusitanian, Atlantic Central, Continental, Nemoral, and Boreal), as well as the impact of different farming systems on such abundance and diversity.

5.2 Material and Methods

Earthworms were sampled in each field case study site at a representative area from three quadrats by a combined method of hand-sorting and chemical expelling by the active agent in mustard, allyl isothiocyanate (AITC; mustard oil) as described in ISO 23611-1:2018. The sampling area of each plot was 50 cm x 50 cm with exception of the Boreal and Mediterranean region, where an area of 25 cm x 25 cm was sampled due to local soil conditions, which makes the hand-sorting of soil arduous. The sampling depth was 25 cm. A detailed description of the sampling procedures is given in deliverable D3.1 Handbook of Methods (June 2020) (chapter 1.3, pages 18-23) under the URL: <http://soildiveragro.eu/data/D3.1.pdf>

Earthworm metrics obtained were referred to 1 square meter for total earthworm abundance as well as for total biomass (g m^{-2}). The number of species in a sample was used as such for obtaining the mean species number in a field. The different type of data was defined as follows:

- Total abundance: all individuals incl. fragments with intact anterior end ("head") that can be unequivocally counted. This was done to avoid overestimation of population numbers.

- Total biomass: all individuals and fragments (anterior and posterior ends and any middle parts)
- Identified species: those individuals and fragments with intact anterior end ("head") and clitellum/tubercula pubertatis that allowed taxonomical identification.
- Unidentified individuals: only fragments with intact anterior end ("head") when species identification was not possible.

Adult and sub-adult earthworms (tubercula pubertatis present, but clitellum absent or not fully developed) were identified to species level by using a stereo microscope (magnitude: 10x to 50x) and specialized taxonomic identification keys. Here, data on species level are the sum of adults and sub-adults. Adults and sub-adults but also juveniles (when possible) were assigned to their ecological groups (epigeic, epiendogeic, endogeic, anecic) according to their dorsal pigmentation. A detailed description of separating developmental stages, assigning individuals to ecological groups and taxonomical identification is given in deliverable D3.1 Handbook of Methods (June 2020) (chapter 4.1, pages 96-99) under the URL: <http://soildiveragro.eu/data/D3.1.pdf>

Data was analyzed using generalized linear mixed models (GLMM). Treatments were compared to the control treatment within experiments and years, and therefore the fixed effects of the models consisted of experiment, treatment, year, and all of their interactions. Random effects were block within experiment, experiment and year and experiment and treatment. The assumptions of gamma (with log link) and Gaussian (with identity link) distributions were applied to all six dependent variables. All models were fitted by using the residual pseudo likelihood (for gamma) or restricted maximum likelihood (for Gaussian) estimation method, respectively. The former was chosen due to the skewed distribution of the dependent variables and to minimize variation between experiments. Diagnostic plots were used to confirm the normality of residuals. Dunnett's method was employed for pairwise comparisons of treatments against the control treatment. A significance level of $\alpha=0.05$ was used for all analyses. Degrees of freedom were calculated using the Kenward-Roger method. The analyses were performed using the GLIMMIX procedure in SAS Enterprise Guide 8.3 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA).

Boxplots were used to illustrate the variation in the total abundance and biomass and species richness of earthworms between the regions and between the managements within regions. Figures were made with 'ggplot2' of R package (Wickham, 2016).

5.3 Results and discussion

5.3.1 Total earthworm abundance

First of all, it should be noted that in Mediterranean South region no earthworms were observed in CS1 and CS2. For the remaining case studies, the earthworm density for the control treatment, taking into account all case studies, varied between 2 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} for CS5 and 273 ± 48 individuals

m^{-2} for CS14b. In addition, significant differences between the different case studies were found ($F=8.305$, $P=0.000$), following the next sequence: $\text{CS10b} \approx \text{CS5} \approx \text{CS15} < \text{CS4} < \text{CS3} \approx \text{CS7} \approx \text{CS11} \approx \text{CS14a} \approx \text{CS13} \approx \text{CS12} \approx \text{CS10a} < \text{CS6} \approx \text{CS9} \approx \text{CS8} \approx \text{CS14b}$. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, the highest density of earthworms was observed in the Central Atlantic region, with an average of 128 ± 77 individuals m^{-2} , followed by the Boreal, Nemoral, Continental, and Lusitanian regions, with average densities of 106 ± 114 , 94 ± 47 , 56 ± 50 , and 20 ± 20 individuals m^{-2} , respectively. However, these differences were not significant.

On the other hand, Figure 5.1 shows the earthworm density (individual m^{-2}) for the Lusitanian region (CS3, CS4, and CS5). In the CS3, average densities of 31 ± 29 , 89 ± 52 , and 2 ± 4 individual m^{-2} were obtained for the Ctrl, Alt1Pea, and Alt2OatVetch treatments, respectively, with the Alt1Pea treatment presenting the highest earthworm density. In fact, significant differences were obtained ($F=6.488$, $P=0.018$), following the sequence $\text{Alt2OatVetch} < \text{Ctrl} \approx \text{Alt1Pea}$. On the other hand, in the CS4, average densities of 20 ± 10 , 43 ± 18 , 42 ± 37 , 21 ± 22 , and 59 ± 83 individual m^{-2} were obtained for the treatments Barley 1, Barley 2, Barley 3, Barley 4, and Barley 5, respectively, with the Barley 5 treatment resulting in higher earthworms density, and the Barley 1 treatment resulting in a lower density. However, the differences observed were very small. In fact, no significant differences were found between the different treatments. Finally, in the CS5, average densities of 4 ± 4 , 13 ± 12 , and 25 ± 23 individual m^{-2} were observed for the Ctrl, WheConvFA, and WheNoFA treatments, respectively, with the Ctrl treatment resulting in a lower density of earthworms, and the WheNoFA treatment resulting in a higher density. However, no significant differences were found between the different treatments.

Figure 5.1 Total density of earthworm (individual m^{-2}) in CS3–CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.2 shows the earthworm density (individuals m^{-2}) for the Atlantic Central region (CS6, CS7, CS8, and CS9). In CS6, average densities of 143 ± 88 , 134 ± 69 , 261 ± 178 , 291 ± 69 , 165 ± 118 , and 197 ± 94 individuals m^{-2} were obtained for the Ctrl, AFV, FYM, AFVFYM, AFVbrFYM, and brFYM treatments, respectively, with the AFVFYM and FYM treatments resulting in the highest earthworms density, while the Ctrl and AFV treatments were the ones resulting in the lowest density. However, no significant differences were found among the different treatments. On the other hand, in CS7, the densities obtained were similar for the different treatments, with average densities of 61 ± 31 , 76 ± 14 , 91 ± 19 , and 55 ± 37 individuals m^{-2} , for the Ctrl, PhaEgClov, Mix5, and Mix12 treatments, respectively. In fact, no significant differences were obtained. Regarding CS8, average earthworm densities of 143 ± 55 , 193 ± 88 , 159 ± 59 , and 441 ± 117 individuals m^{-2} were obtained, with the ConvExt treatment clearly resulting in a higher earthworm density. In fact, significant differences were obtained in this case study ($F = 11.162$, $P = 0.001$), observing the following sequence: $OrgInt \approx ConvInt \approx OrgExt < ConvExt$. Finally, in CS9, average earthworm densities of 159 ± 84 , 151 ± 96 , 231 ± 130 , and 259 ± 55 individuals m^{-2} were obtained, with the Ferm treatment resulting in the highest earthworm density, while the lowest earthworms density was observed in the Ctrl treatment. However, no significant differences were observed.

Figure 5.2 Total density of earthworm in CS6–CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.3 shows the earthworm density (individuals m^{-2}) for the Continental region (CS10a, CS10b, and CS11). For CS10, it was observed that the BiostimAdj treatment was the one that resulted in a higher density of earthworms (152 ± 49 individuals m^{-2}), followed by the Ctrl and Biostim treatments, respectively, with average densities of 104 ± 36 and 95 ± 13 individuals m^{-2} . However, no statistical differences were found. On the other hand, for CS10b, the observed densities were very low and similar among the three different treatments here tested. Thus, average densities of 3 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} were obtained for the Ctrl treatment, 8 ± 7 individuals m^{-2} for the StripUndSow treatment, and 7 ± 5 individuals m^{-2} for the BroadUndSow treatment. Therefore, no statistical differences were found between the different treatments. Finally, in CS11, the DivExtWhe treatment was the one that resulted in a higher density of earthworms, with an average of 107 ± 64 individual m^{-2} , while

the average densities observed in the Ctrl and ExtWhe treatments were 61 ± 32 and 57 ± 27 individual m^{-2} , respectively. However, no significant differences were observed.

Figure 5.3 Total density of earthworm in CS10a–CS11 fields from the Continental region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figure 5.4 shows the earthworm density (individuals m^{-2}) for the Nemoral region (CS12). For this case study, the OrgConvTill treatment was found to be the one that resulted in a higher density of earthworms (252 ± 62 individual m^{-2}). On the other hand, the average densities observed for the ConvConvTill and ConvNoTill treatments were similar, specifically 94 ± 47 and 110 ± 13 individual m^{-2} , respectively. No significant differences were observed between the different treatments.

Figure 5.4 Total density of earthworm in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.5 shows the earthworm density (individuals m^{-2}) for the Nemoral region (CS13, CS14a, CS14b, CS15). Regarding CS13, the densities obtained were similar for the three treatments here tested. Thus, average densities of 83 ± 83 individuals m^{-2} were obtained for the Ctrl treatment, 40 ± 49 individuals m^{-2} for the FS treatment, and 65 ± 98 individuals m^{-2} for the CPMS treatment. In fact, no significant differences were obtained. For CS14a, the mean densities were practically the same for the two treatments, obtaining a mean density of 63 ± 45 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment and 64 ± 48 individuals m^{-2} for the Plough treatment. As expected, no significant differences were found. Similarly, for CS14b, the observed densities were also similar between the two treatments, with an average of 273 ± 48 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment, and an average of 251 ± 60 individual m^{-2} for the Plough treatment. In fact, no significant differences were found between both treatments either. Finally, for CS15, the observed earthworm densities were very low and similar among the different treatments here tested, obtaining average densities of 4 ± 5 , 11 ± 9 , and 7 ± 14 individual m^{-2} for the Ctrl, pha, and rye treatments, respectively. No statistical differences were found among the different

Figure 5.5 Total density of earthworm in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

5.3.2 Total earthworm biomass

First of all, it should be noted that in Mediterranean South region no earthworms were observed in CS1 and CS2. For the remaining case studies, the total earthworm mass for the control treatment, taking into account all case studies, varied from 2 g m⁻² for CS5 to 247 g m⁻² for CS14b. In addition, significant differences between the different case studies were found (F= 18.524, P=0.000), following the next sequence: CS15 ≈ CS5 ≈ CS10b ≈ CS4 ≈ CS8 ≈ CS13 ≈ CS7 ≈ CS12 ≈ CS14a ≈ CS9 ≈ CS3 ≈ CS11 ≈ CS10a ≈ CS6 < CS14b. Therefore, the total mass of earthworm was statistically equal for all case studies, with the exception of CS14b, which had a significantly higher total mass. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, the highest total mass of earthworms was observed in the Boreal region, with an average total mass of 73 ± 108 g m⁻², followed by the Atlantic Central, Continenta, Nemoral, and Lusitanian regions, with total mass averages of 32 ± 25, 31 ± 36, 21 ± 14, and 18 ± 32 g m⁻², respectively. However, these differences were not significant.

On the other hand, Figure 5.6 shows the total mass of earthworm for the Lusitanian region (CS3, CS4, and CS5). For CS3, the highest total earthworm mass was obtained for the Ctrl treatment (average 53 ± 50 g m⁻²), followed by the Alt1Pea treatment (average 34 ± 24 g m⁻²), and finally by the Alt2OatVetch treatment (average 2 ± 4 g m⁻²). However, no statistical differences were obtained. On the other hand, for case CS4, the total mass was low and similar for all treatments, obtaining total mass averages of 8 ± 9, 14 ± 4, 9 ± 6, 5 ± 5, and 13 ± 9 g m⁻² for Barley 1, Barley 2, Barley 3, Barley 4, and Barley 5 treatments, respectively. As expected, no significant differences were obtained for CS4 either. Finally, for CS5, the highest total earthworm mass was observed for the WheNoFA treatment (average 27 ± 27 g m⁻²), followed by the WheConvFA treatment (average 11 ± 11 g m⁻²) and, finally, the Ctrl treatment (average 2 ± 2 g m⁻²), with this treatment having the lowest total mass.

Figure 5.6 Total mass of earthworm in CS3–CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.7 shows the total mass of earthworm for the Atlantic Central region (CS6, CS7, CS8, and CS9). For CS6, the total earthworm mass was similar for all treatments, with mean values of 60 ± 30 , 68 ± 57 , 42 ± 22 , 63 ± 22 , 87 ± 16 , and 47 ± 27 g m⁻² for the Ctrl, FYM, AFV, brFYM, AFVfYm, and AFVbrFYM treatments, respectively. In fact, no significant differences were obtained. Similarly, for CS7 the total earthworm mass was also very similar for the different treatments, with average values of 20 ± 14 , 29 ± 9 , 35 ± 3 , and 31 ± 3 g m⁻², respectively, with the Ctrl treatment resulting in the lowest earthworm mass. However, no significant differences were obtained.

For CS8, significant differences were observed between the different treatments ($F = 5.714$, $P = 0.011$), with the following sequence: $\text{ConvInt} \approx \text{OrgInt} < \text{OrgExt} \approx \text{ConvExt}$. Thus, the average values of total mass obtained were 16 ± 10 , 26 ± 7 , 39 ± 14 , and 43 ± 9 g m⁻², for the ConvInt, OrgInt, OrgExt, and ConvExt treatments, respectively. Finally, for CS9, the lowest total mass was observed for the Ctrl treatment (average 32 ± 19 g m⁻²), while the highest total mass was observed for the Ferm treatment (57 ± 15 g m⁻²). However, no significant differences were found.

Figure 5.7 Total mass of earthworm in CS6–CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.8 shows the total mass of earthworm for the Continental region (CS10a, CS10b, and CS11). For CS10a, it was similar for the different treatments, and no significant differences were found. Thus, total mass average values of 48 ± 25 , 40 ± 18 , and 68 ± 53 g m⁻² were obtained for the Ctrl, Biostim, and BiostimAdj treatments, respectively. For CS10b, the total earthworm masses were very low and similar for the three treatments here tested, with average values of 2 ± 4 , 4 ± 4 , and 3 ± 3 g m⁻² for the Ctrl, StripUndSow, and BroadUndSow treatments, respectively. Therefore, no statistical differences were found. Finally, for CS11, the lowest total mass was observed for the ExtWhe treatment (average

$7 \pm 5 \text{ g m}^{-2}$), while the highest was obtained for the DivExtWhe treatment (average $72 \pm 44 \text{ g m}^{-2}$). However, no significant differences were found.

Figure 5.8 Total mass of earthworm in CS10a–CS11 fields from the Continental region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figure 5.9 shows the total mass of earthworm for CS12 (Nemoral region). In this case, the lowest total mass was observed for the ConvConvTill treatment, with an average of $21 \pm 14 \text{ g m}^{-2}$, while very similar total masses were observed for the OrgConvTill and ConvNoTill treatments, with average values off 89 ± 12 and $88 \pm 27 \text{ g m}^{-2}$, respectively. No statistical differences were observed.

Figure 5.9 Total mass of earthworm in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Finally, Figure 5.10 shows the total mass of earthworm for the Boreal region (CS13, CS14a, CS14b, and CS15). For CS13, the total mass of earthworm was very similar for the three different treatments here tested, with average values of 17 ± 17 , 12 ± 14 , and 7 ± 11 g m⁻², for the Ctrl, CPMS, and FS treatments, respectively. Therefore, no statistical differences between the different treatments were observed. For CS14a, the total mass of earthworm was slightly higher for the Plough treatment (average 32 ± 23 g m⁻²) than for the Ctrl treatment (average 26 ± 21 g m⁻²). However, no statistical differences were found. For CS14b, the total earthworm masses were higher than those observed for CS14a, with average values of 247 ± 55 g m⁻² for the Ctrl treatment, and 146 ± 70 g m⁻² for the Plough treatment. Furthermore, no statistical differences between the two treatments were observed. Finally, for CS15, the Pha treatment gave rise to the highest total earthworm mass (average of 18 ± 18 g m⁻²), followed by the Rye treatment (average of 4 ± 8 g m⁻²) and, finally, by the Ctrl treatment (average of 2 ± 3 g m⁻²).

Figure 5.10 Total mass of earthworm in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

5.3.3 Earthworm species richness

The number of earthworm species for the control treatment, taking into account all case studies, varied from 0.1 ± 0.2 for CS15 and CS10b to 5.5 ± 2.1 for CS12. In addition, significant differences between the different case studies were found ($F=13.261$, $P=0.000$), following the next sequence: CS15 \approx CS10b < CS13 < CS11 \approx CS5 < CS14a \approx CS10a < CS7 \approx CS8 \approx CS14b \approx CS3 \approx CS4 \approx CS6 \approx CS9 < CS12. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, significant differences were also found ($F=20.431$, $P=0.000$), with the following sequence: Continental \approx Boreal < Lusitanian \approx Atlantic Central < Nemoral.

On the other hand, Figures 5.11 to 5.15 show the number of species found in the Lusitanian region (Figure 5.11), in the Atlantic Central region (Figure 5.12), in the Continental region (Figure 5.13), in the Nemoral region (Figure 5.14), and in the Boreal region (Figure 5.15).

In general, within each case study, no significant differences were found in the number of species between the different treatments, with the exception of case study CS3. For CS3, statistical differences were found between the different treatments ($F=18.524$, $P=0.000$), following the sequence Alt2OatVetch < Ctrl \approx Alt1Pea, with average values of 0.25 ± 0.5 , 2.25 ± 0.96 , and 3 ± 0.82 species, respectively.

Figure 5.11 Total number of earthworm species in CS3–CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.12 Total number of earthworm species in CS6–CS9 fields from the Atlantic Center region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.13 Total number of earthworm species in CS10–CS11 fields from the Continental region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figure 5.14 Total number of earthworm species in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.15 Total number of earthworm species in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Jitter boxplots are based on the raw data. For statistical comparisons, refer to the text. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

5.3.4 Abundance of ecological groups

In general, taking into account all case studies and the control treatments, it was obtained that endogenic species were the most abundant, with a mean value of 62.7 ± 68.1 individuals m^{-2} , followed by anecic species, with a mean value of 15.0 ± 18.0 individuals m^{-2} , while epigeic species were the least abundant (average of 0.6 ± 2.4 individuals m^{-2}). In fact, significant differences have been found ($F=36.357$, $P = 0.000$), with the sequence epigeic \approx anecic $<$ endogenic.

The abundance of endogenic species among the different case studies varied from 0 ± 0 individuals m^{-2} for CS5 to 177 ± 47 individuals m^{-2} for CS14b. In fact, statistical differences were obtained between the different case studies ($F=6.711$; $P=0.000$), following the sequence: $CS5 \approx CS10b \approx CS15 \approx CS4 \approx CS3 < CS11 \approx CS7 \approx CS14a < CS12 \approx CS10a \approx CS13 \approx CS6 \approx CS8 \approx CS9 \approx CS14b$. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed in the Atlantic Central region, with an average value of 102 ± 71 individuals m^{-2} , while the lowest abundance was observed in the Lusitanian region, with a mean value of 7 ± 12 individuals m^{-2} . However, grouping by region, no statistical differences were obtained. On the other hand, the abundance of anecic species was also variable between the different case studies, with case study CS14b presenting the highest abundance (average of 28 ± 17 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in case study CS5 (average of 1 ± 2 individuals m^{-2}). Grouping by regions, the Boreal region was the one with the lowest abundance of anecic species (average of 9 ± 15 individuals m^{-2}), while the Atlantic Center region was the one with the highest abundance (average of 26 ± 25 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were observed between regions. Finally, the abundance of epigeic species was very low (practically zero) in most of the case studies.

Figure 5.16 shows the abundance of endogenic species of earthworm for the Lusitanian region (CS3-CS5). For CS3, the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed for the Alt1Pea treatment (average of 37 ± 48 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the Alt2OatVetch treatment (average 37 ± 48 individuals m^{-2}). For CS4, the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed for the Barley 2 treatment (average of 11 ± 8 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the Barley 5 treatment (average 2 ± 2 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, for CCS5, no endogenic species were found in the Ctrl treatment, while the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed for the WheNoFa treatment (average of 8 ± 8 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were found between the different treatments in any of the three cases.

Figure 5.16 Abundance of endogenic species of earthworms in CS3–CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.17 shows the abundance of anecic species of earthworm for the Lusitanian region (CS3-CS5). For CS3, the highest abundance of anecic species was found in the Alt1Pea treatment (average of 37 ± 48 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the Alt2OatVetch treatment (average of 2 ± 4 individuals m^{-2}). On the other hand, for CS4, the highest abundance of anecic species was found in the Barley 5 treatment (average of 24 ± 35 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the Barley 1 treatment (average of 9 ± 5 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, for CS5, the Ctrl treatment was the one that presented a lower abundance of anecic species (average of 1 ± 2 individuals m^{-2}), while the WheNoFa treatment was the one that presented a higher abundance (17 ± 15 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were found between the different treatments in any of the three cases.

Figure 5.17 Abundance of anecic species of earthworms in CS3–CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.18 shows the abundance of epigeic species of earthworm for the Lusitanian region (CS3-CS5). In CS3 and CS5, no individuals of this species were found in any of the treatments. On the other hand, for CS4 the highest abundance of epigeic species was observed in the Barley 5 treatment (average of 32 ± 51 individual m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the Barley 1 (average of 5 ± 8 individuals m^{-2}) and Barley 4 (average of 5 ± 10 individuals m^{-2}) treatments. However, no statistical differences were found between the different treatments.

Figure 5.18 Abundance of epigeic species of earthworms in CS3–CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.19 shows the abundance of endogenic species of earthworm for the Atlantic Central region (CS6–CS9). For CS6, the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed for the FYM treatment (average of 181 ± 103 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the AFV treatment (average 82 ± 37 individuals m^{-2}). However, no statistical differences were observed between the different treatments. For CS7, in general, the abundance of endogenic species was lower than that observed for CS6. In CS7, the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed for the PhaEgClov treatment (average of 50 ± 22 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the Mix12 treatment (average of 30 ± 27 individuals m^{-2}). On the other hand, in CS8, in general, the abundance of endogenic species was higher than in CS6 and CS7. Furthermore, in CS8 significant differences were found between the different treatments ($F=11.016$, $P=0.001$), with the sequence: OrgInt \approx ConvInt \approx OrgExt $<$ ConvExt. Thus, the ConvExt treatment had the highest abundance of endogenic species (average 427 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, in CS9, the highest abundance was found for the Ferm treatment (average 238 ± 65 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the Ctrl treatment (145 ± 89 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were found for CS9 between the different treatments.

Figure 5.19 Abundance of endogenic species of earthworms in CS6–CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

On the other hand, Figure 5.20 shows the abundance of anecic species of earthworm for the Atlantic Central region (CS6–CS9). For CS6, the AFVFYM treatment was the one that presented a higher abundance of anecic species, with an average value of 121 ± 51 individuals m^{-2} , while the AFVbrFYM treatment was the one that resulted in a lower presence of anecic species, with an average value of 32 ± 34 individuals m^{-2} . Despite these observed differences, no statistical differences between the different treatments were found. For CS7, the highest abundance of anecic species was observed for the Mix5 treatment (average of 59 ± 24 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was obtained with the Mix12 treatment (average of 26 ± 11 individuals m^{-2}).

However, no statistical differences between the different treatments were observed. On the contrary, for CS8, significant differences were found between the different treatments ($F = 5.236$, $P = 0.015$), following the sequence $\text{OrgExt} < \text{OrgInt} \approx \text{ConvExt} \approx \text{ConvInt}$, with the OrgExt treatment having the lowest abundance (average of 1 ± 3 individuals m^{-2}) and the ConvInt treatment presenting the highest abundance, with an average value of 19 ± 9 individuals m^{-2} . Finally, for CS9, the highest abundance of anecic species was obtained for the FYM treatment (average of 27 ± 17 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the Ctrl treatment (average of 5 ± 8 individuals m^{-2}). However, no statistical differences were obtained.

Figure 5.20 Abundance of anecic species of earthworms in CS6–CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.21 shows the abundance of epigeic species of earthworm for the Atlantic Central region (CS6-CS9). No epigeic species of earthworm have been found in the Atlantic Central region.

Figure 5.21 Abundance of epigeic species of earthworms in CS6–CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.22 shows the abundance of endogenic species of earthworm for the Continental region (CS10-CS11). Within the Continental region, CS10a was the case study where the highest abundance of endogenic species was found, compared to those observed for CS10b and CS11. In addition, for CS10a, the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed for the BiostimADj treatment, with an

average value of 123 ± 39 individuals m^{-2} , while the lowest abundance was observed in the Ctrl treatment (average of 81 ± 30 individuals m^{-2}). On the other hand, for CS10b, the abundance of endogenic species was very low and similar among the different treatments, with average values ranging between 3 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment and 8 ± 7 individuals m^{-2} for the BroadUndSow treatment. Finally, for CS11, the highest abundance of endogenic species was observed for the DivExtWhe treatment (average of 57 ± 51 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was obtained for the Ctrl treatment (average of 35 ± 19 individuals m^{-2}). No significant differences were found between the different treatments for any case study of the Continental region.

Figure 5.22 Abundance of endogenic species of earthworms in CS10–CS11 fields from the Continental region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figure 5.23 shows the abundance of anecic species of earthworm for the Continental region (CS10–CS11). For CS10a, the highest abundance of anecic species was observed for the BiostimAdj treatment, with an average value of 29 ± 22 individuals m^{-2} , while the lowest abundance was observed in the Biostim treatment (average 17 ± 11 individuals m^{-2}). However, no statistical differences were obtained between the different treatments. On the other hand, for CS10b, no individuals of the anecic species were observed. Finally, for CS11, significant differences have been found ($F = 4.973$, $P = 0.035$), with the sequence ExtWhe (average of 15 ± 17 individuals m^{-2}) < Ctrl (average of 17 ± 12 individuals m^{-2}) \approx DivExtWhe (average of 47 ± 19 individuals m^{-2}).

Figure 5.23 Abundance of anecic species of earthworms in CS10–CS11 fields from the Continental region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figure 5.24 shows the abundance of epigeic species of earthworm for the Continental region (CS10–CS11). For this region, no individuals of epigeic species were found.

Figure 5.24 Abundance of epigeic species of earthworms in CS10–CS11 fields from the Continental region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figures 5.25, 5.26, and 5.27 show the abundance of endogenic, anecic, and epigeic species of earthworm for the Nemoral region (CS12), respectively. The highest abundance of endogenic species was obtained for the OrgConvTill treatment (average of 167 ± 87 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the ConvNoTill treatment (average of 41 ± 29 individuals m^{-2}).

On the other hand, regarding anecic species, the OrgConvTill and ConvNoTill treatments were the ones with the highest abundance, with average values of 61 ± 23 and 61 ± 18 individuals m^{-2} , respectively, while the lowest abundance was observed for the ConvConvTill treatment (average of 17 ± 14 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, regarding epigeic species, similar to endogenic species, the highest abundance was found in the OrgConvTill treatment (average of 24 ± 1 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in the ConvConvTill treatment (average of 4 ± 5 individuals m^{-2}).

Figure 5.25 Abundance of endogenic species of earthworms in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.26 Abundance of anecic species of earthworms in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.27 Abundance of epigeic species of earthworms in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.28 shows the abundance of endogenic species of earthworm for the Boreal region (CS13- CS15). For CS13, the highest abundance of endogenic species was obtained in the Ctrl treatment (average of 83 ± 83 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the FS treatment (average of 32 ± 54 individuals m^{-2}). Regarding CS14a, the abundance observed for the Plough treatment (average of 57 ± 399 individuals m^{-2}) was slightly higher than that observed for the control treatment (average of 47 ± 39 individuals m^{-2}). Similarly, for CS14b, the abundance of endogenic species observed for the Plough treatment (average of 212 ± 51 individuals m^{-2}) was also slightly higher than that observed for the Ctrl treatment (average of 177 ± 47 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, for CS15 the abundance of endogenic species was very low, with mean values varying between 4 ± 5 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment and 8 ± 10 individuals m^{-2} for the Pha treatment. Despite these observed differences, no significant differences were found between the different treatments in any of the cases.

Figure 5.28 Abundance of endogenic species of earthworms in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

Figure 5.29 shows the abundance of anecic species of earthworm for the Boreal region (CS13-CS15). In CS13 no anecic species were found. For CS14a, the abundance of anecic species was higher in the Ctrl treatment (average of 7 ± 7 individuals m^{-2}) than in the Plough treatment (average of 0 ± 0 individuals m^{-2}). Regarding CS14b, the abundance was also higher in the Ctrl treatment (average of 28 ± 17 individuals m^{-2}) than in the Plough treatment (average of 17 ± 14 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, for CS15, in the Ctrl and Rye treatments, no anecic species were found, while in the Pha treatment an average abundance of 3 ± 6 individuals m^{-2} was obtained. In addition, it should be noted that no statistical

differences were found between the different treatments.

Figure 5.29 Abundance of anecic species of earthworms in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

Figure 5.30 shows the abundance of epigeic species of earthworm for the Boreal region (CS13-CS15). For CS13 and CS15, no individuals of epigeic species were found in any of the treatments. On the other hand, for CS14a and 14b, some individuals were found, but the abundance was very low, and no statistical differences were found between the different treatments.

Figure 5.30 Abundance of epigeic species of earthworms in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

5.3.5 Abundance of age classes

In general, taking into account all case studies and the control treatments, significant differences between the different age classes have been found ($F=15.116$; $P=0.000$), with the sequence subadults < adults < juveniles, obtaining an average abundance of 46.0 ± 53.6 individuals m^{-2} for juveniles, 26.7 ± 29.4 individuals m^{-2} for adults, and 8.5 ± 15.8 individuals m^{-2} for subadults.

The abundance of adults among the different case studies varied from 1 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} for CS15 to 91 ± 25 individuals m^{-2} for CS14b. In addition, significant differences were obtained ($F=6.005$, $P=0.000$), with the following sequence: $CS15 \approx CS10b \approx CS5 \approx CS11 \approx CS12 \approx CS4 \approx CS13 \approx CS8 \approx CS7 \approx CS14a \approx CS3 < CS10a \approx CS9 \approx CS6 \approx CS14b$. Grouping the case studies of each pedoclimatic region, the highest abundance of adults was observed in the Atlantic Central region, with an average value of 36 ± 26 individuals m^{-2} , followed by the Boreal region, with an average value of 33 ± 40 individuals m^{-2} , the Continental region, with an average of 20 ± 24 individuals m^{-2} , the Lusitanian region, with an average of 15 ± 18 individuals m^{-2} , and, finally, the Nemoral region, with an average of 13 ± 6 individuals m^{-2} . However, it should be noted that these differences are not significant. On the other hand, the abundance of subadults was also variable between the different case studies, with case study CS14b presenting the highest abundance of subadults (average of 36 ± 10 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed in case study CS4 (average of 0 ± 0 individuals m^{-2}). Grouping by regions, the Nemoral region was the one with the lowest abundance of subadults (average of 0 ± 0 individuals m^{-2}), while the Boreal region was the one with the highest abundance (average of 14 ± 17 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were observed between regions. Finally, the abundance of juveniles was high and very variable between the different case studies. In fact, significant differences have been found ($F=7.306$, $P=0.000$), obtaining the following sequence: $CS10b \approx CS3 \approx CS15 \approx CS5 \approx CS4 \approx CS14a \approx CS11 \approx CS7 \approx CS10a < CS13 \approx CS9 \approx CS6 \approx CS12 \approx CS8 \approx CS14b$. In this sense, the highest abundance of juveniles was observed in CS14b, with a mean abundance of 136 ± 68 individuals m^{-2} , while the lowest was observed in CS10b, with a mean value of 0 ± 0 individuals m^{-2} . Grouping by regions, the abundance of juveniles was also quite variable, with mean abundances ranging from 4 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} for the Lusitanian region to 80 ± 53 individuals m^{-2} for the Atlantic Central region. In fact, significant differences were found, with the sequence $Lusitanian < Continental \approx Boreal \approx Nemoral \approx Atlantic Central$.

Figure 5.31 shows the abundance of adults for the Lusitanian region (CS3-CS5). For CS3, the highest abundance of adults was observed for the Ctrl treatment (average of 25 ± 26 Individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the Alt2OatVetch treatment (average 2 ± 4 individuals m^{-2}). For CS4, the highest abundance of adults was observed for the Barley 2 treatment (average of 29 ± 8 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the Barley 1 treatment (average 14 ± 11 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, for CS5, the highest abundance of adults was observed in the WheNoFA treatment (average of 12 ± 12 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the Ctrl treatment (average 1 ± 2 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences have been found between the different treatments for the case studies from the Lusitanian region.

Figure 5.31 Abundance of adult earthworms in CS3-CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.32 shows the abundance of subadults for the Lusitanian region (CS3-CS5). For CS3, the Alt1Pea treatment presented the highest abundance of subadults (average of 35 ± 7 individuals m^{-2}), while the Ctrl treatment had a much lower abundance (average 3 ± 4 individuals m^{-2}) and the Alt2OatVetch treatment did not have any individual. For CS4, the abundance of subadults was very low in all treatments, with the Barley 5 treatment having the highest abundance, with an average value of 5 ± 4 individuals m^{-2} . Similarly, for CS5, the abundance of subadults was also very low. Thus, the highest abundance was observed in the WheNoFa treatment (average 3 ± 5 individuals m^{-2}), while no subadults were found in the Ctrl treatment. However, no significant differences have been found between the different treatments for these case studies.

Figure 5.32 Abundance of subadults earthworms in CS3-CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.33 shows the abundance of juveniles for the Lusitanian region (CS3-CS5). For CS3, the highest abundance of juveniles earthworm was found in the Alt1Pesa treatment, with an average value of 33 ± 30 individuals m^{-2} , while the Ctrl and Alt2OatVeach treatments presented a very low abundance, with average values of 2 ± 2 and 0 ± 0 individuals m^{-2} , respectively. For CS4, the highest abundance of juveniles was observed in the Barley 5 treatment (average of 35 ± 52 individuals m^{-2}), while the Barley 1 and Barley 4 treatments were the ones that resulted in a lower abundance of juveniles, with average values of 6 ± 2 and 5 ± 5 individuals m^{-2} , respectively. Finally, for CS5, the lowest abundance was found in the Ctrl treatment (average of 3 ± 5 individuals m^{-2}), while the highest abundance was observed for the WheNoFa treatment (11 ± 10 individuals m^{-2}). However, as observed for adults and subadults, for juveniles no significant differences were found between the different treatments in any of the case studies from the Lusitanian region.

Figure 5.33 Abundance of juveniles earthworms in CS3-CS5 fields from the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional crop rotation (wheat) after crop harvest; Alt1Pea, alternative crop rotation 1 (pea) after crop harvest; Alt2OatVetch, alternative crop rotation 2 (oat+vetch during winter and trap crop during spring) after crop harvest; Barley1, conventional P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley2, mycorrhiza + half P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley3, mycorrhiza + no P fertilization after crop harvest; Barley4, half P fertilization after crop harvest; no P fertilization after crop harvest; Ctrl, pest alert system (wheat) after crop harvest; WheConvFA, conventional fungicide application (wheat) after crop harvest; WheNoFA, no fungicide application (Wheat) after crop harvest.

Figure 5.34 shows the abundance of adults earthworm for the Atlantic Central region (CS6-CS9). For CS6, the abundance of adults was similar for the different treatments here tested, with the FYM treatment having the highest abundance (average of 67 ± 48 individuals m^{-2}), while the AFV treatment had the lowest abundance (average of 32 ± 36 individuals m^{-2}). Similarly, for CS7, the abundance of adults was also similar among the different treatments, ranging from 23 ± 17 individuals m^{-2} for the Mix12 treatment to 35 ± 19 individuals m^{-2} for the PhaEgClov treatment. For CS8, the abundance of adults was also similar among the different treatments, with the ConvInt treatment having the lowest abundance, with an average value of 19 ± 20 individuals m^{-2} , while the OrgInt treatment had the highest abundance (average of 46 ± 24 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, for CS9, the lowest abundance was

observed in the Ctrl treatment (average of 49 ± 20 individuals m^{-2}), while the highest abundance was observed for the Ferm treatment (average 93 ± 37 individuals m^{-2}). However, it should be noted that no significant differences were found between the different treatments for any of the case studies in the Central Atlantic region.

Figure 5.34 Abundance of adults earthworms in CS6-CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.35 shows the abundance of subadults earthworms for the Atlantic Central region (CS6-CS9). In all case studies from this region, the abundance of subadults earthworms was very similar among the different treatments here tested. Thus, for CS6, the abundance of subadults ranged from 10 ± 13

to 25 ± 9 individuals m^{-2} for the AFV and AFVFYM treatments, respectively; for CS7, the abundance was practically equal and very low for the different treatments, with average values that oscillated between 3 and 4 individuals m^{-2} ; for CS8, the lowest abundance was observed for the ConvInt treatment (average of 6 ± 6 individuals m^{-2}), while the highest abundance was observed for the ConvExt treatment (average of 40 ± 6 individuals m^{-2}); Finally, for CS9, the abundance of subadults ranged between 15 ± 13 individuals m^{-2} for the Comp treatment and 41 ± 28 individuals m^{-2} for the FYM treatment. As expected, no significant differences were found for any of the case studies from the Central Atlantic region.

Figure 5.35 Abundance of subadults earthworms in CS6-CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.36 shows the abundance of juveniles earthworms for the Atlantic Central region (CS6-CS9). For CS6, the lowest abundance of juveniles was found in the Ctrl treatment, with a mean value of 77 ± 43 individuals m^{-2} , while the highest abundance was observed for the AFVFYM treatment, with a mean value of 216 ± 68 individuals m^{-2} . Despite these variations, statistical differences between the different treatments have not been found. For CS6, the lowest abundances were observed in the Ctrl and Mix12 treatments, with average values of 33 ± 22 and 29 ± 18 individuals m^{-2} , respectively. In contrast, the highest abundance was observed in the Mix5 treatment (average of 63 ± 29 individuals m^{-2}). In CS6 no significant differences between the different treatments have been observed either. However, for CS8, significant differences were found ($F=10.030$, $P=0.001$), with the sequence: OrgInt \approx OrgExt \approx ConvInt $<$ ConvExt. In this sense, for the ConvExt treatment, a mean value of 349 ± 126 individuals m^{-2} was observed, while for the remaining treatments, the mean abundance of juveniles was lower than 135 individuals m^{-2} . Finally, for CS9, the control treatment was the one with the lowest abundance of juveniles (average of 74 ± 51 individuals m^{-2}), while the highest abundance was observed in the Ferm treatment (average of 133 ± 46 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were

found between the different treatments.

Figure 5.36 Abundance of juveniles earthworms in CS6-CS9 fields from the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, BAU; FYM, BAU + FYM; AFV, AFV; AFVFYM, AFV + FYM; AFVbrFYM, BAU + brown FYM; brFYM, BAU + brown FYM; PhaEgClov, Phacelia/Egyptian clover; Mix5, 5-Species mixture; Mix12, 12-Species mixture; OrgInt, organic intensive; OrgExt, organic extensive; ConvInt, conventional intensive; ConvExt, conventional extensive; Comp, compost; Ferm, fermented organic material.

Figure 5.37 shows the abundance of adults earthworms for the Continental region (CS10-CS11). For CS10a, the abundance of adults was very similar between the different treatments, ranging from 39 ± 21 individuals m^{-2} for the Biostim treatment to 56 ± 17 individuals m^{-2} for the BiostimAdj treatment. For CS10b, the abundance of adults was very low, with mean values ranging between 1 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment and 4 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} for the BroadUndSow treatment. Finally, for CS11, the ExtWhe treatment was the one that presented the lowest abundance of adults (average of 3 ± 3 individuals m^{-2}), while the DivExtWhe treatment was the one that presented the highest abundance (25 ± 22 individuals m^{-2}). It should be noted that no significant differences were found between the

different treatments for any of the case studies from the Continental region.

Figure 5.37 Abundance of adults earthworms in CS10-CS11 fields from the Continental region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figure 5.38 shows the abundance of subadults earthworms for the Continental region (CS10-CS11). In general, the abundance of subadults earthworms was very low in the Continental region. In fact, in CS10b, no subadults earthworms were found. For CS10a, the abundance of subadults ranged from 5 ± 4 individuals m^{-2} for the BiostimAdj treatment to 11 ± 8 individuals m^{-2} for the Biostim treatment. Finally, for CS11, the lowest abundance of subadults was found in the Ctrl treatment (average of 1 ± 3 individuals m^{-2}), while the highest abundance was observed for the ExtWhe treatment (5 ± 4 individuals m^{-2}). No significant differences between the different treatments were found in any of the case studies from the Continental region.

Figure 5.38 Abundance of subadults earthworms in CS10-CS11 fields from the Continental region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite

Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figure 5.39 show the abundance of juveniles earthworms for the Continental region (CS10-CS11). For CS10a, significant differences between the different treatments were found ($F=6.829$, $P=0.016$), with the sequence $Ctrl \approx Biostim < BiostimAdj$, ranging the average abundance of juveniles between 39 ± 14 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment to 73 ± 19 individuals m^{-2} for the BiostimAdj treatment. On the other hand, in CS10b, the abundance of juveniles earthworms was very low, ranging the average values between 0 ± 0 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment and 4 individuals m^{-2} for the StripUndSow and BroadUndSow treatments. As expected, for CS10b, no significant differences between treatments were found. Finally, for CS11, the lowest abundance of juveniles was observed in the Ctrl treatment (average of 28 ± 5 individuals m^{-2}), while the highest was found in the DivExtWhe treatment, with an average value of 64 ± 29 individuals m^{-2} . However, significant differences between the different treatments have not been found.

Figure 5.39 Abundance of juveniles earthworms in CS10-CS11 fields from the Continental region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation + reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation + Use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive (Kantor) + plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) + plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) + reduction of fungicides; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing; ExtWhe, extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows no pesticides); DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming (wide seed rows clover undersowing no pesticides).

Figures 5.40, 5.41, and 5.42 show the abundance of adults, subadults, and juveniles earthworms, respectively, for the Nemoral region (CS12). For adults abundance, significant differences were found among the different treatments, following the sequence $ConvConvTill < ConvNoTill \approx OrgConvTill$, obtaining average values of 13 ± 6 , 41 ± 8 , and 44 ± 6 individuals m^{-2} for the ConvConvTill, ConvNoTill, and OrgConvTill treatments, respectively. On the other hand, no subadults earthworms were found for any of the treatments in CS12. Finally, regarding juveniles earthworms, the highest abundance was observed for the OrgConvTill treatment, with an average value of 208 ± 69 individuals m^{-2} , while the

lowest abundance was observed for the ConvNoTill treatment (average of 68 ± 21 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were found between the different treatments.

Figure 5.40 Abundance of adult earthworms in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.41 Abundance of subadults earthworms in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.42 Abundance of juveniles earthworms in CS12 fields from the Nemoral region. Abbreviations: OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; ConvConvTill, conventional farming with conventional tillage 2; ConvNoTill, organic farming with conventional tillage 1; FieldEdge, field edge.

Figure 5.43 shows the abundance of adults earthworms in the Boreal region (CS13-CS15). For CS13, the abundance of adults was very similar and low for the different treatments here tested, with mean values ranging between 8 individuals m^{-2} for the CPMS and FS treatments to 15 ± 16 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment. For CS14a, the abundance of adults was also very similar between the two treatments here tested, with mean values of 24 ± 25 and 21 ± 19 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl and the Plough treatments, respectively. Similarly, for CS14b no differences were observed between both treatments, obtaining an average abundance of 91 ± 25 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment and 111 ± 48 individuals m^{-2} for the Plough treatment. Finally, for CS15, the abundance of adults was low and similar among the different treatments, with the Pha treatment giving rise to a higher abundance (average of 7 ± 5 individuals m^{-2}) compared to the Ctrl and Rye treatments, with average values of 1 ± 3 individuals m^{-2} . It should be noted that no statistical differences were found between the different treatments for any of the case studies from the Boreal region.

Figure 5.43 Abundance of adults earthworms in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

Figure 5.44 shows the abundance of subadult earthworms in the Boreal region (CS13-CS15). For CS13, the highest abundance of subadults was observed for the CPMS treatment (average of 11 ± 13 individuals m^{-2}), while the lowest abundance was observed for the FS treatment (average of 1 ± 3 individuals m^{-2}). However, no significant differences were found between the different treatments. For CS14a, the abundance of subadults was very similar between both treatments, with average values of 15 ± 15 and 20 ± 8 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl and the Plough treatments, respectively. Therefore, no significant differences were found between both treatments. On the other hand, for CS14b, significant differences were found, with the Ctrl treatment presenting a significantly higher abundance

(average of 36 ± 10 individuals m^{-2}) than the Plough treatment (average of 12 ± 3 individuals m^{-2}). Finally, for CS15, no subadults earthworm was found in any of the treatments.

Figure 5.44 Abundance of subadults earthworms in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

Figure 5.45 shows the abundance of juveniles earthworms in the Boreal region (CS13-CS15). For CS13, the abundance of juveniles was similar for the different treatments, with mean values ranging from 23 ± 39 individuals m^{-2} for the FS treatment to 59 ± 50 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment. Similarly, in CS14a, the abundance of juveniles was equal for both treatments, with mean values of 23 ± 17 and

23 ± 35 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl and Plough treatments, respectively. For CS14b, the abundance was also very similar between the two treatments, with mean values of 136 ± 68 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl treatment and 117 ± 43 individuals m^{-2} for the Plough treatment. Finally, for CS15, the abundance of juveniles earthworms was very low and similar for the three treatments here tested, with average values of 3 ± 3 , 4 ± 8 , and 5 ± 11 individuals m^{-2} for the Ctrl, Pha, and Rye treatments, respectively.

Figure 5.45 Abundance of juveniles earthworms in CS13-CS15 fields from the Boreal region. Abbreviations: Ctrl, control without amendments after the early potato harvest; FS, wood fiber sludge (zero fiber) amendment after the early potato harvest; CPMS, composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fiber" amendment after the early potato harvest; Plough, organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat; Ctrl, organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat; Pha, phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest.

5.3.6 Conclusions

The Central Atlantic region was the one that presented the highest abundance of earthworms, with an average value of 128 ± 77 individuals m^{-2} , followed by the Boreal, Nemoral, Continental, and Lusitanian regions. Finally, it should be noted that in the Mediterranean South region, no earthworms have been found. Regarding earthworm masses, the highest total mass of earthworms was observed in the Boreal region, with an average total mass of 73 ± 108 g m^{-2} , followed by the Atlantic Central, Continental, Nemoral, and Lusitanian regions, with total mass averages of 32 ± 25 , 31 ± 36 , 21 ± 14 , and 18 ± 32 g m^{-2} , respectively.

Regarding earthworm diversity, the Nemoral region was the one with the highest species richness. In fact, significant differences between the different regions have been found, following the sequence Continental \approx Boreal < Lusitanian \approx Atlantic Central < Nemoral. On the other hand, regarding the different species, taking into account all regions, significant differences have also been found, with the sequence epigeic \approx anecic < endogenic. Regarding abundance of age classes, juvenile earthworms were the most abundant class with an average value of 46.0 individuals m^{-2} , followed by adults, with an average value of 26.7 individuals m^{-2} and , finally, subadults, with an average abundance of 8.5 individuals m^{-2} .

Finally, it should be noted that no clear relationships were found between the abundance and diversity of earthworms and the different agricultural systems tested here, so the differences found in terms of of abundance and diversity could be mainly due to climatic and geographical factors.

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ANNEXES-tab

Table A1. Average size of sample libraries (raw reads) and analysed reads (filtered) in different monitoring years for each case study in different region.

TABLE 2.1			
REGION	CASE STUDY-YEAR	RAW READS	FILTERED READS
Mediterranean South	CS1-20 ¹⁾	268 754	165 106
	CS1-21	114 984	107 609
	CS1-22	99 703	92 716
	CS1-23	119 838	113 246
	CS2-20 ¹⁾	72 046	68 012
	CS2-21	80 144	76 681
	CS2-22	88 040	83 524
Lusitanian	CS3-21 ¹⁾	122 169	115 455
	CS3-21b	113 869	109 192
	CS3-22	109 601	102 840
	CS3-23	111 504	108 062
	CS4-21 ¹⁾	122 808	114 415
	CS4-21b	107 958	102 165
	CS4-22	113 830	104 995
	CS4-23	115 913	111 355
	CS5-21 ¹⁾	119 762	111 258
	CS5-21b	112 569	106 655
	CS5-22	115 486	106 978
	CS5-23	116 551	112 301
Atlantic Central	CS6-19 ¹⁾	253 085	158 432
	CS6-20	260 306	162 953
	CS6-22	103 332	93 782
	CS6-23	105 165	100 089
	CS7-20 ¹⁾	254 983	155 311
	CS7-21	116 498	109 890
	CS7-22	104 316	95 366
	CS7-23	110 934	106 524
	CS8-20 ¹⁾	251 671	158 719
	CS8-20b	245 671	155 092
	CS8-21	118 158	112 160
	CS8-23	107 687	103690
	CS9-21 ^{a)}	118 784	112 320
CS9-22	109 783	101 438	

	CS9-23	115 363	110 700
Continental	CS10a-21 ¹⁾	126 156	115 322
	CS10a-21b	120 079	108 813
	CS10a-22	93 546	86 409
	CS10a-23	119 751	115 560
	CS10b-21 ¹⁾	114 824	105 435
	CS10b-21b	105 750	95 530
	CS10b-22	95 851	88 014
	CS10b-23	130 795	125 168
	CS11-20 ¹⁾	254 806	158 746
	CS11-21	102 227	93 972
	CS11-22	103 332	94 511
	CS11-23	120 356	113 733
Nemoral	CS12-20 ¹⁾	253 921	156 300
	CS12-21	107 861	101 083
	CS12-22	107 502	98 089
	CS12-23	107 720	103 086
Boreal	CS13-20	255 321	165 552
	CS13-21	121 520	115 018
	CS13-22	98 885	92 417
	CS14a-20	246 531	157 122
	CS14a-21	100 785	86 727
	CS14a-22	88 365	82 375
	CS14b-21	110 852	99 230
	CS14b-22	92 249	87 073
	CS14b-23	106 840	102 187
	CS15-20	240 241	152 390
	CS15-21	113 494	107 631
	CS15-22	90 560	84 258

1) samples to represent initial situation before the actual case study treatments, 2) according to raw reads, 3) after the first filtering steps (assembly, quality and chimera filtering, clustering and taxonomical annotation)